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APPROVAL SHEET

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“Per angusta ad augusta” – Through difficulties to honors. – Poet Virgil

ABSTRACT

Pampanga has a reputation for being well-known as the Culinary Capital of the Philippines, famous for its exquisite and mouthwatering dishes such as the “Sisig”, “Camaru”, “Betute” and many more.

However, Pampanga is so much more than just a food capital, it is also home to a myriad of history, arts, music, dance, literature, religious celebrations, and cultural festivals, making it a worthy tourist destination for people to explore and experience.

Unfortunately, despite this, Pampanga currently does not have a well-developed place/platform dedicated to honoring, preserving and promoting the Kapampangan culture.

This lack of a central facility for accommodating both the tourists and locals' needs for cultural immersion and participation, celebration, recreation, education, and commerce is the main problem that the proposed project wishes to address.

“Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex”, is a cultural complex that would serve as the cradle or formal central hub of Pampanga for social, cultural, and religious celebrations, preservation, and promotion, embodying the Kapampangan cultural identity as an architectural icon.

This project aims to provide complete facilities that can accommodate the Kapampangan’s need for social and cultural activities, notably the Giant Lantern Festival.

Moreover, the proposed project is beneficial to the province in boosting its tourism, allowing for cultural exchange, and in promoting a sense of community among the Kapampangan.

Indu will become an iconic landmark for Pampanga, and can serve as a blueprint for other provinces who wishes to develop a cultural complex in dedication to honoring the past, celebrating the present and preserving the future of our cultural heritage.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

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1.7 ARCHITECTURAL AND DESIGN CONCEPT

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The word "community" is no stranger to man. It is a familiar word often heard, read, and even spoken by people of different tongues. The word seems simple, natural, and human that it can be defined in many ways. According to Chavis & Lee (2015), a community is defined as a feeling and a relationship among people. Another stated that "a community is a group of people who share an identity-forming narrative" (Center for Public Impact, 2021). However, among all its definitions, a community's complete and well-known meaning is that it is defined as a group of people living together in the same location and sharing common values, cultures, and traditions. These values, cultures, and traditions make a community unique. It is the essence, the central heart, that bonds a society together and forms a community's sense of identity.

The Philippines is a country from Southeast Asia and is home to a culturally diverse society with an estimated 14 to 17 million Indigenous People or IPs that belong to 110 ethnolinguistic groups due to the influences of the Spanish, Americans, Chinese, and Japanese colonizers. The majority of them are concentrated in Northern Luzon (Cordillera Administrative Region, 33%) and Mindanao (61%), while others are located in the Visayas Region (UNDP, 2013).

Central Luzon, also known as Region III, is one of the regions in the Philippines located between Northern Luzon and Manila (the Capital of the Philippines), with a topography of mountains, volcanoes, lush farmlands, and natural harbors. It is one of the leading growth regions in the Philippines, strategically located at the heart of Asia, making it an important trading center and transportation terminal for different products and services (Embuscado, 2021). More than being a significant contributor of goods and services for

the Philippines, Central Luzon's pride is in its richness in historical heritage and lively traditions, being the cradle of some of the nation's noble heroes and most significant artists, and home to festivities, celebrations, and religious rites, such as the Carabao Festival and Obando Fertility Rites in Bulacan, Mango Festival in Zambales and Giant Lantern in Pampanga (Embuscado, 2021).

In the plains of Central Luzon lies the province of Pampanga, home of the Kapampangans. Pampanga is known as the "Culinary Capital of the Philippines." It is located in the central parts of Region III and is bounded by neighboring provinces such as Tarlac and Nueva Ecija (North), Bulacan (East), Bataan (Southwest), and Zambales (West). Its terrain is relatively flat, with a land area of 2,180.68 sq. km and one distinct mountain, Mount Arayat (Provincial Government of Pampanga, 2013).

Though well-known for its exquisite cuisines, the province of Pampanga offers so much more. Pampanga is also home to a rich historical background of events, people, and cultural heritage primarily in art, music, dance, literature, religious celebrations and festivities, with 19 municipalities and three cities, each celebrating its unique social and cultural background (CMCI, n.d.).

It is no secret that Pampanga is home to a myriad of mouthwatering and iconic food, from savory dishes such as the Sizzling Sisig, Bulanglang, Adobo, and Burung Asan to sweet delicacies Panecillos de San Nicolas, Kalame Duman, and Ensaimada Antigo to exotic dishes like the Kamaru and Betute (Manabat, 2024).

However, Pampanga is so much more than a food capital. Kapampangans also take pride in their art, such as the "Parul" (San Fernando), "Kuran and Pasu" (Sto. Tomas), "Pukpuk" (Betis & Apalit), "Dukit" (Betis), "Burarul" (Angeles), "Dase" (Candaba), "Kupia" (Apalit), "Santos" (Betis, Macabebe, Bacolor & Apalit), "Gitara" (Guagua), "Gawang Pande" (Apalit) and many more (CKS Admin, 2018).

Besides their art, Kapampangans are also well-known for their music, such as Kapampangan folk songs "Atin Cu Pung Singsing," "Atsing Rosing," "Aro Katimyas Na Nitang Dalaga," and "O Patag A Bunduk" (CKS Admin, 2018). Theatrical performances where musicians, composers, dancers, and actors come alive are also part of Pampanga's cultural heritage. An excellent example of a Kapampangan performance is the zarzuela, a play combining spoken dialogue and song. "Ing Managpe" is an example of a famous Kapampangan zarzuela written by Mariano Proceso Pabalan Byron from Bacolor. Even in the literary arts of oral and written literature, the Kapampangans are never far behind; Aurelio Tolentino, Francisco Makabulos, and Juan Crisostomo Soto are some notable examples of famous Kapampangan writers (Sunnexdesk, 2018).

Furthermore, the Kapampangan also celebrates several religious celebrations such as "San Pedro Cutud Lenten Rites" (San Fernando), "Apung Iru Fluvial Festival" (Apalit), "Fiestang Kuliat" (Angeles City), "Kuraldal" (Sasmuan), and "Apung Monica Fluvial Procession" (Minalin) (Sison, 2024).

More than religious celebrations part of the Kapampangan culture is also celebrating a variety of festivals. One is the famous "Ligligang Parul," or Giant Lantern Festival of San Fernando City, the capital of Pampanga, also known as the Christmas Capital of the

Philippines. Other festivals include the "Sinukwan Festival" (San Fernando), "Pyestang Tugak" (San Fernando), "Sisig Festival" (Angeles City), "Makatapak Festival" (Bacolor), "Duman Festival" (Sta. Rita), "Sabuaga Festival" (Sto. Tomas), "Aguman Sanduk Festival" (Minalin) and many more (Sison, 2024).

These are merely an introduction to Pampanga's rich and diverse historical and cultural world, and it is no surprise that because of this, Pampanga was developed to become a hub for tourism and commerce. The construction of malls such as SM and Robinsons, different shopping centers, restaurants, and even the development of New Clark City and several other entertainment hubs made Pampanga a well-known tourist spot and destination (jontotheworld, 2022).

Since tourists from different parts of the country are interested in visiting Pampanga to immerse themselves in their historical and cultural heritage, there is a need to accommodate several tourists. Moreover, Pampanga has a myriad of history, culture, and talent, and it is only fitting to have a dedicated place where the local Kapampangans can preserve, proudly showcase, and celebrate their cultural richness in history, arts, music, dance, literature, cuisine, religious celebrations, and festivals.

With this in mind, proposing a Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex addressed the tourists' and locals' need for cultural preservation, promotion, education, and celebration. Moreover, having a cultural complex would also help boost the tourism of Pampanga and serve as an architectural icon for the Kapampangans' cultural identity.

1.2 RATIONALE, SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY AND JUSTIFICATION

1.2.1 RATIONALE

The proposed project is entitled "Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex. " It is a cultural complex that would serve as the melting pot or formal central hub of Pampanga for social, cultural, and religious celebrations, preservation, and promotion and embody the Kapampangan cultural identity as an architectural icon. The project proposal is located in the heart and capital of Pampanga, known as the Christmas Capital of the Philippines, the City of San Fernando.

The proposed project's main goal is to host the Giant Lantern Festival of San Fernando City. Hosting the said event is the project's main highlight. Moreover, it aims to cater and house Pampanga's rich history and its well-known cultural heritage in culinary, arts, music, dance, literature, religious celebrations, and festivals from its municipalities and cities. With this, facilities and spaces such as a main plaza, an interactive museum with full dome cinema and library, a theater for performing arts, a cultural convention center and a commercial building will be proposed to support the project. Furthermore, a landscape food park, utilities, and parking areas were included in the proposed project. The proposed project's target users are the local Kapampangan and tourists from all walks of life, where locals and tourists can experience and immerse themselves in Pampanga's rich history and unique cultural background.

The project proposal entitled "Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex" is a dedicated place where the Kapampangan culture is alive and celebrated. Its name, "Indu," was inspired by the Kapampangan folk song entitled "Atin Cu Pung

Singsing," a song about a mother who inherited her child a precious ring; even though she kept it very close, lost it somehow, thus the lyrics "Mewala ya it, eku amalayan." This song inspired this study to propose a project that embodies the Kapampangan spirit to revive, preserve, and celebrate Pampanga's rich cultural heritage and not let it be forgotten and lost in time.

1.2.2 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex is a proposed project that plays a significant role in the cultural preservation and promotion of the Kapampangan cultural heritage. Other significance of this study includes:

Social:

- It encourages community gatherings and social interactions.
- It provides a platform for social activities and cultural celebrations.
- It provides a sense of community and strengthens their relationships.

Education:

- It allows for cultural exchange, where people from different backgrounds can share and immerse themselves in the cultural world of Pampanga.
- It promotes awareness and education to dispel any misconceptions and to foster a deeper understanding of the Kapampangan culture.

Tourism:

- It serves as an icon/symbol of Pampanga's cultural identity, embodying the legacy of the Kapampangans for future generations to witness and honor.
- It boosts Pampanga's tourism and economic growth by providing a place for local and global tourists to visit and by employing and recognizing local Kapampangan artists, merchants, and others.

1.2.3 JUSTIFICATION

As Marcus Garvey once said, “A people without the knowledge of their history, origin and culture is like a tree without roots.”

Cultural centers are more than hollow structures built for social gatherings. It is the heart of the community where their culture and traditions are alive and celebrated. It is a space of high significance for it promotes joint cultural practices and participation, fosters socialization, builds social and cultural bridges, and facilitates communication about one’s culture and society (Derado, 2022). Furthermore, cultural centers offer many benefits for a community, and one of their most significant contributions is education, where knowledge about the past can be shared with the public, which also helps foster a sense of community and engagement (Sharer, 2023).

Given the rationale mentioned above and the significance of the proposed project, developing a culture, arts, and tourism complex in San Fernando City, Pampanga, would be highly beneficial and suitable for the further growth and development of the Kapampangan community. The proposed project is a way to connect tourists and especially locals back to their roots and ensure that their history and legacy will continue and be passed on to future generations.

1.3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Aside from being the Culinary Capital of the Philippines, Pampanga is renowned for its rich and diverse cultural history and heritage, making it a worthy tourist destination for people to explore and experience.

However, despite this, Pampanga currently does not have a well-developed place dedicated to honoring, preserving and promoting the Kapampangan culture. This lack of a central facility for accommodating both the tourists and locals' needs for cultural immersion and participation, celebration and recreation, education and commerce is the main problem that the proposed project titled "Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts and Tourism Complex" will address.

Moreover, due to the program of the former President Rodrigo Duterte called the Build, Build, Build program. Pampanga was further developed to become a hub for commerce and tourism, specifically due to the development of Clark International Airport and New Clark City. This development brought about significant growth in the province's tourism and economy, putting Pampanga further on top of the list of unique travel destinations (Nicholas, 2018). A grand opportunity for the local Kapampangans to shine by showcasing their talents, promoting their local goods and services, and proudly representing their cultural identity to the world.

This development is another reason why developing a Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex is significantly relevant not only to address the present need for celebration and housing the Kapampangan culture but also to keep up with Pampanga's future needs and tourism developments.

1.4 GENERAL AND SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1.4.1 GENERAL OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to propose a Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex in the City of San Fernando, Pampanga, that is interactive, culturally significant, and architecturally innovative. This complex would serve as the melting pot or formal central hub of Pampanga for social, cultural, and religious celebrations and act as an architectural icon embodying the Kapampangan cultural identity.

1.4.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

In general, this study aimed to gather vital information and data that will support the development of the proposed project. Listed below are the specific objectives that this study tackled:

- I. This study aims to find a suitable location within the Vicinity of San Fernando City, Pampanga, and conduct a site analysis to ensure its suitability for the proposed project.
- II. This study aims to gather information about the history and culture in arts, music, dance, literature, cuisine, and festival of each municipality of Pampanga.
- III. This study aims to explore the social and cultural patterns of the Kapampangan to better understand and address their architectural needs for the preservation, celebration and promotion of their cultural heritage.
- IV. This study aims to explore Pampanga's tourism patterns to account for the number of target users both locally and globally for the said project.
- V. This study aims to explore and apply architectural solutions to achieve interactivity, sustainability and aesthetics in the development of the proposed complex project.

VI. This study aims to discuss the social and cultural significance and impact of the proposed project for the development of Pampanga.

1.5 SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The scope of this study is primarily focused on developing and designing a Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex in San Fernando City, Pampanga.

The study selected a suitable location only within the vicinity of San Fernando City, Pampanga. This study covered available data about the history and culture of Pampanga such as its art, music, dance, literature, cuisine, religious celebrations, and festivities. Note that in depth research of Pampanga's history and cultural heritage is not part of the study, but rather it focused on the formulation of spaces and facilities that the project will need to host Pampanga's culture. Lastly, this study covered Pampanga's general social and cultural patterns, and tourism patterns, to gain knowledge to address their architectural needs in a cultural complex.

Due to a limited timeframe, this study only covered aspects within the scope provided. The limitations of this study include not involving the actual construction and implementation phase of this project, as it solely focused on the feasibility of the design and production of architectural plans. In-depth and detailed engineering aspects such as structural, mechanical, electrical, plumbing, and electronic systems will be separate from the study. However, these are addressed in a conceptual/general manner. Moreover, other aspects of Kapampangan culture and traditions except for what is stated above are not also included in the study. Lastly, in-depth and detailed cost estimation and budgeting, as well as long-term maintenance, were not be covered.

1.6 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents related literature and studies from both foreign and local sources. The presented related literature and studies were reviewed to analyze their pros and cons and apply the knowledge gained to improve the proposed study.

1.6.1 DEFINITION OF TERMS

- ***Doric Column*** - This is one of the classical orders of ancient Greece. A doric column is a type of column with a very plain, straightforward design that is thicker and heavier than an Ionic or Corinthian column. It is used for both load-bearing and ornamental purposes (Craven, 2019).
- ***Ionic Column*** - This is one of the classical orders of ancient Greece. An ionic column is a type of column famous from ancient Greece that is slenderer than a Doric column and has a scroll-shaped capital (Craven, 2019).
- ***Pilaster*** – is described as a rectangular, vertical wall protrusion that looks like a flat column or a half pier (Craven, 2018).
- ***Neo-Palladian Architecture*** - is a style of Architecture from the early 1720s that is characterized by symmetry, proportion, and balance. It has temple fronts, a central dome, and Palladian windows (a central arched window with two smaller rectangular windows) (Davis, 2023).
- ***Virtual Reality*** - also known as VR or Virtual World, is the use of technology such as computer modelling software that enables a person to interact with an artificial three-dimensional visual or sensory environment (Lowood, 2023).
- ***Flora*** – is defined as any plant life found in a particular region (Byjus, 2016).
- ***Fauna*** – is defined as any animal life found in a particular region (Byjus, 2016).

- **A Semi-Structured Interview** – is a data collection method that relies on asking pre-determined questions to gather data from the participants. It is usually qualitative in nature (George, 2022).
- **Regression Analysis** - is a set of statistical methods used to estimate relationships between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables (Taylor, 2020).
- **Indu** – is a Kapampangan word which means “mother.” In this study the word mother is use as the title to describe that the propose project will serve as the icon (mother) of the Kapampangan cultural identity (Aviles, 2024).
- **Full Dome Cinema** - This refers to a type of cinema that uses an immersive dome as its based for a video projection screen. Inside the cinema the viewer is surrounded by the video projection in a hemispherical angle view (Fulldome: What Is It? – Fulldome Database, n.d.).

1.6.2 RELATED LITERATURE

Under this chapter two foreign and five local literatures (two examples from the Philippines and three examples from Pampanga) were presented for analysis and review.

1.6.2.1 FOREIGN RELATED LITERATURE

a. National Museum of Singapore

According to Ching (2023), the National Museum of Singapore is an interactive museum located at 93 Stamford Road, Singapore, and is considered to be the nation's oldest museum. Its history began as a section of the Raffles Library Museum and was first established in 1849 at the Victoria Memorial Hall. After years of moving around, in 1887, the museum finally settled down on its current location at Stamford Road and became known as Singapore's National Museum.

Figure 1.6.2.1.a. 1 Raffles Library and Museum

Retrieved from <https://thesmartlocal.com/read/national-museum-of-singapore/>

The museum was designed by Colonial Engineer Sir Henry E. McCallum in the style of Neo-Palladian architecture, as seen from the main façade. Moreover, some Neoclassical features such as Doric and Ionic columns and pilasters were also incorporated into the structure as part of the commemoration of the monarch Queen Victoria's reign in 1887 (Golden Jubilee), the same year the museum was officially opened. The rotunda, a crowned dome covered with fish-scale tiles, with arched windows and colored glass panels to allow light to be transmitted inside the building, is considered to be the museum's most stunning feature.

Figure 1.6.2.1.a. 2 Rotunda of the National Museum of Singapore
Retrieved from <https://www.nhb.gov.sg/nationalmuseum/>

Figure 1.6.2.1.a. 3 The National Museum of Singapore
Retrieved from Tour al National Museum - IWG Singapore

Though it is claimed to be the oldest museum in Singapore, its galleries have adapted advanced virtual reality technology to redefine the conventional museum experience and to provide a multi-perspective way of presenting the rich history and culture of Singapore to its audience (National Heritage Board, 2020).

Moreover, according to Steens (2021), the museum features immersive storytelling through the use of art installations, 3d animations and screens to create an interactive space to appeal to the modern generation.

One of the museum's stunning exhibits is the "Story of the Forest", created by teamLab, a Japanese digital art collective. The exhibit is an immersive artwork that represents Singapore's colonial past in contrast to its present-day modernity. It was achieved by transforming the Natural history drawings of William Farquhar into a three-dimensional animated visual landscape (NMS, 2017).

Figure 1.6.2.1.a. 4 Story of the Forest National Museum of Singapore

Retrieved from <https://www.tickets.com/blog/interactive-museum/>

The National Museum of Singapore is a cultural and architectural landmark that acts as the nation's main platform for cultural activities, such as hosting innovative festivals and events while also housing some of Singapore's culturally significant artefacts. In addition to the 14 immersive exhibits, the museum also hosts retail and dining facilities, a resource center, and a variety of galleries for tourists and locals to enjoy (National Heritage Board, 2020).

b. The Hellenic Cosmos

The Hellenic Cosmos, also known as the Cultural Center of the Foundation of the Hellenic World, is an ultra-modern cultural center complex that teaches visitors about the rich cultural heritage of Athens, Greece, in an innovative and immersive manner through interactive exhibits and the utilization of modern technology, such as virtual 3D tours (Athens 24, 2023).

The Hellenic Cosmos is located between Athens and Piraeus on a site that was formerly an industrial zone. The Hellenic Cosmos acts as the melting pot of Greek culture, providing locals and tourists with a multi-functional venue in which they can be immersed in Hellenic history and culture. The cultural complex hosts facilities such as a theatre, museum, art galleries and exhibits to support the different cultural activities of Athens, such as art events, theatrical performances, interactive exhibitions, virtual reality tours, etc. (Foundation of the Hellenic World, n.d.).

Figure 1.6.2.1.b. 1 The Hellenic Cosmos Cultural Center

Retrieved from http://www.fhw.gr/cosmos/index.php?id=1&m=1&lg=_en#

The goal of the cultural complex is to preserve and promote the Hellenic history and tradition of the Greek to the world. The purpose of the cultural complex is to teach and raise awareness about the importance of the past and how cultural heritage can help prepare the present generation for the future. Interactivity through architecture and state-of-the-art technology was utilized to address this objective (Athens 24, 2023). One of the complex's interactive facilities includes the Hellenic Cosmos' Tholos, a domed-shaped virtual reality theater, where visitors can explore ancient Greece through an interactive screen. This architectural marvel was designed to host a capacity of 130 people. Another facility is the Theatron, a multi-functional hall that houses contemporary artistic creations such as plays, musicals and other cultural performances.

Figure 1.6.2.1.b. 2 The Tholos of the Hellenic Cosmos Cultural Complex

Retrieved from <https://www.kidslovegreece.com/en/culture/hellenic-cosmos-cultural-centre/>

The Hellenic Cosmos continuously evolves, and new facilities are also continuously being developed. From the initial 16,000 m² in 1998, the cultural center has developed into a cultural park with 60,000 m² and is now considered to be a center for history, technology, and Architecture for the Hellenic Culture (Foundation of the Hellenic World, n.d.).

Review and Analysis of Foreign Related Literatures

The National Museum of Singapore and the Hellenic Cosmos of Athens, Greece, are great examples of a cultural center complex built to promote and preserve their cultural heritage. The ingenious beauty behind these examples lies in their idea of breaking the boring conventional experience of visiting a cultural center by making it interactive and immersive for people to appreciate and experience their heritage fully. Both examples achieved this by adapting modern technology such as virtual screens, virtual galleries, light and sound effects, 3D art installations, and other interactive exhibits. Moreover, more than the main cultural center, they also incorporated other facilities such as restaurants, commercial establishments, theaters for cultural performances, and other multi-functional spaces for social gatherings and art and music events to host all their cultural celebrations and activities in one complex. The examples addressed the need for cultural celebration and preservation while providing entertainment, education, and commerce for visitors to enjoy.

In conclusion, it has been reviewed that in designing a cultural center, it is essential to consider its relevance and appeal to the present generation. Incorporating interactivity within the project is vital to transforming a conventional space into a convivial and immersive place for the end users.

1.6.2.2 LOCAL RELATED LITERATURE (PHILIPPINES)

a. Cultural Center of the Philippines

The Cultural Center of the Philippines, also known as CCP, is a cultural center located in Pasay City, Manila, Philippines. It was created in 1966. The Cultural Center of the Philippines was designed by the famous National Artist for Architecture, Ar. Leandro Locsin. Its purpose was to promote and preserve the Philippines' rich culture and arts and to embody the values of truth, beauty and goodness (katotohanan, kagandahan at kabutihan). The CCP has been at the Philippines' forefront of culture and the arts for more than 50 years and is continuously working with the government, academe and international community to enrich the Philippines' brand and economy (Cultural Center of the Philippines, 2023).

Figure 1.6.2.2.a. 1 The Cultural Center of the Philippines

Retrieved from <https://culturalcenter.gov.ph/about/>

In addition, according to the article *Sentrong Pangkultura ng Pilipinas (2023)*, the Cultural Center of the Philippines hosts performing companies representing dance, music, and theater, such as Ballet Philippines, The Ramon Obusan Folkloric Group, Tanghalang Pilipino CCP's resident theater company, and many more. It also hosts films, broadcasts, and literary and visual arts with the goal of encouraging young, talented Filipinos to develop and nourish their talents in their respective fields.

One of the facilities that the Cultural Center of the Philippines hosts are the main theater, little theater, studio theater, audio-visual room, black box theater, rehearsal hall, main theater lobby and little theater lobby. Each theater was designed to host different cultural performances for tourists and locals to experience.

Figure 1.6.2.2.a. 2 Tanghalang Nicanor Abelardo (Main Theater)

Retrieved from <https://culturalcenter.gov.ph/venues-and-tours/>

Review and Analysis of Cultural Center of the Philippines

According to the Cultural Center of Philippines (2023), the CCP will undergo a three-year redevelopment from 2023 to late 2025, for the purpose of transforming the 50-year-old building into a state-of-the-art center for cultural celebrations and artistic excellence. Due to this the researcher utilized YouTube by watching Kramsenoj Anidem (2009) tour vlog inside the CCP to conduct her review and analysis.

Pros

- It has been observed that the Cultural Center of the Philippines offers a variety of facilities to host different and simultaneous cultural events. Such as a library for research, small and main lobby for accommodation, 3 performing theaters for cultural performances, an audio-visual room for film viewing, and galleries for exhibitions.
- The CCP has a decent parking space near the building along side with other commercial establishments. Moreover, every space inside the CCP is remarkably unique and designed with a purpose, it is truly a work of art and it captures the essence of promoting the Philippine cultural heritage.

Cons

- The only con is that the current design does not fully integrate modern technology to enhance the experience of the visitors. But since it is under redevelopment this issue will surely be addressed.

Conclusion

This review and analysis of the CCP's pros and cons were all taken into consideration by the researcher for the development of her proposed thesis.

b. The National Museum Complex of the Philippines

The National Museum Complex (Pambansang Museo) is located in Ermita, Manila, Philippines and can be considered as a cultural center for it hosts the Philippines' well-known museums, namely the National Museum of Fine Arts, National Museum of Anthropology, National Museum of Natural History and National Planetarium. Each museum is home to a variety of culturally significant artefacts, tools, photographs and other artworks, such as paintings and sculptures, that play a vital role in the history and culture of the Philippines (Patrick, 2023).

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 1 The National Museum Complex of Manila

Retrieved from <https://guidetothephilippines.ph/articles/history-culture/museums-philippines>

The National Museum of Natural History is a museum that hosts stunning exhibits dedicated to showcasing the Philippines' most notable flora and fauna, such as the Tree of Life and Rainforest Diorama. Its purpose is to preserve and teach the audience about the Philippines' natural environment through educational displays and galleries.

The National Museum of Fine Arts, established in the early 1920s, on the other hand, features the works of famous Filipino artists such as Guillermo Tolentino, Felix Resurreccion Hidalgo, and Juan Luna, who is famous for his Spoliarium painting.

Lastly, there is the National Museum of Anthropology. This museum features ethnographic materials and agricultural tools, such as baskets and weapons, that were used in ancient times. It is a cultural center dedicated to preserving and exploring human development or the study of anthropology in the Philippines (Munzones, n.d.).

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 2 National Museum of Natural History

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 3 National Museum of Fine Arts

Retrieved from <https://guidetothephilippines.ph/articles/history-culture/museums-philippines>

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 4 National Museum of Anthropology

Retrieved from <https://guidetothephilippines.ph/articles/history-culture/museums-philippines>

Review and Analysis of National Museum Complex

Pros of National Museum of Fine Arts

- The museum adapted modern technology such as kiosk machines and flat screen televisions to enhance the visitors experience as they explore the exhibit displays of the museum.
- Each exhibit was unique through the use of color representations, distinct arrangement of the displays and use of lighting.

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 5 Flat Screen TV

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 6 Kiosk Machine

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 7 Colored Exhibits

Retrieved from My Gallery

Pros of National Museum of Natural History

- The museum adapted modern technology such as kiosk machines, flat screen televisions, sound dome and touch screens, to immerse the visitors of the museum.
- Each exhibit was designed and arranged in a creative way, mimicking the actual scenery of the natural world.
- A directory or guide map was introduced giving insight to visitors on where and what exhibits are present inside the museum.
- Ramps and an elevator were also introduced to address the accessibility for the PWD and elderly.

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 8 Modern Technology

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 9 Marine Exhibit

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 10 Directory Guide

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 11 Ramp & Elevator

Retrieved from My Gallery

Pro of National Museum of Anthropology

- The museum utilized natural lighting and ventilation as part of its design through an open courtyard, large windows and open space plan.

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 12 Open Courtyard

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.2.b. 13 Hallway

Retrieved from My Gallery

Cons of National Museum Complex

- The National Museum of Fine Arts and Anthropology lacks a guide map that indicates the flow of how to visit and experience the museum in an organized manner and for the visitors to know the list of exhibits that are present and available inside the museum.
- All three museums do not offer other facilities such as restaurants, souvenir shops and even public parking space for visitors to fully enjoy the complex.

Conclusion

Overall, all three museums of the National Museum Complex have great facilities that incorporated modern technology with architectural solutions to create an interactive atmosphere. However, the complex lacks in terms of providing other facilities such as restaurants, souvenir shops and a public parking space which limited the visitors' experience with the complex. This analysis will be taken into consideration by the researcher for the development of her proposed thesis.

1.6.2.3 LOCAL RELATED LITERATURE (PAMPANGA)

a. Center for Kapampangan Studies

The Center for Kapampangan Studies is a small cultural center located in Angeles City, inside the campus of Holy Angel University. It is a facility dedicated to researching, compiling, preserving facts, and promoting the Kapampangan cultural heritage. The center is a three-story building, where the ground-floor level hosts the main lobby gallery, mini-museum of Pampanga's history, culture, and archaeology, and John A. Larkins library. The second-floor level contains the archived collection, the Mt. Pinatubo Museum, and the Museum of Kapampangan Arts. Lastly, the third-floor level houses the mini-theater (HeaRth.PH, 2021).

Figure 1.6.2.3.a. 1 Holy Angel University View 1

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a. 2 Holy Angel University View 2

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a. 3 Center for Kapampangan Studies

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a. 4 CKS Main Entrance

Retrieved from My Gallery

Review and Analysis of Center for Kapampangan Studies

Pros:

- The center's main lobby has adopted a Kiosk that contains information about Kapampangan culture. It features music, short videos, a Kapampangan and Kulitan translator app, publications, and culinary items. This machine helps the center promote interaction and cultural immersion, especially among the younger generation.
- All exhibits were well-lit, artificially ventilated, and designed uniquely to fit the content. Written information and creative visual representations were utilized to help visitors understand and appreciate the displays.
- The mini-theater has an excellent acoustic design utilizing a smooth wood panel finish and carpet floors to provide good audible sound quality for the viewers.

Figure 1.6.2.3.a 5 Kiosk

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a 6 Mini-Theater

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a 7 Information Display

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a 8 Museum of Pampanga's History

Retrieved from My Gallery

Cons:

- The location of the exhibits and galleries is not appropriately zoned, creating an unorganized circulation flow for visitors touring inside. The center addressed this problem through managerial solutions, such as providing a student tour guide to help visitors navigate and experience the center.
- The center focused more on sight-seeing displays and lack interactivity and social engagement.
- Both the Museum of Kapampangan Arts and Mt. Pinatubo Museum have been observed to have only one access door serving as the visitors' entrance and fire exit.

Figure 1.6.2.3.a 9 Mt. Pinatubo Museum

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a 10 Museum of Kapampangan Arts

Retrieved from My Gallery

Conclusion:

Overall, the Center for Kapampangan Studies has good facilities that are welcoming and well-kept. Their displays are educational, and adapting a Kiosk was a significant upgrade that made the place more appealing for the newer generation. However, it has been reviewed that the CKS lacks interactivity and space flow organization, which were taken into consideration by the researcher for the development of the proposed project.

b. Clark Museum and 4D Theater

Located in Clark Freeport Zone, Pampanga, Clark Museum is a dedicated museum that houses essential artifacts, local products, military memorabilia, and other displays showcasing Clark's rich history from 1901. The museum is composed of four galleries and an interactive 4D theater (Clark Museum, n.d.).

The first gallery features Clark's geography and geology, educating visitors about Clark's location. The second gallery features the city's craftsmanship and innovation. The third gallery showcases the Clark Air Field base, while the last one tells the origin story of Clark's people (Clark Museum, n.d.).

Figure 1.6.2.3.b 1 Clark Museum & 4D Theater
Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.b 2 Clark Museum
Retrieved from My Gallery

The 4D theater, located beside the main museum, has a capacity of 48 pax sitting that shows a 20-minute documentary film titled "Risen From the Ashes," highlighting Clark's history during the Mt. Pinatubo eruption. The theater is in 4D because it uses special effects such as seat shaking and movement, smoke machines to create the effect of smoke and ashfall, and other visual effects and sounds to immerse the audience as if transporting them back to the actual moment the Mt. Pinatubo erupted (Clark Museum, n.d.).

Review and Analysis of Clark Museum and 4D Theater

Pros:

- The museum exhibits an organized circulation flow, where visitors can easily navigate through the four galleries while understanding the story the museum aims to showcase.
- The museum's interior design utilized curves and geometric forms to create stunning visual displays. Creative lighting also emphasized essential displays and created a serene atmosphere.
- The museum also provided public restrooms, and fire exits to ensure the comfort and safety of the visitors.

Figure 1.6.2.3.b 3 Gallery 1
Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.b 4 Gallery 4
Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a 5 Restroom in Gallery 2
Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.a 6 Fire Exit in Gallery 3
Retrieved from My Gallery

Cons:

- The museum only has stunning sightseeing displays, does not feature interactive exhibits, and needs more social engagement.
- On the second floor of the third gallery's entrance, the researcher observed a collection of light switches without labels that controlled the light fixtures of the second-floor galleries. This is not an advisable layout for placing light switches, for it could cause confusion and inconvenience.
- The museum also needs proper fire exit signages and fire escape route maps for the information and safety of the visitors.

Figure 1.6.2.3.b 7 Light Switches
Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.b 8 Fire Exit
Retrieved from My Gallery

Conclusion:

Overall, the Clark Museum and 4D theater have good facilities, visually stunning displays, and an excellent circulation flow of spaces. The galleries are well-kept, artificially cooled, and spacious enough to accommodate several visitors. However, the researcher has reviewed that the Clark Museum needs more interactivity and has some ineffective design features that are inconvenient and unsafe for visitors and the management involved. The researcher considered this analysis for the development of the proposed project.

c. Museo Ning Angeles

Museo Ning Angeles, also known as the Angeles City Museum, was built in 1999 to serve as a venue for exhibits, art classes, concerts, and cultural celebrations to preserve the rich history and culture of Angeles City. It is currently under the management of Kuliat Foundation Incorporation. In 2012, the museum was declared by the National Museum of the Philippines as an “Important Cultural Property of the Philippines” (Museo Ning Angeles, n.d.).

Figure 1.6.2.3.c 1 Museo Ning Angeles

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.c 2 Lobby Area

Retrieved from My Gallery

Museo Ning Angeles features a main exhibit called Balikdan (to look back) on the ground floor level, which showcases the works of local artists, photographs during the Philippine-American war, artefacts and memorabilia of Mt. Pinatubo’s eruption in 1991, and some notable personalities in the Angeles City Hall of Fame. On the second floor, it features a clothing diorama exhibit of traditional Filipino fashion and the Culinarium featuring the Kapampangan’s culinary expertise and love for food (Museo Ning Angeles, n.d.).

Review and Analysis of Museo Ning Angeles

Pros:

- The museum generally has an organized circulation flow, where visitors can easily navigate and explore the exhibits. The ground floor is dedicated to the main exhibit of history, while the second floor hosts the culinarium and clothing diorama.
- The ground-floor gallery is artificially cooled and well-lit, containing many displays that are visually attractive, well-kept, and well-organized.
- The ground-floor gallery also incorporated modern technology, such as flat-screen TVs and LED poster displays, to enhance the visitors' experience.

Figure 1.6.2.3.c 3 LED posters display

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.c 4 Flat Screen TV

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.c 5 Ground Floor Exhibit

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.c 6 Culinarium

Retrieved from My Gallery

Cons:

- The researcher experienced mild discomfort while exploring the culinarium due to the exhibit's poor ventilation system. The second-floor level uses natural ventilation, an excellent sustainable feature in a structure. However, due to the drastic change in the Philippines' climate, natural ventilation on its own is no longer an effective cooling solution.
- Moreover, the second-floor gallery needs to improve its display organization and should consider separating the public and private spaces. It has been observed that the staff's kitchenette (private area) is located directly beside the clothing diorama displays (public area). This type of layout is not ideal, unattractive, and unsanitary and should be addressed to maintain order and uphold the museum's reputation.

Figure 1.6.2.3.c 7 Kitchenette & Clothing Diorama

Retrieved from My Gallery

Figure 1.6.2.3.c 8 Second Floor

Retrieved from My Gallery

Conclusion:

Overall, the Museo Ning Angeles has good exhibits showcasing Pampanga's rich cultural history. Moreover, providing a culinarium made the museum stand out, emphasizing the Kapampangan culture and their love for cooking. However, the museum needs more interactivity to capture and immerse visitors into the Kapampangan cultural world and to improve its overall planning layout to address the poor ventilation system and privacy.

Overall Review and Analysis of Foreign and Local Related Literatures

After reviewing all related literature on existing cultural projects individually from both foreign and local sources, the researcher concludes that to design an effective cultural complex, one must consider the following:

- Include interactivity in the design. This can be achieved by incorporating modern technology such as Kiosks, flat-screen TVs, creative use of LED lighting, playful use of form and color, stunning visual displays, and strategic space layout planning.
- Multifunctional spaces are vital in cultural projects to allow for adaptable and functional use of spaces for different activities and celebrations.
- Landscape and nature play a vital role in sustainability and achieving comfort and harmony within the surroundings. Designing a cultural project incorporating nature helps create a more natural, serene, and welcoming environment.
- Utilities and services such as bathrooms and parking areas are necessary in every project, especially in a cultural project where several people gather.
- Lastly, it has been reviewed that existing cultural centers in the Philippines, especially in Pampanga, are limited to one purpose, such as being a museum, library, or theater. This lack of a central facility or complex limits the potential of these cultural centers, thus lessening their importance and making them dull and unworthy for some people. Therefore, designing a cultural project offering amenities and complete facilities is vital to accommodate tangible artifacts and people's need for social and cultural gatherings.

1.6.3 RELATED STUDIES

Under this chapter two foreign and three local related studies were presented for analysis and review.

1.6.3.1 FOREIGN RELATED STUDIES

a. Much More Than A Museum: Motivations and Experiences of Young Visitors at Urban Cultural Clusters by Kondrateva et al.

Is a study exploring how members of Generation Z are showing less interest in learning and visiting “classic” museums and other traditional cultural hubs. This research bridges the gap of making cultural centers much more appealing to the new generation’s taste. Moreover, the purpose of this study was to identify the factors that influence the motivations and experiences of young audiences towards urban cultural centers. The significance of this study was to provide modern cultural centers with information on how to design structures that can promote the cultural heritage of a community while appealing to the younger audience. The study utilized semi-structured interviews and survey methods to collect data from their young participants. Several hypotheses were tested using factor and regression analysis, and based on the results, it was discovered that Gen Zs value interaction and innovative attractions. It was concluded that for museums and cultural centers to be effective in reaching their younger audiences, they need to include interaction and co-creating in their spaces (Kondrateva et al., 2023).

b. Qawafel: Cultural Center by Amira S. Alamoudi

Is a research study that aims to design a cultural center in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. According to Alamoudi, the purpose of the study was to create a cultural center that can host, preserve and promote the rich culture and history of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Moreover, it was stated in the study that the need for a cultural center was highlighted not only to enrich the visitor's experience and knowledge about Jeddah but also to boost the country's tourism. In this study, the researcher Alamoudi considered different kinds of design elements such as lighting, colors and form to design an interactive cultural center. Creating an interactive learning environment was one of the study's main objectives, and it was achieved through the incorporation of technological innovations such as VR or Virtual Reality, interactive screens and wall screens to provide an immersive learning experience.

Furthermore, the study emphasized providing facilities to cater to the needs of the end-users for cultural activities. This study concluded by stating that the project can help develop the social, cultural, and economic aspects of tourism in Saudi Arabia. Additionally, Saudi Arabia's rich cultural heritage can be proudly preserved and showcased for future generations to see and experience (Alamoudi, 2020).

Review and Analysis of Foreign Related Studies

It has been reviewed according to the two studies that have been presented on designing an effective cultural center. It is essential to consider interactivity, which can be achieved through adapting modern technology and utilizing design solutions to create an interactive learning environment. Both studies emphasized modernizing cultural centers to become relevant, effective, and attractive in today's generation.

1.6.3.2 LOCAL RELATED STUDIES

a. Bale Pipaglutuan: A Culinary Heritage Village by Berlin Guanlao

Is an architectural thesis whose project was to propose a culinary heritage village in Pampanga, Philippines. According to Berlin Guanlao (2016), the proposed project aims to revive the culinary heritage of Pampanga and promote the Kapampangan identity by creating a space where one can taste, experience and learn all about the Kapampangan Cuisine. His project is a proposed complex having facilities such as a school that offers culinary workshops, a museum to formally house traditional Kapampangan culinary artefacts, a function hall, restaurants, an administration office, souvenir stores and a main plaza.

b. Teatro Sabina: Where Zarzuelitas Take Centerstage

According to Castro (2014), in the early 20th century, there was a theater for Kapampangan artists known as Teatro Sabina in Bacolor, Pampanga. It was a theater where Kapampangan actors, singers, playwrights, and composers performed and vented their talents amongst adoring audiences. One of these performances was “Zarzuela,” a play sung and acted by Zarzuelitas. It is a combination of dialogues and song lyrics written in Kapampangan.

Historically, the theater did not have a permanent venue until Indang Sabina, an unmarried sister of Pampanga’s governor, offered her plot of land in downtown Bacolor to host the theater. Earning the name Teatro Sabina in honor of her generosity. This theater became the home of some of the famous Kapampangan Zarzuela dramatists, performers, and composers such as Proceso Pabalan, Juan Crisostomo Soto, Felix Galura, Pascual Gozun, Pablo Palma, Jose Prado, Amado Gutierrez-David and Jose

Gutierrez-David. Teatro Sabina paved the way for the Kapampangan Zarzuela era to thrive for over three decades. Unfortunately, the legendary theater ceased operations in the late 20th century due to financial difficulties. Thus, the golden era of Kapampangan Theater ended (Castro, 2014).

c. Paskuhan Village

Paskuhan Village was a Christmas-themed Park located in San Fernando City, Pampanga, which was dedicated to showcasing the lantern-making tradition of San Fernando. The Paskuhan Village was realized by former Governor Bren Guia and DOT Secretary Jose Antonio Gonzalez. Its operation first began on December 11, 1990, and served as the venue for the “Ligligang Parul” or Giant Lantern Festival. However, due to the eruption of Mt. Pinatubo in 1991 and the rise of commercial establishments in Pampanga, the number of visitors to Paskuhan Village began to decline. Seeing as people tend to spend more time inside shopping malls, the Giant Lantern Festival was eventually moved to SM City Pampanga in 2001 and Robinsons in 2004 (City of San Fernando Pampanga, 2020).

This led to the conversion of Paskuhan into the North Philippines Cultural and Historical Village in 2003, which hosts the culture of Ilocos, Cagayan Valley Central Luzon, and Cordillera regions. Unfortunately, by 2012, the village had been bankrupt and had to be closed down. Since then, Premier Central, Four SM Group affiliates, and Robinsons have bided on the village property. Premier Central won the bid, but the village was further neglected due to a sales dispute under its management, thus declaring its ownership void by Solicitor General Jose Calida in 2017 and formally closing the property (City of San Fernando Pampanga, 2020).

Review and Analysis of Local Related Studies

The architectural thesis entitled “Bale Pipaglutuan” is an example study showcasing Pampanga's culinary culture. The study provided insights and proposed detailed facilities that would help preserve and promote the culinary culture of the Kapampangan. However, the study only focuses on Pampanga's culinary culture and lacks information regarding other aspects of the Kapampangan culture.

Teatro Sabina and Paskuhan Village were once significant cultural centers for the Kapampangans and were once the heart and soul of their artistic activities. However, both examples went into decline, and the main reason for their decline was financial instability due to the decrease in visitors. Both examples failed to keep up with the times and to remain relevant amidst the emergence of change. This was Teatro Sabina and Paskuhan Village's flaw, ultimately leading to their abandonment and closure. This information serves as a reminder for the researcher of this study to consider in formulating the proposed project Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts and Tourism Complex.

1.7 ARCHITECTURAL AND DESIGN CONCEPT

1.7.1 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- I. To develop a Kapampangan Culture, Arts and Tourism Complex in the City of San Fernando, Pampanga.
- II. To develop a culturally significant complex that will serve as the melting pot for Kapampangan social, cultural and religious celebrations.
- III. To plan and develop a complex that can effectively function in catering for the needs of cultural celebrations without contributing to environmental degradation.
- IV. To develop an immersive and interactive complex that will attract and engage the target users in visiting and immersing themselves in experiencing the rich cultural heritage of Pampanga.

1.7.2 DESIGN OBJECTIVES

- I. To design a complex that will become the icon of Pampanga and embody the Kapampangan cultural identity.
- II. To design a complex complete with facilities and amenities that can accommodate the Kapampangan's needs for social, cultural and religious celebrations.
- III. To design structures that are sustainable and eco-friendly to lessen the harmful effects of pollution on the environment.
- IV. To design architecturally innovative structures and spaces to promote interactivity and immersion.

1.7.3 DESIGN CRITERIA

I. To design an iconic Kapampangan cultural complex by utilizing Contemporary Style of Architecture through:

- a. Utilizing a color scheme of gold, bronze, white, gray, and blue to attract tourists and to give emphasis on the building's importance.
- b. Adapting traditional elements inspired from the bahay-kubo and bahay-na-bato and re-interpret them in a modern way as part of the building's design.
- c. Utilizing a curved, clean, and streamlined form creating a unique, dynamic and iconic look to attract end-users.

II. To design a multi-functional Kapampangan cultural complex by:

- a. Designing a cultural convention center, a main plaza, and outdoor food park that will act as a social gathering area for leisure, recreation, and cultural celebrations for the end users.
- b. Designing a theater for performing arts and an interactive museum with full dome cinema and a library to host both the tangible and intangible cultures of Pampanga and to serve as an institution for the preservation, promotion, and education of the Kapampangan culture.
- c. Designing a commercial building with various Kapampangan commercial establishments (such as restaurants) dedicated for business and trading for the end-users.

III. To design a sustainable Kapampangan cultural complex by:

- a. Designing adaptable buildings that can address various calamities such as flooding, earthquake and typhoons. This can be achieved by utilizing base isolators (earthquake), elevated floor line (flood), and durable building materials.
- b. Utilizing sustainable features such as a rain water collector, solar panels, skylights, and low thermal building materials to lessen energy consumption.
- c. Utilizing greenery, such as outdoor landscapes, and waterscapes, to help lessen heat gain and to provide natural cooling for the complex.

IV. To design an innovative Kapampangan cultural complex that is immersive and interactive by:

- a. Adapting a unique, stylish, and dynamic design to each space and buildings to capture and attract the visitors' attention and immersing them into experiencing the Kapampangan culture.
- b. Adapting modern technology into the structures, such as flat screens, kiosks, 3D displays, and lighting, to create an interactive, modern, and fun way of introducing Pampanga's cultural heritage especially to the younger generations.
- c. Adapting proper zoning and good circulation within the complex and spaces of each building to achieve accessibility and easy navigation for the end-users to fully explore and enjoy the complex.

1.7.4 DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

I.

AESTHETICS

PSYCHOLOGY
OF PERCEPTION

HISTORICAL

II.

BUILDING
ENVELOPE

FUNCTIONALITY

ACCESSIBILITY

III.

ADAPTABILITY

BUILDING
MATERIALS

FEASIBILITY

IV.

INNOVATION

CIRCULATION

CULTURAL
PATTERNS

1.7.5 DESIGN CONCEPT

The design concept for the proposed project was inspired from the word "**Lunduyan**," a Filipino word which means "center" or "cradle." This concept fits the project's goal of developing a central cultural complex that will become the cradle of the Kapampangan cultural identity.

1.7.6 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

"There is a fourth principle in Architecture and that is Spirit." (Aviles, 2024).

Aviles's philosophy explains that besides the three core principles of Architecture by Vitruvius (Firmitas, Utilitas, Venustas), there is a fourth one which is Spirit. The spirit pertains to the value given to the structure on how it impacts the society in an emotional way. Every building can be built to become durable, beautiful, and functional, but to create a building that is valuable and meaningful to the people is an incredible thing to achieve.

CHAPTER 2: METHODS

CONTENTS:

2.1 METHODS OF RESEARCH

2.2 RESEARCH TOOLS

2.3 ACTUAL SETTING OF THE PROJECT

2.1 METHODS OF RESEARCH

The researcher collected data using mixed-method research, which combines qualitative and quantitative research methods.

According to Hassan (2024), qualitative research is a methodology that analyzes non-numerical data. It focuses on exploring and understanding subjective data such as people's beliefs, attitudes, behaviors, and experiences. On the other hand, quantitative research is a methodology dealing with numerical data. It focuses on gathering objective measurements and numerical data for analysis to provide answers to a study's objectives. (University of Southern California Libraries, 2022).

2.2 RESEARCH TOOLS

Research tools refer to the instrument or tools used to collect, analyze and interpret data in research. These tools help the researcher gain information, validate hypotheses, and create evidence-based decisions (Funky, 2023).

The research tools utilized by the researcher for data collection were structured interview, survey, observation, and secondary data-gathering method.

a. Structured interview

The researcher conducted a structured interview to collect important information and details that would benefit and further improve the proposed study. Data such as architectural solutions, project significance, social and cultural patterns, tourism patterns, and even current threats and solutions involving cultural preservation were all gathered from the interview.

b. Survey Questionnaires

The researcher conducted an online survey questionnaire to collect information about the feasibility of the proposed study. This helped the researcher assess whether the study is feasible and will serve as a guide for its development. The survey gathered data such as the participants' knowledge about the study, their preferred facilities to visit, and their opinions regarding the project's significance.

c. Observation

The researcher conducted a site observation to assess the condition of the project site. All information gathered helped the researcher with site analysis and context.

d. Secondary Data Gathering

A secondary data-gathering method was applied to collect data concerning Pampanga's tangible and intangible cultures. Data was collected through internet surfing and scanning available reliable references and sources. All information gathered serves as the researcher's basis for formulating the proposed study's space requirements.

2.2.1 PARTICIPANTS OF THE STUDY

In order to gather the necessary data and information to improve and develop the proposed study, the researcher sought the help of government professionals and experts in the fields of Kapampangan culinary, arts, music and dance, literature, and history of Kapampangan culture.

Structured Interview

- Tourism Officer of San Fernando City (1 participant)
- A Kapampangan Culinary Expert (1 participant)
- A Kapampangan Artist (1 participant)
- A Kapampangan Musician/Performer (1 participant)
- A Kapampangan Writer (1 participant)
- A Kapampangan Cultural Historian (1 participant)
- A Registered and Licensed Architect knowledgeable in designing cultural centers (1 participant)

Survey Questionnaires

- A Kapampangan Local in Pampanga (of any age, gender and occupation) (100 participants)

The following presents the sample survey and interview questionnaire that was given to the participants of the study.

a. SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Google Form Link: <https://forms.gle/QVd8yByLPJvbcCXR9>

INTRODUCTION

A Blessed Day!

I am **Joyce Anne Aviles**, a **fifth-year Bachelor of Science in Architecture** student from **the University of the Assumption**. I am currently working on my thesis entitled **“Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex”** as part of my final requirement in Architectural Design 9—Thesis Research Writing.

This study is a project proposal to have a Kapampangan culture, arts, and tourism complex in San Fernando City. The complex would serve as the melting pot or formal central hub of Pampanga for social and cultural celebrations and act as an architectural icon embodying the Kapampangan cultural identity.

CONSENT FORM

To determine whether the proposed project is feasible, the researcher humbly requests your help in answering the survey form below to achieve a target number of participants. Answering this survey will only take a few minutes and will not take up much of your precious time. Your participation is highly appreciated!

Please be informed that all data collected from this survey will strictly be used for educational purposes only. Rest assured that all data gathered will be treated with strict confidentiality following the Data Privacy Act of 2012 – RA 10173 to ensure the safety and data privacy of the participants.

For questions and clarifications, you may reach me through the following contact details:

UA Gsuite Account: jalaviles.student@ua.edu.ph

Facebook Account: <https://www.facebook.com/joyceanne.aviles/>

Looking forward to your participation!

- I have read and agreed to become a participant of this study.

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Instructions: Please read and answer each question carefully and truthfully. Select the item that corresponds to your answer. *(Mangyaring basahin at sagutin ang bawat tanong nang maingat at tapat. Piliin ang item na tumutugma sa iyong sagot.)*

Name (*Pangalan*) (optional) _____

Email (optional) _____

Age (*Edad*)

- Under 18 years old
- 18 – 25 years old
- 26 – 40 years old
- 41 – 59 years old
- 60 years old and above

Gender (*Kasarian*)

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

Occupation (*Trabaho*)

- Student
- Self Employed
- Employed
- Unemployed
- Retiree

Address (*Tirahan*)

- | | | | |
|---|--------------------------------------|---------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> San Fernando City | <input type="radio"/> Florida Blanca | <input type="radio"/> Masantol | <input type="radio"/> Santa Ana |
| <input type="radio"/> Angeles City | <input type="radio"/> Guagua | <input type="radio"/> Mexico | <input type="radio"/> Santa Rita |
| <input type="radio"/> Apalit | <input type="radio"/> Lubao | <input type="radio"/> Minalin | <input type="radio"/> Santo Tomas |
| <input type="radio"/> Arayat | <input type="radio"/> Mabalacat City | <input type="radio"/> Porac | <input type="radio"/> Sasmuan |
| <input type="radio"/> Bacolor | <input type="radio"/> Macabebe | <input type="radio"/> San Luis | |
| <input type="radio"/> Candaba | <input type="radio"/> Magalang | <input type="radio"/> San Simon | |

PART I: PROJECT BACKGROUND

Instructions: Please read and answer each question carefully and truthfully. Select the item that corresponds to your answer. *(Basahin at sagutin nang mabuti at totoo ang bawat tanong. Piliin ang aytem na tumutugma sa iyong sagot.)*

1. Do you have any idea or knowledge of what is a cultural center? *(Mayroon ka bang ideya o kaalaman kung ano ang isang cultural center?)*
 Yes No
2. Have you ever seen and/or visited a cultural center? *(Nakakita o nakabisita kana ba sa isang cultural center?)*
 Yes No
3. A cultural center is a place/building dedicated to preserve and promote the culture and arts of a community. Knowing this do you think it is important to preserve and promote our cultural heritage? *(Ang cultural center ay isang lugar/istruktura na nakalaan upang mapangalagaan at maisulong ang kultura at sining ng isang komunidad. Sa kaalaman na ito, sa tingin mo ba mahalaga na pangalagaan at isulong ang ating pamanang kultura?)*
 Yes No
4. Would you be interested to have a cultural complex for Pampanga, that offers facilities and amenities to preserve, promote and celebrate the Kapampangan culture? *(Interesado ka bang magkaroon ng isang cultural complex para sa Pampanga, na nag-aalok ng mga pasilidad upang mapanatili, itaguyod, at ipagdiwang ang kulturang Kapampangan?)*
 Yes No
5. Would you visit and support this Kapampangan cultural complex? *(Bibisitahin at susuportahan mo ba itong cultural complex para sa mga Kapampangan?)*
 Yes No

PART II: PROJECT FACILITIES AND EXPERIENCE

Instructions: Please read and answer each question carefully and truthfully. Select the item that corresponds to your answer. *(Basahin at sagutin nang mabuti at totoo ang bawat tanong. Piliin ang aytem na tumutugma sa iyong sagot.)*

1. Which among the facilities are you interested in visiting? You may choose more than one. *(Alin sa mga sumusunod na pasilidad ang interesado kang bisitahin? Maaaring pumili ng higit sa isang sagot.)*

- Main Immersive Interactive Museum Building
- History of Pampanga Exhibit
- Culinary Exhibit
- Art Exhibit (Immersive Art Installations, Paintings, Sculptures, Pottery etc.)
- Festival Exhibit
- Music and Dance Exhibit
- Literary Exhibit / Library Café
- 4D Immersive Full Dome Cinema
- Grand Theater for Performing Arts
- Commercial Shops and Restaurants
- Local Kapampangan Workshops (Culinary, Arts, Music & Dance & Literary)
- Outdoor Grand Plaza (Leisure and Food Park)

2. Are there any other specific facilities that you wish to see/visit in the project? Please specify. *(Mayroon ka pa bang ibang pasilidad na nais makita at bisitahin sa proyekto? Kung mayroon paki-sulat sa patlang.)*

3. What kind of atmosphere do you wish to experience in visiting the project? You may choose more than one. *(Anong uri ng kapaligiran ang nais mong maranasan sa pagbisita sa proyekto? Maaaring pumili ng higit sa isang sagot.)*

- Festive and Colorful *(Masaya at Makulay)*
- Serene and Peaceful *(Tahimik at Payapa)*
- Highly Educational and Engaging *(Puno ng Kaalaman at Nakakaengganyo)*

PART III. PROJECT SIGNIFICANCE

Instructions: On a scale of 1 to 5, 5 corresponding to Strongly Agree and 1 corresponding to Strongly Disagree, please rate the following questions by selecting the circle that corresponds to your answer.

(Sa sukat na isa hanggang lima. Kung saan ang Lima ay tumutukoy sa lubos na sumasang-ayon at ang isa ay tumutukoy sa lubos na hindi sumasang-ayon, paki-rate ang mga sumusunod na tanong sa pamamagitan ng pagpili ng bilog na tumutugma sa iyong sagot.)

1. Do you agree that the project would significantly contribute to the preservation and promotion of the Kapampangan cultural heritage? (Culture)

(Sang-ayon kaba na ang proyekto ay makatutulong sa pangangalaga at pagpapalaganap ng pamanang kultura ng Kapampangan?)

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

2. Do you agree that the project would significantly encourage community engagement and provide a platform for social activities and cultural celebration? (Social)

(Sang-ayon ka ba na ang proyekto ay makahihikayat ng pakikilahok sa komunidad at magbibigay ng plataporma para sa mga sosyal na aktibidad at pagdiriwang ng kultura?)

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

3. Do you agree that the project would significantly promote cultural exchange, immersion and educate visitors about the Kapampangan cultural heritage?

(Education)

(Sang-ayon ka ba na ang proyekto ay magsusulong ng palitan ng kultura, imersyon at pagpapalaganap ng kaalaman sa mga bisita patungkol sa pamana ng kulturang Kapampangan?)

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

4. Do you agree that the project would significantly boost the tourism and economic growth of Pampanga? (Tourism/Economic)

(Sang-ayon ka ba na ang proyekto ay makapagpapasigla sa turismo at paglago ng ekonomiya ng Pampanga?)

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

Do you have any other comments or thoughts you wish to share about the project **“Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex”**? If so, please leave a note below. Thank you for your participation!

(Mayroon ka bang ibang mga komento o saloobin na nais ibahagi tungkol sa proyektong “Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex”? Kung gayon, mangyaring mag-iwan ng tala sa ibaba. Salamat sa iyong pakikilahok!)

b. INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE

INTRODUCTION

A Blessed Day!

I am **Joyce Anne Aviles**, a fifth-year **Bachelor of Science in Architecture** student from **the University of the Assumption**. I am currently working on my thesis entitled **“Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex”** as part of my final requirement in Architectural Design 9—Thesis Research Writing.

This study is a project proposal to have a Kapampangan culture, arts, and tourism complex in San Fernando City. The complex would serve as the melting pot or formal central hub of Pampanga for social and cultural celebrations and act as an architectural icon embodying the Kapampangan cultural identity.

CONSENT FORM

The researcher humbly requests your participation in this interview for the purpose of data gathering which will greatly benefit the study.

The interview questionnaire only has five questions to answer and will not take up much of your precious time. Your participation is highly appreciated!

Please be informed that all data collected from this survey will strictly be used for educational purposes only. Rest assured that all data gathered will be treated with strict confidentiality following the Data Privacy Act of 2012 – RA 10173 to ensure the safety and data privacy of the participants.

For questions and clarifications, you may reach me through the following contact details:

UA Gsuite Account: jalaviles.student@ua.edu.ph

Facebook Account: <https://www.facebook.com/joyceanne.aviles/>

Looking forward to your participation!

- I have read and agreed to become a participant of this study.

TOURISM OFFICER OF SAN FERNANDO CITY

1. What does the word tourism mean and why is it important for San Fernando and Pampanga in general?
2. Where do tourists usually go to visit in Pampanga and what are their tourism patterns?
3. Are there current problems or threat in Pampanga's tourism? If so, what are they and are there current solutions being done to address these issues?
4. Do you agree that the proposed project entitled Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex is significant? Why or why not?
5. As a tourism officer, what spaces/facilities/features would you suggests in developing a Kapampangan cultural complex, that would attract and encourage locals and tourists to visit?

A KAPAMPANGAN CULINARY EXPERT

1. How would you define the culinary or cuisine of Pampanga?
2. Why is it important to preserve and promote the Kapampangan cuisine?
3. What are the struggles that the Kapampangan culinary world faces in today's generation and are there current solutions being done to address these issues?
4. Do you agree that the proposed project entitled Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex would significantly help in preserving and promoting the Kapampangan cuisine? Why or why not?
5. As a Kapampangan culinary expert, what spaces/facilities/features would you suggest and what to see in the proposed project, to honor and host the Kapampangan cuisine?

A KAPAMPANGAN ARTIST

1. How would you define the art culture of Pampanga?
2. Why is it important to preserve and promote the Kapampangan art culture?
3. What are the struggles that the Kapampangan artists face in today's generation and are there current solutions being done to address these issues?
4. Do you agree that the proposed project entitled Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex would significantly help in preserving and promoting the Kapampangan art culture? Why or why not?
5. As a Kapampangan artist, what spaces/facilities/features would you suggest and what to see in the proposed project, to honor and host the Kapampangan art culture?

A KAPAMPANGAN MUSICIAN/PERFORMER

1. How would you define the music and dance (performing arts) of Pampanga?
2. Why is it important to preserve and promote the Kapampangan music and dance (performing arts)?
3. What are the struggles that the Kapampangan musicians and performers face in today's generation and are there current solutions being done to address these issues?
4. Do you agree that the proposed project entitled Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex would significantly help in preserving and promoting the Kapampangan music and dance (performing arts)? Why or why not?
5. As a Kapampangan musician/performer, what spaces/facilities/features would you suggest and what to see in the proposed project, to honor and host the Kapampangan music and dance (performing arts)?

A KAPAMPANGAN WRITER

1. How would you define the literature or literary arts of Pampanga?
2. Why is it important to preserve and promote the Kapampangan literary arts?
3. What are the struggles that the Kapampangan writers face in today's generation and are there current solutions being done to address these issues?
4. Do you agree that the proposed project entitled Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex would significantly help in preserving and promoting the Kapampangan literary arts? Why or why not?
5. As a Kapampangan writer, what spaces/facilities/features would you suggest and what to see in the proposed project, to honor and host the Kapampangan literary arts?

A KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL HISTORIAN

1. How would you define the culture and traditions of Pampanga? What are the social and cultural patterns of the Kapampangan?
2. Why is it important to preserve and promote the Kapampangan culture?
3. Are there current problems or threat in Pampanga's cultural preservation? If so, what are they and are there current solutions being done to address these issues?
4. Do you agree that the proposed project entitled Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex would significantly help in preserving and promoting the Kapampangan culture? Why or why not?
5. As a Kapampangan historian, what spaces/facilities/features would you suggest and what to see in the proposed project, to honor and host the Kapampangan culture?

A RLA KNOWLEDGABLE IN DESIGING CULTURAL CENTERS

1. What are your important key points and advice to consider when designing an effective cultural center project? (Planning Approach)
2. How do you achieve an interactive and immersive atmosphere in a cultural center project through architectural planning? (Interactivity)
3. What sustainable features or practices are good to incorporate into a cultural center project? (Sustainability)
4. What makes a cultural center project iconic and culturally significant? (Iconic)
5. What kind of spaces/facilities should be incorporated to create a functional and adaptable cultural center project? (Space Requirements)

2.2.2 TARGET USER OF THE PROJECT

The proposed project, "Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex," welcomes people from all walks of life regardless of age, gender, race, and even civil status. However, the primary target users the proposed project wishes to cater to are the Kapampangans and the local and international tourists.

Indu is a project proposal that may serve as the central hub of entertainment, local commerce, cultural celebrations, social gatherings, and leisure for the Kapampangan community. It also be a place where local and international tourists can immerse themselves in Pampanga's rich history and cultural background.

2.2.3 PROJECT PROPONENT

Below are possible examples of Philippine agencies that can financially support the development of the researcher's proposed project, a Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex.

Figure 2.2.3. 1 NCCA Logo

Retrieved from <https://ncca.gov.ph/about-ncca-3/history-and-mandate/>

The National Commission for Culture and the Arts (NCCA) Philippines

It is a government agency that serves as the overall policy-making body, coordinating, and grant-giving agency of the Philippines that deals with the preservation, development, and promotion of the Philippine arts and culture (NCCA History and Mandate, 2020).

Figure 2.2.3. 2 DOT PH Logo

Retrieved from <http://tourism.gov.ph/link.aspx>

Department of Tourism of the Philippines (DOT)

It is a government agency mandated to encourage, promote, and develop tourism in the Philippines (Department of Tourism Philippines, 2023).

Figure 2.2.3. 3 TPB PHL Logo

Retrieved from <https://www.tpb.gov.ph/>

Tourism Promotions Board Philippines (TPB PHL)

It is an attached agency of the Department of Tourism Philippines. This government agency exists to promote and market the Philippines as world-class tourism domestically and internationally through partnerships with public and private stakeholders (About Us – Tourism Promotions Board, n.d.).

Figure 2.2.3. 4 Ayala Foundation Logo

Retrieved from <https://www.ayalafoundation.org>

Ayala Foundation

It is a private agency and the social development arm of the Ayala group of companies. Its vision is to create a community where people are creative, self-reliant, productive, and proud to be Filipinos. The Ayala Foundation's program areas include community and leadership development, corporate citizenship, and arts and culture. (Who We Are, n.d.).

Figure 2.2.3. 5 PAMCHAM Logo

Retrieved from <https://pamcham.org.ph/pamcham-logo/>

PAMCHAM

The Pampanga Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Inc. serves as a business organization that advocates in promoting the local business and economy of Pampanga to become globally competitive. One of the advocacies that it supports include economic development and tourism development for the province of Pampanga (About Us – Pampanga Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Inc., 2022).

Figure 2.2.3. 6 Provincial Government of Pampanga Logo

Retrieved from <https://th.bing.com/th/id/OIP.gWmXTBGg7VPp9sTyBYmR7QAAAA?rs=1&pid=ImgDetMain>

Provincial Government of Pampanga

Is the main government agency of Pampanga that is committed to enhance transparency, responsiveness, and competitiveness within the province. As stated in its mission statement the provincial government also adheres to uphold the promotion of culture and to improve economic growth within Pampanga (Mission & Vision, 2024).

2.3 ACTUAL SETTING OF THE PROJECT

Presented under this chapter are all the details and information pertaining to the proposed project's site. This chapter covers and analyzes the site's general profile, condition, and justification and provides legal documents to support the study. All legal documents and information under this chapter were solely used for educational purposes. They were acquired from the architectural thesis book of Mr. Janiel Charvey Lara (2024) entitled Polaris: Animation and Film Studio with his consent and approval.

2.3.1 SITE PROFILE AND ANALYSIS

2.3.1.1 PROJECT SITE CRITERIA

The following are the list of criteria in choosing the best suited project site or location for the proposed project. The target site location:

- Should be within the City of San Fernando Pampanga.
- Should be along a major road.
- Should be accessible to public and private transportation.
- Should be near and accessible to other developments and commercial establishments.
- Should not be relatively flat and not prone to flooding.
- Should be big enough to host a cultural complex.

2.3.1.2 PROJECT SITE DESCRIPTION

The location of the proposed project will be at **Barangay Dolores in San Fernando City, Pampanga**. The project property is said to be owned by S.P. Realty Development Corporation. It is situated in an **inside lot that is relatively flat** with a **Total Lot Area of 95,642 sq.m (9.5 hectares)**, abutting Jose Abad Santos Avenue (**JASA Major Road**) at the frontage. However, there is a portion of the lot where a commercial establishment called the **Northwalk exists, covering approximately 6,341 square meters** of the project site under lease with the property's owner.

The frontage of the site is facing **30 degrees Southeast** where the major road is situated. Residential houses and private property lots are located on the rear and left side of the lot, while the Green Medical Center is situated on the right side.

Moreover, the project site is a **commercial two-development zoned property** due to its location within the business district of San Fernando City, where different commercial establishments and offices, such as the city tourism office, are situated. Furthermore, the site is situated near the North Luzon Expressway (NLEX). It has access to nearby bus and jeepney terminals that travel to different cities such as Angeles, Tarlac, Bataan, Olongapo, Zambales, Bulacan, and Manila.

2.3.1.3 PROJECT SITE PROFILE

According to Lara (2024), all information under this chapter is according to the City Planning and Development Coordinator's Office of San Fernando, Pampanga.

Figure 2.3.1.3.1 Location of the Site

Retrieved from https://www.zamboanga.com/z/images/0/09/Pampanga_san_fernando.png

a. Geography

- The project site is located at Barangay Dolores in San Fernando City, Pampanga, Luzon, Philippines. It is situated approximately at 15.0388 latitude North and 120.6809 Longitude East, with an estimated elevation above sea mean level of 11.00 meters.

b. Topography

- The project site's topography generally has a relatively flat terrain with low susceptibility to flooding.

c. Vegetation

- The project site has a few existing vegetations namely hardwood trees, tropical grass and wild shrubs.

d. Utilities

- **Water Source**

The main water source provider of Dolores in San Fernando City is the Prime Water CSFP.

- **Electricity Source**

San Fernando Electric Light and Power Company (SFELAPCO) is the main electric power distributor of San Fernando City.

- **Telecommunication and Internet Service Facilities**

Some of the main telecommunication and Internet providers for San Fernando includes PLDT, Globe Telecom, and Converge ICT Solutions Inc.

e. Public Transportation and Road Network

- The frontage of the project site is bounded by a fifty meter (50 meter) major road right of way along Jose Abad Santos Avenue. Available public transportation near the site includes: Public Utility Jeepneys, E-Jeepney/Bus, Taxi, and Tricycles.

f. Climatic Conditions and Rainfall

- The average climate condition within the City of San Fernando is 32°C to 21°C which is typically warm with a gentle breeze.

Average High and Low Temperature in San Fernando City, Pampanga

The graph showcases that the month of March to May are the hot seasons, with April being the hottest month, while July to January are the cool seasons, with January being the coldest month in San Fernando City.

Figure 2.3.1.3.f. 1 Average High and Low Temperature in San Fernando

Retrieved from <https://weatherspark.com/y/134780/Average-Weather-in-San-Fernando-Philippines-Year-Round>

Average Rainfall in San Fernando City, Pampanga

The graph showcases that the month of August experiences the most amount of rainfall with an average of 50cm, while the month of February experiences the least amount of rainfall with an average of 1.2cm.

Figure 2.3.1.3.f. 2 Average Rainfall in San Fernando

Retrieved from <https://weatherspark.com/y/134780/Average-Weather-in-San-Fernando-Philippines-Year-Round>

Average Precipitation in San Fernando City, Pampanga

The graph showcases that the month of May to October are the wet seasons, with August having the highest amount of precipitation (23 days). While October to May are the dry seasons, with February having the lowest amount of precipitation (2.1 days)

Figure 2.3.1.3.f. 3 Average Precipitation in San Fernando

Retrieved from <https://weatherspark.com/y/134780/Average-Weather-in-San-Fernando-Philippines-Year-Round>

Average Humidity in San Fernando City, Pampanga

The graph showcases that the muggy season last for 10 months from March to January with the month of August having the muggiest days, while February has the fewest.

Figure 2.3.1.3.f. 4 Average Humidity in San Fernando

Retrieved from <https://weatherspark.com/y/134780/Average-Weather-in-San-Fernando-Philippines-Year-Round>

Average Hours of Daylight and Twilight in San Fernando City, Pampanga

The graph showcases that the month of June has the longest daytime with an average of 13 hours, while December has the shortest daytime with an average of 11 hours.

Figure 2.3.1.3.f. 5 Average Daylight in San Fernando

Retrieved from <https://weatherspark.com/y/134780/Average-Weather-in-San-Fernando-Philippines-Year-Round>

Tourism Score in San Fernando City

The graph showcases that the month of December to March is the best time of the year to visit San Fernando City, with the mid of January having the highest peak score.

Figure 2.3.1.3.f. 6 Tourism Score in San Fernando

Retrieved from <https://weatherspark.com/y/134780/Average-Weather-in-San-Fernando-Philippines-Year-Round>

2.3.1.4 LEGAL DOCUMENTS OF PROJECT SITE

a. Zoning Certificate

Figure 2.3.1.4.a. 1 Zoning Certificate

Retrieved from Municipal Hall of City of San Fernando

b. San Fernando, Pampanga – Barangay Boundary Map

The project site is located in Barangay Dolores, San Fernando City, Pampanga.

Figure 2.3.1.4.b. 1 Barangay Boundary Map of San Fernando, Pampanga

Retrieved from City Planning and Development Coordinator's Office

c. San Fernando, Pampanga – Road Network

The frontage of the project site is bounded by MacArthur Highway.

Figure 2.3.1.4.c. 1 Road Network and Road Name

Retrieved from City Planning and Development Coordinator's Office

d. San Fernando, Pampanga – Conceptual Land Use Map

The project site's land use is classified as a Commercial 2 Development Zoning.

Figure 2.3.1.4.d. 1 Conceptual Land Use Map 2019

Retrieved from City Planning and Development Coordinator's Office

e. San Fernando, Pampanga – Hazard Map

The project site is located within the low to moderate susceptibility of flooding area.

LANDSLIDE AND FLOOD SUSCEPTIBILITY MAP OF CITY OF SAN FERNANDO

Figure 2.3.1.4.e. 1 Hazard Map

Retrieved from City Planning and Development Coordinator's Office

f. San Fernando, Pampanga – Topography Map

The project site's topography is relatively a flat terrain.

CSFP TOPO MAP

Figure 2.3.1.4.f. 1 Topography Map

Retrieved from City Planning and Development Coordinator's Office

g. Tax Declaration

TAX DECLARATION OF REAL PROPERTY

RPTA Form No. 1

City Ordinance No. 2017-025

ARP/TD No.: **18-0011-03894**

PIN: **205-00-0011-035-69**

Owner: S.P. Realty Development Corp

Address: SBC Bldg., II Del Pilar, City of San Fernando

Admin/Ben. User/

Occupant:

Address:

Location of Property _____ **DOLORES/00** _____ **San Fernando**
Street & Subdivision *Barangay/District* *City*

OCT/TCT/CLOA No.: 042-2016009987

Survey No.: Psd-03-218345

CCT:

Lot Number: 3574-C-14- F

Unit No.

Block Number:

BOUNDARIES:

North: L-3574-C-14- A, B, C, D & E

South: L-3514

East: L-3574-AA; 3574-C-10

West: L-3574-C-5, 7, 8 & 9

KIND OF PROPERTY ASSESSED

LAND

MACHINERY

BUILDING

OTHERS
Specify:

CLASS/KIND	AREA (sq.m.)	MARKET VALUE	ACTUAL USE	ASSMNT. LEVEL	ASSESSED VALUE	TAXABILITY
RES	86,242.50	77,618,250.00	RES	20	15,523,650.00	TAXABLE
COM	9,449.50	37,798,000.00	COM	40	15,119,200.00	TAXABLE
TOTAL	95,692.00	115,416,250.00			30,642,850.00	
Total Assessed Value:		THIRTY MILLION SIX HUNDRED FORTY-TWO THOUSAND EIGHT HUNDRED FIFTY PESOS ONLY				

(Amount in Words)

Effectivity of Assessment/Reassessment: _____ 2018
 RECOMMENDED BY: _____ Qtr Year

APPROVED BY:

LUZ T. BAUTISTA, PhD
 OIC-City Assessor

Owner's Copy

This declaration cancels ARP/TD No.: 09-0011-13984

Owner: S.P. Realty Development Corp

Previous A.V.: 19,971,080

MEMORANDA:

Figure 2.3.1.4.g. 1 Tax Declaration

Retrieved from Municipal Hall of City of San Fernando

**LAND REGISTRATION AUTHORITY
CERTIFIED TRUE COPY VERIFICATION FORM**

Judicial Form No. 109

TCT No.: 042-2016009987

Page No.: 2

TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION (Continued from page 1)

BOUNDARIES:

LINE	DIRECTION	ADJOINING LOT(S)
1-2	SE	LOT 3574-A (LRC), PSD-03-258959
2-3-4	SE	LOT 3574-A (LRC), PSD-258959
4-5-6	SE	LOT 3574-C-10, PSD- 03-017314
6-7	SW	LOT 3514 CAD. 71, SAN FERNANDO CAD.
7-8	NW	LOT 3574-C-5, PSD-03- 017314
8-9	NW	LOT 3574-C-7, PSD-03- 017314
9-10	NW	LOT 3574-C-8, PSD-03- 017314
10-11	NW	LOT 3674-C-9, PSD-03- 017314
11-12-13-14-15	NW	LOT 3574-C-9, PSD-03- 017314
15-16	NE	LOT 3574-C-14-A, PSD- 03-218345
16-17-18	NE	LOT 3574-C-14-B, PSD- 03-218345
18-19	NE	LOT 3574-C-14-C, PSD- 03-218345
19-20	NE	LOT 3574-C-14-D, PSD- 03-218345
20-1	NE	LOT 3574-C-14-E, PSD- 03-218345

TIE POINT: BBM NO. 24, CAD 71, MUNICIPALITY OF SAN FERNANDO, PROVINCE OF PAMPANGA

LINE	BEARING	DISTANCE
TO CORNER 1	S. 01° 48' E	285.71 M.
1-2	S. 57° 57' W	147.21 M.
2-3	S. 62° 27' W	19.42 M.
3-4	S. 57° 05' W	17.38 M.
4-5	N. 47° 34' W	166.42 M.
5-6	S. 41° 33' W	44.82 M.
6-7	N. 48° 27' W	133.07 M.
7-8	N. 26° 41' E	47.13 M.
8-9	N. 26° 41' E	21.12 M.
9-10	N. 26° 41' E	21.25 M.

Figure 2.3.1.4.h. 2 Page 2 of 4 Transfer Certificate of Title

Retrieved from Registry of Deeds

LAND REGISTRATION AUTHORITY
CERTIFIED TRUE COPY VERIFICATION FORM

Judicial Form No. 109

TCT No.: 042-2016009987

Page No.: 3

10-11	N.	27	°	47	'	E	17.83 M.
11-12	N.	50	°	39	'	W	29.40 M.
12-13	N.	33	°	49	'	E	23.61 M.
13-14	N.	63	°	19	'	W	28.50 M.
14-15	N.	27	°	07	'	E	146.17 M.
15-16	S.	58	°	04	'	E	154.39 M.
16-17	S.	58	°	04	'	E	24.28 M.
17-18	S.	35	°	00	'	E	102.63 M.
18-19	S.	35	°	00	'	E	55.52 M.
19-20	S.	35	°	00	'	E	83.26 M.
20-1	S.	35	°	00	'	E	67.36 M.

AREA: NINETY FIVE THOUSAND SIX HUNDRED NINETY TWO SQUARE METERS
(95692), MORE OR LESS

DESCRIPTION OF CORNERS: PS CYL. CONC. MONS. 15 X 40 CMS.,

BEARINGS: TRUE

DECLINATION:

DATE OF ORIGINAL SURVEY: MARCH 1915-APRIL 1916

DATE OF SUBD/CONS SURVEY: DECEMBER 03, 2015

DATE OF APPROVED SURVEY: JANUARY 22, 2016

GEODETIC ENGINEER: ALFEO S. GALANG

NOTES:

It is hereby certified that this is a true electronic copy of TCT 2016009987 on file in Registry of Deeds of San Fernando, Pampanga, which consists of 4 page(s). This is a system-generated Certified True Copy, and does not require a manually-affixed signature. Printed at Registry of Deeds of San Fernando, Pampanga. Requested By: LARA JA NIEL CHARVEY BUSTOS

Ref. : 2023030855 OR No. : 1031542223
Date : 10/11/2023 OR Date : Oct 11 2023
Time : 03:23:03 PM Amt Paid : 273.35

Page 3 of 4

LTCP Form No.: 0019 version 3
(revision date: 2022.10.01)

Figure 2.3.1.4.h. 3 Page 3 of 4 Transfer Certificate of Title

Retrieved from Registry of Deeds

Judicial Form No. 109

TCT No. : 042-2016009987

Page No. : 4

MEMORANDUM OF ENCUMBRANCES

Entry No. : 4450

Date: August 28, 1998 03:45:00PM

. : LEASE AGREEMENT- PURSUANT TO THE LEASE AGREEMENT EXECUTED BY AND BETWEEN S.P. REALTY & DEV'T CORP. & TOTAL PETROLEUM PHILS. CORP. A PORTION OF 4,500 SQUARE METERS OF THE PROPERTY COVERED IN THIS TITLE IS PLACED UNDER LEASE FOR A PERIOD OF 15 YEARS AND 6 MONTHS DOC. NO. 269; PAGE NO. 55; BOOK NO. VII; SERIES OF 1998 OF N.P. EMMAUEL C. PARS OF MAKATI, DATED APRIL 13, 1998.

Entry No. : 2700

Date: May 05, 2008 08:30:00AM

. : CONTRACT OF LEASE BY AND BETWEEN S.P. REALTY & DEV'T CORP AND NORTHWALK LAND INC.,- AFFECTING A PORTION OF 4500 SQUARE METERS OVER THE LOT HEREIN DESCRIBED IS PLACED UNDER LEASE FROM SEPT. 1, 2007 UNTIL AUGUST 31, 2030 OTHER CONDITIONS SET FORTH IN THE DEED ON FILE IN THIS OFFICE, DOC. NO. 719; PAGE NO. IX; BOOK NO. IV; SERIES OF 2007 OF N.P. FRANCISCO TAALA OF Q.C. DATED OCT. 08, 2007.

LORNA M. SALANGSANG-DEE
Register of Deeds IV

It is hereby certified that this is a true electronic copy of TCT 2016009987 on file in Registry of Deeds of San Fernando, Pampanga, which consists of 4 page(s). This is a system-generated Certified True Copy, and does not require a manually-affixed signature. Printed at Registry of Deeds of San Fernando, Pampanga. Requested By: LARA JA NIEL CHARVEY BUSTOS

Ref. : 2023030855 OR No. : 1031542223
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Page 4 of 4

LTCP Form No.: 0019 version 3
(revision date: 2022.10.01)

Figure 2.3.1.4.h. 4 Page 4 of 4 Transfer Certificate of Title

Retrieved from Registry of Deeds

i. Project Site Lot Bearings

The Total Lot Area of the project site is approximately 95,692 square meters (9.5 hectares) with twenty (20) Lot Bearings.

POINT	BEARING				DISTANCE	
TO CORNER 1	S.	01°	48'	E	285.71	M.
1-2	S.	57°	57'	W	147.21	M.
2-3	S.	62°	27'	W	19.42	M.
3-4	S.	57°	05'	W	17.38	M.
4-5	N.	47°	34'	W	166.42	M.
5-6	S.	41°	33'	W	44.82	M.
6-7	N.	48°	27'	W	133.07	M.
7-8	N.	26°	41'	E	47.13	M.
8-9	N.	26°	41'	E	21.12	M.
9-10	N.	26°	41'	E	21.25	M.
10-11	N.	27°	47'	E	17.83	M.
11-12	N.	50°	39'	W	29.40	M.
12-13	N.	33°	49'	E	23.61	M.
13-14	N.	63°	19'	W	28.50	M.
14-15	N.	27°	07'	E	146.17	M.
15-16	S.	58°	04'	E	154.39	M.
16-17	S.	58°	04'	E	24.28	M.
17-18	S.	35°	00'	E	102.63	M.
18-19	S.	35°	00'	E	55.52	M.
19-20	S.	35°	00'	E	83.26	M.
20-1	S.	35°	00'	E	67.36	M.

Table 2.3.1.4.i. 1 Project Site Lot Bearings

Retrieved from Transfer Certificate of Title

j. Shape of the Project Lot

Figure 2.3.1.4.j. 1 Shape of the Lot

Retrieved from Transfer Certificate of Title

2.3.1.5 PROJECT SITE JUSTIFICATION

Advantages:

- Located within the Business District of San Fernando City.
- Located along a major road (Jose Abad Santos Ave) and nearby the NLEX.
- Accessible for public (nearby bus terminal) and private transportation.
- Located nearby the City Tourism Office, SM Pampanga, Robinsons Starmills, Azure North Pampanga and other similar developments.
- Not prone to flooding.

Disadvantages:

- Having only one main road access can lead to heavy vehicular traffic congestion especially during rush hours and special holidays.

2.3.1.6 PROXIMITY TO RELATED PROJECTS

As stated in Chapter One under the statement of the problem, there are no current projects similar to the researcher’s proposal, making the proposed study entitled “Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex” the first Kapampangan Cultural Complex in San Fernando City, Pampanga. However, there are some related projects, such as cultural centers, typically museums and libraries, that are located within the vicinity of Pampanga.

The table below showcases some examples of well-known cultural centers, their location, and approximate travel distance from the proposed site.

NAME	LOCATION	DISTANCE FROM THE SITE
Museum of Philippine Arts and Culture (MOPAC)	Ramar Village, San Agustin, City of San Fernando, Pampanga	Approximately 3.6 km
Santungan ning Kulturang Kapampangan (SKK) Hall	Sto. Nino, San Fernando, Pampanga	Approximately 3.2 km
San Fernando Old Train Station Museum	Saturn Street, San Fernando, 2000 Pampanga	Approximately 3.5 km

Table 2.3.1.6. 1 Proximity of Related Projects within San Fernando City

Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/maps>

NAME	LOCATION	DISTANCE FROM THE SITE
Museo Ning Angeles	Heritage District, Santo Rosario Street, Angeles City	Approximately 15.5 km
Center for Kapampangan Studies	Holy Angel University, Angles City	Approximately 15.5 km
Angeles City Library	Heritage District, Santo Rosario Street, Angeles City	Approximately 15.5 km
Museum of Philippine Social History	Santo Entierro Street, Angeles City	Approximately 15.5 km
Museo at Aklatan ni Diosdado Macapagal	San Nicolas I, Lubao, Pampanga	Approximately 16 km
Clark Museum	Sergio Osmeña, Clark Freeport Zone, Mabalacat, Pampanga	Approximately 35.4 km

Table 2.3.1.6. 2 Proximity of Related Projects within Pampanga

Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/maps>

2.3.1.7 PROJECT SITE FIGURES

a. Site Pictures

Figure 2.3.1.7.a. 1 Front View
Retrieved from Google Earth

Figure 2.3.1.7.a. 2 Aerial View
Retrieved from Google Earth

Figure 2.3.1.7.a. 3 Lot Frontage
Retrieved from camera gallery

Figure 2.3.1.7.a. 4 Left Side View
Retrieved from camera gallery

Figure 2.3.1.7.a. 5 Frontage with JASA and Northwalk
Retrieved from camera gallery

Figure 2.3.1.7.a. 6 Right Side View
Retrieved from camera gallery

b. Site Location

Figure 2.3.1.7.b. 1 Project Site Location

Retrieved from Google Earth

Figure 2.3.1.7.b. 2 Project Site Location

Retrieved from Google Earth

c. Site Analysis

Figure 2.3.1.7.c. 1 Project Site Analysis

d. Vicinity Map

Figure 2.3.1.7.d. 1 Vicinity Map

CHAPTER 3: DATA PRESENTATION

CONTENTS:

3.1 PRESENTATION OF GATHERED DATA

3.2 ARCHITECTURAL PROGRAMMING

3.1 PRESENTATION OF GATHERED DATA

3.1.1 SURVEY RESULTS

Consent Form

Figure 3.1.1. 1 Consent Form

The chart above showcases that 100% (125) of the 125 participants have read and agreed to become a participant of the study.

Demographic Profile

Name (optional)

• Chaiyer	• Micah	• Andy Manaloto	• Jasmine Rubio	• Maki
• Mary Grace	• Aliza Margie Musngi	• Leo Angelo	• Ellyn P. Soriano	• Tim Pangilinan
• John Rei	• Pauldoh	• Leilani Iaxamana	• Jhen Lazatin	• Sheen turla
• Vinz	• Jean Yrra Mutuc	• KJ	• Jorel Kent L. Figueroa	• Dranyel L. Quiambao
• Angelo	• Divina Basilio Espiritu	• mark solemn castro	• Marichelle Reyes	• Jeremiah Chan
• Totep	• Tolentino, Zeane Francis	• Joy Lyn Cagungun	• Jerome S. Cordova	• Tula, Fitz Jericho S.
• John Daryl Montano	• Kristine Cassandra Intal	• g	• Roman Salazar	• Fatima pangan
• Carl	• Yanika Sundry Roman	• Miko Panlilio	• Anne	• Mary Anne D. Garcia
• Lalaine Dela Pena	• Reynan lazatin	• Sean Sebastian	• MELANIE LULU	• Arlene Javier
• Patricia P. Yumul	• rosola s. teodosio	• Tony	• Mariel	• Rhielyn Park
• Alessandra	• Divina Gracia Sindac	• Kean		
• Julie	• Allen garcia	• Mark Anthony		
• Christian Gabriel R. Dizon	• Dan Guevarra.	• Aviane Del Rosario		
• Jenny-Vi Landayan	• Carmel C Deang	• Sen		
• Kristine Joy	• Jennilyn P. Mallari	• Kathreen Condino		
		• jhoane		
		• JOVS		

Figure 3.1.1. 2 Name

The figure above showcases that 67 out of the 125 participants submitted their names.

Email (optional)

Figure 3.1.1. 3 Email

The figure above showcases that 42 out of the 125 participants submitted their emails.

Age

Figure 3.1.1. 4 Age

The chart above shows that 58.4% (73) of the 125 participants belongs to the age group of 18 to 25 years old, 22.4% (28) are 26 to 40 years old, 12% (15) are 41 to 59 years old, 6.4% (8) are under 18 years old, and 0.8% (1) is 60 years old and above.

Gender

Figure 3.1.1. 5 Gender

The chart above shows that 50.4% (63) of the 125 participants are male, while 49.6% (62) of the participants are female.

Occupation

Figure 3.1.1. 6 Occupation

The chart above shows that 52% (65) of the 125 participants are students, 23.2% (29) are unemployed, 14.4% (18) are employed, and 10.4% (13) are self-employed.

Address

Figure 3.1.1. 7 Address

The chart above shows that 28% (35) are from Santa Ana, 16.8% (21) from Arayat, 12.8% (16) from Mexico, 11.2% (14) from Apalit, 10.4% (13) from Candaba, 6.4% (8) from San Fernando, 3.2% (4) from Santo Tomas, 2.4% (3) from San Simon, 1.6% (2) from San Luis, 1.6% (2) from Minalin, 1.6% (2) from Macabebe, 1.6% (2) from Guagua, 0.8% (1) from Lubao, 0.8% (1) from Magalang, and 0.8% (1) are from Florida Blanca.

Part I. Background of the Project

Figure 3.1.1. 8 Question 1

The chart above shows that 83.2% (104) of the 125 participants answered yes, while 16.8% (21) of them answered no.

Figure 3.1.1. 9 Question 2

The chart above shows that 56.8% (71) of the 125 participants answered yes, while 43.2% (54) of them answered no.

Figure 3.1.1. 10 Question 3

The chart above shows that 100% (125) of the 125 participants all answered yes.

Figure 3.1.1. 11 Question 4

The chart above shows that 99.2% (125) of the 125 participants answered yes, while 0.8% (1) answered no.

Figure 3.1.1. 12 Question 5

The chart above shows that 99.2% (125) of the 125 participants answered yes, while 0.8% (1) answered no.

Part II. Facilities and Experience

Figure 3.1.1. 13 Question 6

The chart above shows that 76% (95) of the 125 participants answered History of Pampanga Exhibit, 69.6% (87) for Local Kapampangan Workshops, 65.6% (82) for Outdoor Grand Plaza, 63.2% (79) for Art Exhibit, 60.8% (76) for Culinary Exhibit, 52.8% (66) for Main Museum, 45.6% (57) for Grand Theater, 41.6% (52) for Festival Exhibit, 41.6% (52) for Library Café, 40.8% (51) for Music and Dance Exhibit, 39.2% (49) for Commercial Shops, and 36.8% (46) for 4D Theater.

2. Are there any other specific facilities that you wish to see/visit in the project?

Please specify. (Mayroon ka pa bang ibang pasilidad na nais makita at bisitahin sa proyekto?

Kung mayroon paki-sulat sa patlang.)

Additional facilities that the participants wish to see/visit are: Religious Exhibits, Outdoor Gallery Walk, Traditional Kapampangan Games Area, Souvenir Workshops, and Temporary Exhibits for the present time. Most of the participants suggestions gave emphasis on having an exhibit for the Kapampangan History, Arts and Culinary. Moreover, a participant also suggested to incorporate informative signages and displays in every exhibit to act as a guide and to fully immerse the visitors of the project.

Figure 3.1.1. 14 Question 8

The chart above shows that 72% (90) of the 125 participants answered Highly Educational, 64.8% (81) for Festive and Colorful, and 52.8% (66) for Serene and Peaceful.

Part III. Project Significance

Figure 3.1.1. 15 Question 9

The chart above shows that 81.6% (102) of the 125 participants answered Strongly Agree, 12.8% (16) for Agree, 1.6% (2) for Neutral, and 4% (5) for Strongly Disagree.

Figure 3.1.1. 16 Question 10

The chart above shows that 74.4% (93) of the 125 participants answered Strongly Agree, 17.6% (22) for Agree, 3.2% (4) for Neutral, and 4.8% (6) for Strongly Disagree.

Figure 3.1.1. 17 Question 11

The chart above shows that 78.4% (98) of the 125 participants answered Strongly Agree, 9.6% (12) for Agree, 5.6% (7) for Neutral, and 6.4% (8) for Strongly Disagree.

Figure 3.1.1. 18 Question 12

The chart above shows that 77.6% (97) of the 125 participants answered Strongly Agree, 12.8% (16) for Agree, 4% (5) for Neutral, 1.6% (2) Disagree, and 4% (5) for Strongly Disagree.

Do you have any other comments or thoughts you wish to share about the project “**Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex**”? If so, please leave a note below. Thank you for your participation!

- Padayon po sa Thesis! (wala na pong makita na butas sa topic)
- PADAYON! FOR KAPAMPANGAN CULTURE!
- Maganda ang proyekto para sa kulturang kapampangan
- To address the noticeable decline in the use of the kapampangan language particularly among younger generations, a cultural complex that serves as a hub for preserving and promoting our linguistic heritage to encourage the active use and appreciation of Kapampangan culture.
- It's a brilliant idea! Greatly wishing you a goodluck on your thesis journey po~~ and definitely rooting for your delightful success. Padayon! :)
- Sharing your talents and passion to our kabalens is a huge blessing for pampanga. May you all be part of Pampanga's success and put your heart and mind to everything you do. Wishing you all the best ☺🍀
- Mas lalo pagandahan para maka engganyo sa mga tao
- I appreciate the initiative to promote Kapampangan culture and the preservation of it.
- Mapanatili sana ang orihinal n kultura ng mga kapampangan. 🇵🇭
- sana mahikayat na palaganapin ang kulturang kapampangan.gudluck po
- The research is excellent, and a cultural center would be a valuable resource to truly understand and appreciate the rich culture of the Kapampangans.
- none, thankyou for understanding have a nice day
- Luid ya ing kapampangan! Good luck and God bless!
- Make it more interactive po and more serene at the same time sana
- It would represent the essence of Kapampangan Culture! Goodluck! 🍀
- Sakin gusto ko lang na it is interactive and it will give a fun experience to the end users
- wala na kasi parang kumpleto na yung project
- Go go go
- I hope na magkaroon ng ganito sa Pampanga.
- It is exciting to have a culture, arts ad tourism complex that promotes our own or local area here in Pampanga.

Figure 3.1.1. 19 Comments

- It is a well thought and comprehensive thesis study.
- Very good idea about this project
- Amazing 🤩
- i hope that this project will push through. due to digital age, the traditions are slowly dying. It is better that we may preserve our heritage and tradition for the future generation.
- kailangan pahalagahan ng bawat kapampangan ang atin nakagisnan kultura dito sa Pampanga
- Walkable, Easy to access one building to another through comfortable walk paths
- I hope this project will help the tourism and economic growth of pampanga
- Best of luck!
- Pagyamanin at pahalagan Ang kulturang kapampangan upang sa paglipas man ng pamahon itoy pakinabang ng mga susunod pang henarasyon.
- good for school tours
- I wish to give heritages the provilage for every kapampangab
- It could enhance and preserve the Kapampangan culture. It has the potential to serve as a hub for local artisans, artists, and cultural practitioners, fostering community engagement and education. By integrating tourism, it could also boost the local economy while highlighting the pampanga's rich heritage. Looks like a good project Godspeed!
- isulong ang proyekto
- Add a facility/activity that teaches kapampangan language
- It is good to consider that they represent modern practices
- Goodluck Kapampangan Culture
- Looking forward to visit this kind of project someday

Figure 3.1.1. 20 Comments

The figures above showcase the participants comments and suggestions about the proposed project entitled Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex.

3.1.1.1 SURVEY RESULTS SUMMARY

The survey results presented above showcases data that supports the project proposal's feasibility, where majority of the participants are familiar with the project, are interested to visit and have agreed to have a cultural complex for Pampanga. Moreover, the data gathered also presents that majority of the participants have agreed that the proposed project is culturally, socially, and economically significant and relevant for the province of Pampanga.

3.1.2 INTERVIEW RESULTS

This chapter presents the demographic profile of the participants and the summary of their answers from the conducted personal structured interview.

3.1.2.1 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE:

TOURISM OFFICER / REPRESENTATIVE OF SAN FERNANDO CITY

Figure 3.1.2.1. A

Name: Architect Camille P. Mercado

Age Bracket: 26 – 40 years old

Gender: Female

Occupation: Employed (Architect & Head of the Cultural Department of San Fernando Tourism Office)

Address: San Fernando City, Pampanga

A KAPAMPANGAN CULINARY EXPERT

Figure 3.1.2.1. B

Name: Lilian Mercado Lising Borromeo

Age Bracket: 60 years old and above

Gender: Female

Occupation: Self-Employed (A Kapampangan Culinary Chef and Historian)

Address: Mexico, Pampanga

A KAPAMPANGAN ARTIST

Figure 3.1.2.1. C

Name: Architect Berlin Guanlao

Age Bracket: 26 – 40 years old

Gender: Male

Occupation: Employed (Architect Professor in the University of the Assumption)

Address: Guagua, Pampanga

A KAPAMPANGAN MUSICIAN/PERFORMER

Figure 3.1.2.1. D

Name: Aljon P. Simbillo

Age Bracket: 26 – 40 years old

Gender: Male

Occupation: Employed (Professor in Sta. Ana Public School)

Address: Sta. Ana, Pampanga

A KAPAMPANGAN WRITER

Figure 3.1.2.1. E

Name: Roilingel Puno Calilung

Age Bracket: 26 – 40 years old

Gender: Male

Occupation: Employed (Librarian & Professor in University of the Assumption)

Address: San Fernando City, Pampanga

A KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL HISTORIAN

Figure 3.1.2.1. F

Name: Leonardo R. Calma Jr.

Age Bracket: 26 – 40 years old

Gender: Male

Occupation: Employed (Multimedia Creative Director of the Center for Kapampangan Studies)

Address: Angeles City, Pampanga

A RLA KNOWLEDGABLE IN DESIGNING CULTURAL CENTERS

Figure 3.1.2.1. G

Name: Architect Joseph Lideson Mallari

Age Bracket: 41 – 59 years old

Gender: Male

Occupation: Employed (Architect)

Address: Sta. Ana, Pampanga

3.1.2.2 SUMMARY OF ANSWERS:

GENERAL QUESTIONS

1. Define the culture of Pampanga.

- **According to Madam Borromeo (Culinary Expert)**, Kapampangan cuisine is defined as the cuisine that uses the best ingredients to create food that is hearty and flavorful. Moreover, food that is made by an authentic Kapampangan is rich, appetizing and packed with flavor.

- **According to Ar. Guanlao (Artist)**, Kapampangan Art is a melting pot of art styles influenced by a number of diverse cultures (Spanish, American, and Japanese), but with a Kapampangan twist. He explained that Kapampangan artists' get inspiration from other cultures which they then adopt and translate in their own perspective, therefore producing a unique work of art that is Kapampangan.
- **According to Mr. Simbillo (Musician/Performer)**, Kapampangan Music is a form of artistic expression through song. It is a conduit for the Kapampangans to convey their story and thoughts to other people. Music for the Kapampangans is a way of life, it is part of their cultural identity. This is evidently seen in Kapampangan celebrations, such as festivals, mass, funerals, weddings, and many more.
- **According to Mr. Calilung (Writer)**, Kapampangan Literature is anything that is spoken and written in the language of Kapampangan.
- **According to Mr. Calma (Cultural Historian)**, the word "culture" is a very broad term that cannot be defined and explain in a few sentences. He explained that culture is something that can be seen or touch (tangible) and it can also be something that we do and believe (intangible). Furthermore, culture is dynamic and is continually evolving, therefore, to define the Kapampangan culture is not an easy task to do, but it is not impossible. Mr. Calma explained that the Kapampangan culture is the very essence that makes someone a true Kapampangan. Kapampangan Culture is the very heart and soul or the foundation of the Kapampangan identity, and without it not only will their cultural heritage die but also their sense of identity.

2. Explain the importance of Kapampangan cultural preservation and promotion.

- All interview participants have stated that the importance of Kapampangan cultural preservation and promotion is to ensure that it will not be lost and forgotten, and for it to be passed on to the next generation. They all agreed that the culture of Kapampangan cuisine, arts, music and dance, literary, history, festivals and religious celebrations are all part of their cultural identity. These are what makes them who they are, their cultural background is part of what makes them Kapampangan and without it one will lose who they are.

3. Problems that the Kapampangan culture faces in today's generation and their current solutions.

- All interview participants have stated that the problems they face are the lack or inadequate support from the government, the lack of proper facilities dedicated to hosts and promote Pampanga's cultural celebrations and heritage, and the ignorance of the younger generations. These factors negatively affect people's views about Kapampangan culture, deeming them unimportant, unappreciated and unrecognized especially by the younger generations and if left unaddressed could lead to the Kapampangan culture being lost and forgotten. The current temporary solutions available to address these issues involves hosting seasonal events inside shopping malls such as SM and Robinsons and the formation of different small and private projects such as the Center for Kapampangan Studies dedicated to preserve the Kapampangan culture in their own unique ways.

4. Explain the significance of the proposed project entitled Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex in preserving and promoting the Kapampangan culture.

- All interview participants strongly agrees that the proposed project would significantly help in uplifting, preserving and promoting the Kapampangan culture by providing a platform where the Kapampangan culture is alive and celebrated. They stated that having a dedicated place for cultural celebration could benefit Pampanga's economy by boosting its tourisms and would encourage cultural appreciation and recognition, especially for the younger generations. Moreover, the proposed project is a great opportunity for the Kapampangan locals to thrive and for Pampanga to be known globally and internationally.

5. Spaces/facilities/features to consider in designing the proposed project, to honor and host the Kapampangan culture.

Spaces/facilities/features that the participants have shared includes: museum, library, archives, an indoor and outdoor theater, an open plaza, an open kitchen or culinarium, multipurpose halls, commercial stalls for local workshops, souvenir shops, restaurants, food park, food stalls, parks and playground and to have a number of parking spaces for accessibility.

SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

1. What is tourism and explain its importance.

- **According to Ar. Mercado (Tourism Officer SF)**, tourism means to visit, where people from different places visits a certain place. Tourism involves the

people who travel to places with the purpose of site seeing and immersing themselves in the culture of that place.

2. What are Pampanga's tourist spots and explain its tourism patterns.

- **According to Ar. Mercado (Tourism SF)**, tourists visiting Pampanga generally visits SM (the longest mall in the Philippines), Mt. Pinatubo, and Clark, while here in San Fernando City, for the tourists to experience the Kapampangan culture, the SF tourism office usually encourage visitors to visit the local Kapampangan restaurants such as Apag Marangle and Bale Capampangan, the San Fernando public market and some well-known museums in San Fernando such as the MOPAC (Museum of Philippine Arts and Culture), and the Paskuhan Office.

3. Key points to consider to design an effective cultural center project.

- **According to Ar. Mallari (RLA)**, in order to design an effective cultural project, it is important to conduct research to gather the necessary data required to support the project. Gathered information will serve as a guide and basis to create an effective and accurate cultural center project.

4. Key points to consider to achieve interactivity in a cultural center project.

- **According to Ar. Mallari (RLA)**, the incorporation of modern technology such as LED visual screens, kiosks machines, and holographic projections is a way to create an interactive and fun cultural project. Moreover, interactivity can also be achieved through space planning and circulation and by designing the structure in a fun and attractive way, to immerse and encourage the users to visit the project.

5. Key points to consider to achieve sustainability in a cultural center project.

- **According to Ar. Mallari (RLA)**, to achieved sustainability it is important to design buildings that will not become a white elephant. He stated that sustainability is not only about creating green spaces and adapting renewable solutions, it is also about creating functional spaces that will be used for a very long time.

6. Key points to consider to design an iconic cultural center project.

- **According to Ar. Mallari (RLA)**, to design an iconic cultural project it is important to have a clear and definitive concept. The concept or the inspiration behind the design of the project is what makes a project unique, iconic, and well-known. Moreover, the concept should have a significant connection to the culture that the project wishes to represent for this will be the basis for the project's design.

3.1.2.3 INTERVIEW RESULTS SUMMARY

The interview results presented above showcases gathered data about Pampanga's cultural and tourism patterns, the importance of cultural preservation, the current problems involving cultural preservation and celebration, the project's significance, and architectural solutions. These gathered data further support the proposed project's feasibility, relevance and significance, moreover, it would serve as the researcher's guide in developing the architectural plans for the proposed project.

3.1.3 SECONDARY DATA RESULTS

The data presented below will serve as the researcher’s guide in developing the architectural design of the proposed project and acts as a supporting data further reinforcing the project’s feasibility, significance and relevance.

3.1.3.1 CULTURAL TABLE OF PAMPANGA

Presented below is a table that showcases the Kapampangan culture of each municipality in Pampanga in terms of art, cuisine, festivals / celebrations, religious celebrations, and a brief description about the town.

MUNICIPALITY	DESCRIPTION	ART	CUISINE	FESTIVALS / CELEBRATIONS	RELIGIOUS CELEBRATIONS
San Fernando City	Named after King Philip VI of Spain. It is the capital city of Pampanga also known as the “Christmas Capital of the Philippines” due to its famous industry of lantern making.	Parul (Lantern Making)	Tocino Longanisa Panara Ensaymada Kamaru Betute	Giant Lantern Festival Kapampangan Frog Festival Sinukwan Festival El Circulo Fernandino	Feast of San Fernando San Pedro Cutud Rites / Maleido
Angeles City	It is known as the “Entertainment Capital of Pampanga” also known as “City of Angels.” Its former name was called “Culiat” which was derived from the abundant vines of the area.	Burarul (Kite Making)	Empanada Empanadita Silvana Halo-Halo (Corazon Style) Pansit Luglug Galang galang Silvana Sisig (Aling Lucing Style)	Sisig Festival Tigtigan Terakan keng Dalan	Feast of Apung Macalulu Kuliat Festival Nuestra Senora del Santisimo Rosario de la Naval de Angeles Feast Day
Apalit	Named after the local tree species called “Apalit” or pterocarpus indicus. It is a town in Pampanga that is known for its black smith industries.	Pukpuk Kupia (Hat Making) Santos Gawang Pande (Black Smith)	Puto Seco Espasol		Apung Iru Fluvial Festival St. Peter the Apostle Feast Day
Arayat	Was once called “Dayat” which means irrigated farmlands. A town in Pampanga that is located at the foothills of Mount Arayat.		Samani Halo-Halo (Kabigting Style) Pansit Luglug	Manga Festival	St. Catherine of Alexandria Feast Day
Bacolor	Known as the former capital of Pampanga during the British occupation from 1762 to 1763. It is home to the oldest church in the Philippines the San Guillermo Church.	Santos	Putu Lazon Bobotu Kutsinta Suman (tili, bulagta, ebus) Kalame (biko, nasi, ale, duman, kapit, kopis)	Makatapak Festival	

Table 3.1.3.1. 1 Cultural Table 1

The table above showcases the Kapampangan culture and brief description of Pampanga’s municipalities namely: San Fernando City, Angeles City, Apalit, Arayat and Bacolor.

MUNICIPALITY	DESCRIPTION	ART	CUISINE	FESTIVALS / CELEBRATIONS	RELIGIOUS CELEBRATIONS
Candaba	<p>A town in Pampanga known for its fishing and farming industries.</p> <p>The Candaba swamp is a famous tourist destination of the town where thousands of birds and ducks migrate during the winter season of Siberia and China.</p> <p>It is famous for making "Burong Asan" or fermented fish paste.</p>	Dase (Weaving Mats Making)	Burong Asan (Fermented Fish)	Ibon-Ebon Festival	St. Andrew the Apostle Feast Day
Florida Blanca	<p>A town in Pampanga where the "Basa Air Base of the Philippines" is located.</p> <p>Also known as the "Rice Granary of the Pampanga."</p>	Pottery		<p>Pinukpukan Festival</p> <p>Sukit Festival</p>	St. Joseph the Worker Feast Day
Guagua	<p>Named after the word "Wawa" which means mouth of the river, due to its riverside location.</p> <p>A town in Pampanga known for its arts and crafts of wood carving.</p>	<p>Pukpuk</p> <p>Ukit Dukit (Wood Carving)</p> <p>Santos</p> <p>Gitara (Guitar Making)</p>	<p>Burung Paro (Fermented Shrimp)</p> <p>Halo-Halo (Razon Style)</p> <p>Pansit Luglug</p>	Sabuaga Festival	La Purisima Concepcion Feast Day
Lubao	<p>Named after the word "Lubo" which means low.</p> <p>It is considered to be as the oldest town of Pampanga.</p>				<p>St. Augustine of Hippo Feast Day</p> <p>St. Catherine of Alexandria Feast Day</p>
Mabalacat City	<p>Named after the word "Balacat" which is a class of timber, and was originally occupied by the Aetas with Caragan as their chief.</p> <p>It is a component city due to its various industrial establishments.</p>		Putung Galang-Galang	<p>Philippine Hot Air Balloon Festival</p> <p>Caragan Festival</p>	Nuestra Senora de la Divia Gracia Feast Day
Macabebe	The name "Macabebe" means bordering river banks due to its location along Pampanga River.	Santos			St. Nicholas of Tolentine Feast Day

Table 3.1.3.1. 2 Cultural Table 2

The table above showcases the Kapampangan culture and brief description of Pampanga’s municipalities namely: Candaba, Florida Blanca, Guagua, Lubao, Mabalacat City, and Macabebe.

MUNICIPALITY	DESCRIPTION	ART	CUISINE	FESTIVALS / CELEBRATIONS	RELIGIOUS CELEBRATIONS
Magalang	<p>Another town that is located at the foothill of Mount Arayat.</p> <p>It is believed that its name derived from the Indonesian first settlers who were called "Magaleng."</p> <p>It is known for making creamy delicacies made from Carabao's milk such as the Pastillas De Leche.</p>		<p>Pastillas De Leche</p> <p>Yemas</p> <p>Tibuk Tibuk</p> <p>Kalame Kopis</p>		St. Bartholomew the Apostle Feast Day
Masantol	<p>It is named after the word "santol" a sour fruit also known as sour apple or cotton fruit which is commonly used for cooking.</p> <p>Masantol was formerly part of Macabebe, but in the year 1878 became a town of its own.</p>		<p>Tabang Talangka</p> <p>Sigang Palapat</p>	<p>Palapat Festival</p> <p>Tabang Talangka Festival</p>	<p>Cruzada Festival</p> <p>Batalla Festival</p> <p>Batala Apu Lucia</p>
Mexico	<p>A town located near San Fernando City.</p> <p>Its name came from the word "Masiku" which means elbowed, due to its location in the elbow of the Abacan River.</p> <p>While others say that its name came from the word "Chico" a sweet fruit that is abundant in the area.</p>		<p>Dulciprenda</p> <p>Panecillos de San Angelo (Angel Biscuits)</p> <p>Sanikulas Cookies</p> <p>Mayumung Kamatis (Sweetened Tomatoes)</p> <p>Ebun Barag</p>		<p>San Nicolas Festival</p> <p>Saint Monica Feast Day</p>
Minalin	<p>Its name came from the Kapampangan word "Minalis" which means to move.</p> <p>It is known as the "Egg Basket of Luzon" as it is a large producer of chickens and eggs.</p>			Aguman Sanduk Festival	Apung Monica Fluvial Festival
Porac	<p>Its name was derived from the word "Purag" or "Kurag" which is a kind of rattan plant that grows near the river.</p> <p>It is well-known for its "Uraro" a cookies delicacy made out of roots crops powder, eggs, milk and sugar.</p>		<p>Uraro Cookies</p> <p>Binulang Bia</p>	Binulu Festival	St. Catherine of Alexandria Feast Day
San Luis	<p>It was originally named "Cabagsak" which is derived from the huge amount of fruit bats propagating in the town.</p> <p>However, after sometime it was named after San Luis Gonzaga (St. Aloysius Gonzaga) who is the patron saint of the town.</p> <p>It was formerly part of the town of Sta. Ana, but due to its growing economy became a town of its own.</p>	Dase (Weaving Mats Making)			St. Aloysius Gonzaga Feast Day

Table 3.1.3.1. 3 Cultural Table 3

The table above showcases the Kapampangan culture and brief description of Pampanga's municipalities namely: Magalang, Masantol, Mexico, Minalin, Porac, and San Luis.

MUNICIPALITY	DESCRIPTION	ART	CUISINE	FESTIVALS / CELEBRATIONS	RELIGIOUS CELEBRATIONS
San Simon	Formerly known as "Senior Del Pilar" named after its founder Mariano Del Pilar. But was later changed to "San Simon" named after the apostle St. Simon. It is a town of Pampanga that is divided into 2 parts: Agricultural Zone and Industrial Zone. Earning the title "The Emerging Business Haven of Central Luzon" due to the existence of different industrial establishment in the area.	Dase (Weaving Mats Making) Metal Craft Pottery Wood Carving			Nuestra Senora del Pilar Feast Day
Santa Ana	Formerly known as "Bale Pinpin" which means to lay aside. But was later on changed to "Santa Ana" named after the patron St. Anne. It is a town in Pampanga that is mainly a farm town specifically its 4 barangays namely: San Agustin, Sto. Rosario, San Roque and San Pablo.			Majjanggal Festival	Saint Anne Feast Day
Santa Rita	The town is locally called "Gasac" or "Sta. Rita De Lele" due to its proximity to Porac and Bacolor. But was formally named after "Sta. Rita de Casia" the town's patron saint. It is famous for its delicacies namely the Turrone De Kasuy and Sans rival.		Turrone De Kasuy Sans rival Araru (Arrowroot Biscuits) Bangka Bangka (Boat Tart) Batya Batya (Round Tart) Duman (Green Rice with Carabao Milk)	Duman Festival	Santa Rita of Cascia Feast Day
Santo Tomas	It is also called "Baliwag" which means tardy. But its name was derived from St. Thomas the apostle the town's patron saint. Also known as the "Casket Capital of Central Luzon" due to its industry of producing coffins.	Kuran among Pasu (Clay Pots and Vases) Coffins Textile			St. Thomas the Apostle Feast Day
Sasmuan	It is formerly called "Sexmoan" but was later called "Sasmuan" which came from the Kapampangan word "sasa" a type of bamboo that is abundant in the town and "pitabmuan" which means meeting place.		Bobotu Pulburun Turrone de Pili (Marzipan) Ningnang Bangus Sasmuan		Kuraldal Festival St. Lucy, Martyr of Syracuse Feast Day

Table 3.1.3.1. 4 Cultural Table 4

The table above showcases the Kapampangan culture and brief description of Pampanga's municipalities namely: San Simon, Santa Ana, Santa Rita, Santo Tomas and Sasmuan.

January	February	March
<p>Aguman Sanduk/ Minalin – Jan 1</p> <p>Kuraldal/ Sasmuan – Jan 6-10</p> <p>Ding labas larawan king Masantol/ Masantol – Every Week of January “Sunday”</p>	<p>Ibon-Ebon Festival/ Candaba – February 1-2</p> <p>Nuestra Señora de la Divia Gracia Feast Day / Mabalacat City – February 2</p> <p>Caragan Festival/ Mabalacat City – February 28-29</p>	
April	May	June
<p>San Pedro Cutud Lenten Rites (Mal a Aldo) / City of San Fernando</p> <p>Tabang Talangka Festival/ San Roque, Bebe Anac Masantol – every 3rd or 4th Sunday of April</p>	<p>Sabat/Santacruzán</p> <p>El Circulo Fernandino – First week of May</p> <p>Pinukupukan Festival/ Floridablanca – May 1</p> <p>St. Joseph the worker Feast Day / Floridablanca – May 1</p> <p>Saint Monica Feast Day / Minalin – Second Sunday of May</p> <p>Saint Monica Feast Day / Mexico – May 4</p> <p>St. Rita of Cascia Feast Day / Santa Rita -May 22</p> <p>San Fernando Day – May 30</p>	<p>Mt. Pinatubo Day (Aldo ning Bunduc Pinatubo)– June 15</p> <p>St. Aloysius Gonzaga Feast Day / San Luis – June 21</p> <p>Apung Iru Fluvial Procession/ Apalit – June 28–30</p> <p>St. Peter the Apostle Feast Day / Apalit – June 28,29 and 30</p>
July	August	September
<p>Saint Anne Feast Day / Santa Ana – July 26</p>	<p>St. Dominic De Guzman Feast Day / Santo Domingo – August 8</p> <p>Batalla Festival (Batallya) / San Roque de Montpelier, Bebe Anac Masantol – August 15-17</p> <p>St. Bartholomew the Apostle / Magalang – August 24</p> <p>Apung Monica Fluvial Procession / Minalin – August 27</p> <p>St. Augustine of Hippo Feast Day / Lubao – August 28</p>	<p>Sanikulas Festival / Mexico, Pampanga – September 10</p> <p>St. Nicholas of Tolentine Feast Day / Macabebe – September 10</p>
October	November	December
<p>Pyestang Tugak (Frog Festival) / City of San Fernando</p> <p>Fiestang Kuliát-Twin Fiesta (La Naval de Angeles and Apung Mamacalulu) / Angeles City</p> <p>Tigtigan Terakan Keng Dalan / Angeles City – Last Friday and Saturday of October</p> <p>Nuestra Señora del Santísimo Rosario de La Naval de Angeles Feast Day / Angeles City – Second Sunday of October</p> <p>Nuestra Señora del Pilar Feast Day / San Simon – October 12</p>	<p>Makatapak Festival/ Bacolor</p> <p>Binulo Festival/ Porac</p> <p>Duman Festival/ Sta. Rita – Last week of November</p> <p>St. Catherine of Alexandria Feast Day / Lubao and Porac – November 25</p> <p>St. Andrew the Apostle Feast Day / Candaba – November 30</p>	<p>Sisig Festival (Sadsaran Qng Angeles) / SM Clark, Angeles City</p> <p>Sinukwan Festival / City of San Fernando – December 1–7</p> <p>La Purisima Concepcion Feast Day / Guagua – December 8</p> <p>Sukit Festival / Floridablanca – December 9</p> <p>Aldo Ning Kapampangan (Pampanga Day) – December 11</p> <p>Saint Lucy, Martyr of Syracuse Feast Day / Sasmuan – December 13</p> <p>Batala Apu Lucia / Santa Lucia Masantol – December 13</p> <p>Lubenas, various towns in Northern Pampanga – December 16–24</p> <p>St. Thomas the Apostle Feast Day / Santo Tomas – December 21</p> <p>Ligligan Parul (Giant Lantern Festival) / City of San Fernando- Saturday before Christmas Eve</p>

Table 3.1.3.1. 5 Pampanga’s Cultural Calendar

The table above showcases the cultural calendar of Pampanga’s cultural celebrations and religious festivals.

Kapampangan Music

According to the Center for Kapampangan Studies (2024), throughout the 300 years that the Philippines was colonized by the Spaniards, the Kapampangan language was never used for singing especially during church celebrations; thus, the Kapampangans expressed their musicality by composing their own alternative songs and melodies for Latin and Spanish hymns and by writing their own version of the bible. This led to the formation of Kapampangan folk music.

FORM	DESCRIPTION
Pantatanam	It is a song that is sung by the Kapampangan during the long hours of planting rice in the open field.
Tumalia	It is a Kapampangan lullaby that is sung by mothers to put their baby to sleep. It is also sometimes sung by men during courtship.
Gosu	It is a Kapampangan song dedicated to a saint, that is sung during feast days and on the eve of All Saints Day. On the eve of October 31 st (Kapampangan Halloween) a band of carolers go from house to house to sing and expect to be rewarded for their performance; when they are not, one of them steals a chicken from the ungrateful household (Kapampangan version of trick-or-treat).
Kantang Ukbu	It is a Kapampangan song from the underground, protest songs or patriotic songs. It was originally sung by members of the Huk Guerilla movement during the World War II.
Basulto	It is a generic term for the Kapampangan songs that follow a certain beat or tempo. It can be a love song, a humorous song or a song with a vulgar content.
Polosa	It is a unique Kapampangan style of singing in which a singer incorporates details about his/her listeners looks or background and the general environment and extemporaneously includes them in the song's lyrics. This style is usually sung during birthday parties, political rallies, beauty contests, bulak lakan (poetic jousts during a wake) and as intermission numbers during a crissotan (public debate in verse form).
Arana (Serenade)	It is sung by men or groups of men with a guitar to woo or court a girl. This is usually done at night either in the front house or in the living room of the girl being courted and while the arana is being done the girl's mother would show hospitality by preparing a quick meal for the guests usually lelut manuk (chicken rice porridge).

Table 3.1.3.1. 6 Traditional Forms of Kapampangan Folk Music

The table above showcases the well-known traditional forms of Kapampangan folk music namely: Pantatanam, Tumalia, Gosu, Kantang Ukbu, Basulto, Polosa, and Arana.

Kapampangan Literature

According to the Center for Kapampangan Studies (2024), Pampanga is more than a culinary capital of the Philippines, but is also home to a land of poets and playwrights.

KAPAMPANGAN WRITERS / POETS	MUNICIPALITY	DESCRIPTION
Juan Crisostomo Soto	Bacolor	Wrote more than 50 plays, 20 zarzuelas, more than 100 poems, essays, short stories, and novels. "Alang Dios" a Kapampangan zarzuela and his novel "Lidia" was one of his best known works. Moreover, the Kapampangan balagtasán called "Crisotan" was named after him. He is known as the "Father of Kapampangan Literature."
Padre Anselmo Jorge Fajardo	Bacolor	He wrote "Heroica de la Conquista de Granada o Sea Vida de Don Gonzalo de Cordoba" which is considered to be the longest literary work in Philippine literature. It is a Kapampangan comedy with three volumes, 832 pages, and 31,000 lines. It premiered in Bacolor, Pampanga in the year February, 1831 and lasted for seven nights.
Luisa Gonzaga de Leon	Bacolor	She is the first Kapampangan female author. She translated the book "Ejercicio Cotidiano" (Daily Devotion) into Kapampangan and was published one year after her death on June 1, 1843.
Mariano Proceso Pabalan Byron	Bacolor	He wrote "Ing Managpe" the first non-Spanish zarzuela in the Philippines and was first staged in the year 1900.
Aurelio Tolentino	Guagua	Guagua's biggest literary star who wrote not only in Kapampangan but also in Tagalog and Spanish. One of his masterpiece is a poem entitled "Ngeni, Napun, at Bukas" (1913).
Monico Mercado	Sasmuan	He wrote the first Kapampangan translation of Mi Ultimo Adios only days after witnessing the execution of his cousin Jose Rizal. His best-known work is entitled "Quetang Milabas" a verse novel.
Zoilo Galang	Bacolor	He is the first Filipino to write an English novel, which was entitled "A Child of Sorrow", and was even made into a movie in the year 1930. One of his greatest work was the 10-volume Encyclopedia of the Philippines.
Zoilo Hilario		His work "Bayung Sunis" (1962) revolutionized Kapampangan orthography replacing c and q with k.
Amado Yuzon		Is honored as the Philippines' Most Outstanding Man of Letters in 1962.

Table 3.1.3.1. 7 Kapampangan Poets and Playwrights

The table above showcases some of best and well-known Kapampangan writers, poets, and playwrights, and their literary works.

3.1.3.2 TOURISM PATTERNS OF PAMPANGA

A. Tourism Patterns of Pampanga (2019 – 2021)

Presented below are the tourist statistics of Pampanga from the year 2019 – 2021. The data gathered were provided by the Arts, Culture, and Tourism Office of Pampanga (ACTOP) (2024) and were solely used for educational purposes.

PROVINCES										
YEAR	Aurora	Bataan	Bulacan	Nueva Ecija	Pampanga	Tarlac	Zambales	Clark	Subic	TOTAL
2019	273,906	397,849	149,171	316,730	259,575	108,706	850,240	721,571	1,008,646	4,086,394
2020	41,944	17,333	113,951	68,387	89,700	45,175	72,411	582,902	286,924	1,318,727
2021	42,783	101,754	133,788	98,003	188,901	38,142	112,369	640,353	704,871	2,060,964

Table 3.1.3.2. a.1 Region III Tourist Arrivals 2019-2021

The table above showcases the tourist arrivals of Region III in the year 2019 to 2021.

PAMPANGA TOURIST ARRIVALS					
2019		2020		2021	
259,575		89,700		98,003	
Average Tourist Arrivals Per Month	21,632	Average Tourist Arrivals Per Month	7475	Average Tourist Arrivals Per Month	8167
Average Tourist Arrivals Per Day	712	Average Tourist Arrivals Per Day	246	Average Tourist Arrivals Per Day	269

Table 3.1.3.2. a.2 Pampanga Tourist Arrivals 2019-2021

The table above showcases the tourist arrivals of Pampanga in the year 2019 to 2021 and the average tourist arrivals per year, month, and day.

B. Tourism Patterns of San Fernando City (2021 – 2023)

Presented below are the tourist statistics of San Fernando City from the year 2021 – 2023. The data gathered were provided by the City Tourism Office of San Fernando City (2024) and were solely used for educational purposes.

Tourist Statistics of San Fernando City Year 2021

TOURIST DESTINATIONS- DAY VISITORS													
NAME	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL
Attraction 1	186	128	261	44	0	0	0	37	85	95	105	0	941
Attraction 2	100	32	23	0	40	54	43	0	0	0	0	0	292
Attraction 3	2050	3130	1600	0	0	0	275	0	0	0	200	226	7481
Attraction 4	7204	2610	1855	0	0	20	0	15	18	27	0	0	11749
Attraction 5						0	5849	845	2025	5915	8610	62560	85804
TOTAL													106267

Table 3.1.3.2. b.1 SF Tourist Destinations 2021

DAY VISITORS- HOTELS													
DAILY VISITS (LOCAL)	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL
H1													
H2													
H3													
H4													
H5	20	12	21	16	17	25	45	19	32	27	31		
H6	2197	2098	2098	2228	2139	2072	1796	1254	1577	2315	2120		
H7													
H8													
H9													
H10													
H11													
H12													
H13													
H14													
H15													
H16													
H17			91	76	81	88	92	152	86	91	102		
H18													
H19			6	7	13	22							
TOTAL													23066

Table 3.1.3.2. b.2 SF Hotels 2021

DAY VISITORS- RESORTS													
DAILY ARRIVALS (LOCAL)	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL
R1					36	61							
R2													
R3													
R4													
R5				7	22	57	45	37	66	73	97		
R6		6		8	34	52	16	14	54	38	58		
R7													
R8													
R9													
R10													
R11						4	6	7					
R12													
R13													
R14													
TOTAL													798

Table 3.1.3.2. b.3 SF Resorts 2021

DAY VISITORS- MICE													
DAILY ARRIVALS (LOCAL)	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	
M1	692	276	300	0	105	510	251	145	280	710	680	525	
M2	30	38	40	0			30	0				0	
M3	400	0	0	0			50	0	302	300	1150	1200	
M4	60	148	174	0	15	122	170	0				430	
M5	130	0	150				250	170	90	215	150	485	
M6	185	107	66	100	17	120	99	90	110	135	302	249	
M7	50	0	68			50	0	0			130	140	
M8	80	350	100	230	70		679	250	200	483	240	360	
M9	40	0	30				0	0				0	
M10	226	0	294			60	52	30				0	
M11	535	100	400	850	205	1320	360	0	150		780	1934	
M12	132	50	0				0	0				0	
M13				320		120	250	380	225			680	
M14				150			0	0	90	270	450	670	
M15											30	68	
M16				149			120	60	Jun-00	170	140	1329	
	2560	1069	1622	1799	412	2302	2311	1125	1627	2283	4052	8070	29232

Table 3.1.3.2. b.4 SF MICE 2021

Tourist Statistics of San Fernando City Year 2022

TOURIST DESTINATIONS- DAY VISITORS														
NAME	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	TOTAL	
Attraction 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					0	
Attraction 2	1340	270	0	1724	0	2171	2171	0					7676	
Attraction 3	201	218	51	26	59	306	306	0			28		1195	
Attraction 4	0	55	25	43	63	20	20	25					251	
Attraction 5	49245	24291	59686	44640	30592	38862	38862	22861	17735	20489	20442		367705	
Attraction 6				15000					108084				123084	
Attraction 7				520000									520000	
Attraction 8					259	155	155	307	216	4829	1546		7467	
Attraction 9								38	42				80	
													TOTAL	1027458

Table 3.1.3.2. b.5 SF Tourist Destinations 2022

DAY VISITORS- HOTELS													
DAILY VISITS (LOCAL)	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	
H1													
H2													
H3													
H4													
H5	34	18	19	57			26	27	26	23	20	21	
H6	1845	1695	1397	1697	1278	1309	1269	1206	1106	1222	989	1178	
H7													
H8				83	1478	1755	1685	1692	1668	1911	1964	2185	
H9													
H10			30	62	37	35	55	68	38	81	138	174	
H11													
H12													
H13													
H14						29	145	163	147	152	145	151	
H15						35	150	154	149	157	149	156	
H16										6			
H17			139	211	90	133	141	202	160	136	150	192	
H19													
	1879	1713	1585	2118	2885	3296	3471	3514	3294	3688	3555	4057	35055
DAILY VISITS (FOREIGN)	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	
H18						2							
						2							2

Table 3.1.3.2. b.6 SF Hotels 2022

DAY VISITORS- RESORTS												
DAILY ARRIVALS (LOCAL)	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
R1	66	84	97	154								
R2	60	58	503	438	556							
R3												
R4	5	33	60	56	57	28	39	36	19	12	33	16
R5	120	236	352	422	621							
R6	54	32	69	92	134	0	0	0	0	12	0	0
R7												
R8												
R9												
R10												
R11												
R12												
R13												
R14			97	316	127	76	62		34	66	63	161
	234	326	1178	1478	1495	104	101	36	53	90	96	177

Table 3.1.3.2. b.7 SF Resorts 2022

DAY VISITORS- MICE												
DAILY ARRIVALS (LOCAL)	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
M1	150		100					620				
M2						120						
M3			2500		800	1800	2500	1200	500	2575	2800	1500
M4	100		346	240	290	411	510	987	832		1728	1577
M5			20						490			
M6	170	80	177	198	255	186	280	500	544	295		
M7												
M8	70								150			
M9												
M10			391	898	704	1095	1199	1438	945	841		
M11	300	1620	425	2041	2270	1180	3618	650	1950	1100	3930	6820
M12												
M13	210	200	300	550	650	810	185	300				
M14	270		940	920			400	1550	800	1420	2050	1100
M15	60											
M16	161	151	276	1018	1175	345	660	590	600	700	700	1270
M17				15000								
M18				520000								
M19					700							
M20						29						
M21						150						
M22							120					
M23							40	145				
M24									500			
	1491	2051	5475	540865	6844	6126	9512	7980	7311	6931	11208	12267

Table 3.1.3.2. b.8 SF MICE 2022

Tourist Statistics of San Fernando City Year 2023

	Tourist Attractions	MICE	Resorts	Hotels	TOTAL
JAN	58784	10317	96	4143	73340
FEB	74056	19140	83	3675	96954
MAR	83676	17188	160	3953	104977
APR	90648	16634	302	3721	111305
MAY	120980	29578	129	3996	154683
JUN	119252	27051	61	3845	150209
JUL	149818	16109	34	3863	169824
AUG	0	12355	275	5254	17884
SEP	0	16689	134	3873	20696
OCT	0	18090	284	4029	22403
NOV	0	18799	283	3627	22709
DEC	0	31697	1366	4079	37142
TOTAL	697214	233647	3207	48058	982126

Table 3.1.3.2. b.9 SF Tourist Statistics 2023

SAN FERNANDO TOURIST ARRIVALS					
2021		2022		2023	
Tourist Destinations	106,276	Tourist Destinations	1,027,458	Tourist Destinations	697,214
Hotels	23,066	Hotels	35,057	Hotels	233,647
Resorts	798	Resorts	5,368	Resorts	3,207
MICE	29,232	MICE	61,806	MICE	48,058
TOTAL	159,372	TOTAL	1,685,944	TOTAL	982,126
Average Tourists Arrival Per Month	13,281	Average Tourists Arrival Per Month	140,496	Average Tourists Arrival Per Month	81,844
Average Tourists Arrival Per Day	437	Average Tourists Arrival Per Day	4,620	Average Tourists Arrival Per Day	2,691

Table 3.1.3.2. b.10 San Fernando City Tourist Arrivals 2021-2023

The table above showcases the tourist arrivals of San Fernando City in the year 2021 to 2023 and the average tourist arrivals per year, month, and day.

3.1.4 APPLICABLE BUILDING LAWS FOR THE PROJECT

3.1.4.1 PD 1096 – NATIONAL BUILDING CODE OF THE PHILIPPINES

Rule VII: Classification and General Requirements of All Buildings by Use or Occupancy

Classification of Use/Character of Occupancy of Building Structure	Type of Building / Principal Use	Accessory	Zoning Classification
<p>Group I – Occupant Load 1,000 or More (Cultural and/or Recreational)</p> <p>Division I-1 (Recreational assembly buildings with stage and an occupant load of 1,000 or more in the building)</p>	<p>Theater</p> <p>Convention Center</p> <p>Museum</p>	<p>Parks/Garden</p> <p>Monuments and other park structures</p>	<p>CUL (Cultural) – a community to national level of cultural use or occupancy, characterized mainly as low-rise or medium-rise building/structure for cultural activities</p> <p>PRE (Park Structures, Recreation and Entertainment) – a range of recreational uses or occupancies, characterized mainly as a low-rise or medium-rise building/structure for low to medium intensity recreational or entertainment functions related to educational uses, e.g., structures on campuses or its component parks/open spaces and all other kinds of recreational or assembly building/structures on campus such as auditoria, mess halls, seminar facilities, gymnasias, stadia, arenas, and the like.</p>

Table 3.1.4.1. 1 Classification of Use/Occupancy of Building

Determination of Building Height Limit (BHL)

BHL excludes the height of permitted/allowed projections above the roof of the building/structure, e.g., signage, antenna, telecom tower, beacons and the like.

Character of Use or Occupancy	Type of Building/Structure	No. of allowable storeys/floors above established grade	Meters above highest grade
Cultural		30 meters (or must follow the duly-approved BHL in the major zone it is part of)	
Parks and Open Recreational and Entertainment Spaces		15 meters (or must follow the duly-approved BHL in the major zone it is part of)	

Table 3.1.4.1. 2 Building Height Limit (BHL)

Parking Requirements

Type of Vehicle		Standard Parking Slot, Area, Loading/Unloading Space
Average Car	Parallel	2.15 m x 6.00 m
	Diagonal / Perpendicular	2.5 m x 5.00 m
Truck or Bus		3.6 m x 12.00 m
Articulated Truck		3.6 m x 18.00 m
Jeepney or Shuttle		3.00 m x 9.00 m

Table 3.1.4.1. 3 Standard Parking Slot Dimensions

Building	Specific Uses or of Occupancy	Reference Uses or Character of Occupancies or Type of Buildings/Structures	Minimum Required Parking Slot, Area, and Loading Space Requirements
Museum Theater Convention Center	Group I Division I-1	Recreational or similar public assembly buildings such as stadia, sports complexes, convention centers, etc.	One (1) car slot and one (1) jeepney/shuttle slot for every 50.00 sq. mts. of spectator area; and one (1) bus parking slot for every two hundred (200) spectators.

Table 3.1.4.1. 4 Minimum Parking Slot Requirements

Rule VIII: Light and Ventilation

Type of Lot of the Project

Figure 3.1.4.1. 1 Type of Lot

Setbacks for the Project

RROW (Road Right of Way)	Front (Meters)	Sides (Meters)	Rear (Meters)
30.00 Meters & Above	8.00	5.00	5.00

Table 3.1.4.1. 5 Setbacks Requirement

Ceiling Heights Required for the Project

Floor Level	Artificially Ventilated	Naturally Ventilated
Ground Floor	2.70m	2.70m
Second Floor	2.4m	2.70m
Succeeding Floors	2.1m	2.70m
Mezzanines	1.8m	2.70m

Table 3.1.4.1. 6 Ceiling Height Requirements

Minimum TOSL Requirements by Lot Type

Inside Lot otherwise referred to as a Regular Lot (Non – corner or single frontage lot)

30% minimum percentage of open space for proposed developments without firewalls or abutments.

3.1.4.2 BP 344 – ACCESSIBILITY LAW (2024)

Ramps		
	Maximum	Preferred
Total Ramp Rise	1000 mm	1000 mm
Ramp Gradient	1:15	1:20
Total Ramp Run	15.00 m	20.00 m
Intermediate Landings	1800 mm	1800 mm
Landings Before & After	2 x 1800 mm	2 x 1800 mm
Overall Ramp Length	20.40 m	25.40 m

Table 3.1.4.2. 1 Ramp

Figure 3.1.4.2. 1 Ramp

Figure 3.1.4.2. 2 Handrail

Accessible Parking Slot Requirement	
Total Number of Parking Slot	Required Number of Accessible Parking Slot
1 – 25	1
26 – 50	2
51 – 75	3
76 – 100	4
101 – 150	5
151 – 200	6
201 – 300	7
301 – 400	8
401 – 500	9
501 – 1000	2% of Total Parking Spaces
1001 – over	20+ (1 For Each 100 or a Fraction Thereof Over 1000)

Table 3.1.4.2. 2 Accessible Parking Slot Requirement

Fig. A.6.1: Plan of Accessible Parking Slot

Figure 3.1.4.2. 3 Plan of Accessible Parking Slot

Doors	
Minimum Width of Single Leaf Door	900 mm
Minimum Width of Double Leaf Door	1800 mm
Elevators	
Inside dimensions of car	1200 mm wide x 1400 mm deep
Maximum travel distance from building entrance	30.00 m
Stairs	
Minimum Tread	300 mm
Maximum Riser	150 mm
Standard nosing preferred over protruding nosing	

Table 3.1.4.2. 3 Door, Elevators & Stairs

Figure 3.1.4.2. 4 Stairs

Figure 3.1.4.2. 5 Turnabout Spaces at Corridors

Wheelchair Seating Requirement for Assembly Halls, Theater, Auditorium and related Facilities	
Seating Capacity	Wheelchair Seating Space
4 – 50	2
51 – 300	4
301 – 500	6
500 – over	Additional 1 seating for every 100 seats

Table 3.1.4.2. 4 Wheelchair Seating Requirement

3.1.4.3 RA 9514 – FIRE CODE OF THE PHILIPPINES

Doors	
Minimum Height of Door	2.00 m
Minimum Width of Door	710 mm
Maximum Width of Door	1220 mm
Exits	
Number of exits required (based on occupant load)	0 – 500 Occupant Load: 2 Exits 501 – 999 Occupant Load: 3 Exits 1000 or more Occupant Load: 4 Exits
Minimum Width of Exit Door	915 mm
Change in Floor Level at Doors	13 mm
Maximum Length of Dead Ends	6.00 m
Travel Distance to Exit with Sprinkler	61 m
Travel Distance to Exit without Sprinkler	46 m
Elevators	
Provide at least one exit per elevator lobby.	
Fire Exit Stairs	
Minimum Width	600 mm clear between rails
Minimum Horizontal Dimension any landing of platform	600 mm
Maximum Rise	230 mm
Minimum Tread, exclusive of nosing	230 mm
Tread Construction	Solid, 13.00 m diameter perforation permitted
Winders (Spiral)	None
Risers	None
Maximum Height between landings	3.66 m
Minimum Headroom	2.00 m
Access to Escape	Door or Casement Windows 610 mm by 1.98 m or double hung windows 762 mm by 914.40 mm clear
Level of Access Opening	Not Over 305 mm above floor; steps if higher
Discharge to Ground	Swinging stair section permitted
Capacity Number of Persons	45 per unit access by door; 20 if access by climbing over window rail

Table 3.1.4.3. 1 Fire Code of the Philippines

3.1.4.4 RA 1378 – NATIONAL PLUMBING CODE OF THE PHILIPPINES

Minimum Plumbing Facilities		
Type of Building or Occupancy Assembly Places: Theaters, Auditoriums, Convention Halls, etc. – for Public Use	Water Closets (Fixtures per Person)	
	Male	Female
	1 : 1-100 2 : 101-200 3 : 201-400	3 : 1-50 4 : 51-100 8 : 101-200 11 : 201-400
	Over 400, add 1 fixture for each additional 500 males and 2 for each 300 females.	
	Urinals (Fixtures per person)	
	1 : 1-100 2 : 101-200 3 : 201-400 4 : 401-600	
	Over 600, add 1 fixture for each additional 500 males.	
	Lavatories (Fixtures per person)	
	Male	Female
	1 : 1-200 2 : 201-400 3 : 401-750	1 : 1-200 2 : 201-400 3 : 401-750
Over 750, add 1 fixture for each additional 500 persons.		
Type of Building or Occupancy Office or Public Buildings (Museum)	Water Closets (Fixtures per Person)	
	Male	Female
	1 : 1-100 2 : 101-200 3 : 201-400	1 : 1-200 2 : 201-400 3 : 401-750
	Over 55, add 1 fixture for each additional 500 males and 2 for each 55 females.	
	Urinals (Fixtures per person)	
	1 : 1-100 2 : 101-200 3 : 201-400 4 : 401-600	
	Over 600, add 1 fixture for each additional 300 males.	
	Lavatories (Fixtures per person)	
	Male	Female
	1 : 1-200 2 : 201-400 3 : 401-750	1 : 1-200 2 : 201-400 3 : 401-750
Over 750, add 1 fixture for each additional 500 persons.		

Table 3.1.4.4. 1 Minimum Plumbing Facilities

Horizontal drainage pipes shall be run in practical alignments and at a uniform slope between manholes of not less than **20mm/m or 2%** toward the point of disposal, provided that, where it is impracticable to obtain a 2% slope due to the following constraints in: (1) excessive depth of the proposed drainage line; (2) structural and/or geological features of the terrain; and (3) existing adverse in arrangements of building or structure; any such pipe or piping 102mm or larger in diameter may have a slope of **10mm/m or 1%** provided it is first approved by the Administrative Authority.

3.1.4.5 ELECTRICAL CODE OF THE PHILIPPINES

General Lighting Loads by Occupancy	
Type of Building or Occupancy	Unit Load per Square Meter (Volt-Amperes)
Office Building	39
Restaurants	22
Stores	33
Assembly Halls and Auditorium	11
Industrial Commercial (loft) Buildings	22
Storage Facilities	3

Table 3.1.4.5. 1 General Lighting Loads by Occupancy

3.1.5 APPLICABLE DESIGN STANDARDS FOR THE PROJECT

- **Time-Saver Standards for Building Types (2nd Edition)** by Joseph De Chiara & John Hancock Callender
- **Planning and Designer's Handbook (2nd Edition)** by Max B. Fajardo Jr.

MOVIE THEATER / AUDITORIUM

Movie Theater
The viewer's angle of sight from the bottom of the screen top should not exceed 33 degrees.
The farthest viewing distance should not be greater than two times the screen width = $2W$.
The width of the seating pattern should vary from W to $1.3W$ at the farthest row from the screen.
For the standard 35mm films, the projected picture width should not exceed 11.00 meters.
For cinemascope 35mm films picture width = 14 meters.
For 70mm film = 20 meters

Table 3.1.5. 1 Movie Theater

Figure 3.1.5 1 Maximum Viewing Distance

Figure 3.1.5. 2 Minimum Distance from Screen to First Row of Seat

Figure 3.1.5. 3 Sight Clearances

Figure 3.1.5. 4 Single Slope Auditorium Non-Staggered Seats

Figure 3.1.5. 5 Seating Dimensions

Figure 3.1.5. 6 Seating for Disabled Persons

Screen and Projection Angle	
Projected angle from the horizontal line of the projector lens to the screen should be 10 degrees or less to have the least distortion of the picture details.	
The screen is provided with curvature to attain better dispersal of screen lighting. The curvature radius of the screen is about 1.25 times the projection distance .	
Projection Room Area Requirements	
First Projection Machine	5.0 meters
Each Additional Projector	2.5 meters

Table 3.1.5. 2 Screen and Projection Angle

Figure 3.1.5. 7 Plan of the Projection Room

Lighting
The cinema auditorium lighting has three functions:
Lighting during intermission.
Emergency exit and mood lighting used during screen presentations.
Full intensity lighting for making announcement clearing of the house or other special occasions.
Sources of these lights from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflected from the screen. • Wall and ceiling surface lighting. • Light projected on walls or concealed pictures.

Table 3.1.5. 3 Lighting

COMMUNITY LIBRARY

Figure 3.1.5. 8 Minimum Clearances for Various Positions in Library Stack Areas

Figure 3.1.5. 9 Comfortable Book Shelving (Adults & Children)

3.2 ARCHITECTURAL PROGRAMMING

3.2.1 DESIGN/SPACE REQUIREMENTS

A. KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM GROUND FLOOR

MAIN BUILDING

RECEPTION LOBBY AREA

- PORCH
- INFORMATION DESK

HISTORY EXHIBIT

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- MACHINE ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- ELECTRICAL & UTILITY ROOM
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

SOUVENIR SHOP

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- MACHINE ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- ELECTRICAL & UTILITY ROOM
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

RIGHT ANCILLARY BUILDING

MANAGEMENT OFFICE LOBBY AREA

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- MACHINE ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- MAIN STAIRCASE

MANAGEMENT OFFICE

- ELECTRICAL & UTILITY ROOM
- RESTORATION ROOM
- CURATOR'S OFFICE
- ADMIN'S OFFICE

LIBRARY

- LOBBY AREA
- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- CIRCULATION AREA
- LIBRARIAN'S OFFICE
- STORAGE ROOM
- COMPUTER SECTION ROOM
- READING AREA
- 2 MEETING ROOMS

LEFT ANCILLARY BUILDING

STORAGE ROOM FLOOR AREA

- 14 STORAGE ROOMS
- 2 MACHINE ROOMS
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM SECOND FLOOR

MAIN BUILDING

CULINARY EXHIBIT

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

TEMPORARY EXHIBIT

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

RIGHT ANCILLARY BUILDING

FESTIVAL/RELIGIOUS EXHIBIT

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR
- STORAGE ROOM
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

LEFT ANCILLARY BUILDING

ART EXHIBIT

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- STORAGE ROOM
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM THIRD FLOOR

MAIN BUILDING

FULL DOME CINEMA

- FULL DOME
- LED SCREEN MAINTENANCE AREA

WORKSHOP EXHIBIT (LEFT)

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

WORKSHOP EXHIBIT (RIGHT)

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

RIGHT ANCILLARY BUILDING

MUSIC / DANCE EXHIBIT

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

LEFT ANCILLARY BUILDING

LITERARY EXHIBIT

- MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
- HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR
- MAIN STAIRCASE
- FIRE EXIT

B. KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER GROUND FLOOR

ENTRY AND EXIT VESTIBULE

2 GRAND HALLS

PRIVATE LOUNGE ROOM

- PWD RESTROOM

VIP LOUNGE ROOM

- PWD RESTROOM

LACTATION ROOM W/ TOILET

SECURITY ROOM W/ TOILET

4 SETS OF UTILITY CORE

- UTILITY ROOM
- ELECTRICAL ROOM
- AHU ROOM

2 SETS GARBAGE CHUTES

2 SETS OF MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM W/ PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM

2 HYDRAULIC PASSENGER ELEVATOR W/ MACHINE ROOM

HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR W/ MACHINE ROOM

2 SETS ESCALATOR

4 FIRE EXITS

4 SETS KITCHEN

- GAS STORAGE
- COLD STORAGE
- DRY STORAGE
- PANTRY
- DUMBWAITER

6 STORAGE ROOMS

DELIVERY DOCK

ADMIN MANAGEMENT OFFICE

ADMIN LOUNGE ROOM W/ T&B

EMPLOYEE MALE/FEMALE RESTROOM W/ PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM

GRAND STAIRCASE

PRIVATE STAIRCASE

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER SECOND FLOOR

LOBBY AREA

4 RENTABLE STALLS

6 FUNCTION HALLS

LACTATION ROOM W/ TOILET

SECURITY ROOM W/ TOILET

4 SETS OF UTILITY CORE

- UTILITY ROOM
- ELECTRICAL ROOM
- AHU ROOM

2 SETS GARBAGE CHUTE

2 SETS OF MALE, FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM W/ PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM

2 HYDRAULIC PASSENGER ELEVATOR W/ STORAGE ROOM

HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR W/ STORAGE ROOM

1 SET ESCALATOR

4 FIRE EXIT STAIRCASES

4 SETS KITCHEN

- GAS STORAGE
- COLD STORAGE
- DRY STORAGE
- PANTRY
- DUMBWAITER

6 STORAGE ROOMS

STAFF OFFICE

STAFF LOUNGE ROOM W/ T&B
EMPLOYEE MALE/FEMALE RESTROOM
W/ PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
GRAND STAIRCASE
PRIVATE STAIRCASE

**KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL
CONVENTION CENTER THIRD FLOOR**

6 RENTABLE STALLS
6-12 MEETING ROOMS
GALLERY DISPLAY AREA
CAFÉ KITCHEN

- GAS STORAGE
- COLD STORAGE
- DRY STORAGE
- PANTRY
- DUMBWAITER

LACTATION ROOM W/ TOILET
4 SETS OF UTILITY CORE

- UTILITY ROOM
- ELECTRICAL ROOM
- AHU ROOM

2 SETS GARBAGE CHUTE
1 SET OF MALE, FEMALE AND PWD
RESTROOM W/ PIPE CHASE & UTILITY
ROOM
HYDRAULIC PASSENGER ELEVATOR
W/ STORAGE ROOM
HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR W/
STORAGE ROOM
1 SET ESCALATOR
4 FIRE EXIT STAIRCASES

STAFF OFFICE
STAFF LOUNGE ROOM W/ T&B
EMPLOYEE MALE/FEMALE RESTROOM
W/ PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM
PRIVATE STAIRCASE
GRAND STAIRCASE
LED DISPLAY MAINTENANCE AREA

AUDITORIUM

- AUDITORIUM LOBBY
- TICKET BOOTH
- CONCESSION STAND
- STORAGE ROOM
- MALE & FEMALE & PWD
RESTROOM
- ENTRY & EXIT FOYERS
- ELEVATED STAIRED SEATING
AREA
- STAGE
- BACKSTAGE / PREPARATION
AREA
- 2 TECHNICAL ROOMS
- 2 STORAGE ROOMS
- MALE DRESSING ROOM
- FEMALE DRESSING ROOM

**KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL
CONVENTION CENTER ROOF DECK
PLAN**

ROOF DECK AREA

- HELIPAD
- SERVICE MAINTENANCE
STAIRCASE
- SPACE FOR COOLING TOWERS

C. KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER GROUND FLOOR PLAN

FRONT PORCH

RECEPTION LOBBY AREA

TICKET BOOTH

STAFF OFFICE & LOUNGE ROOM

WAITING AREA (LEFT)

- MALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- ENTRY FOYER GOING TO THEATER SEATS
- MALE RESTROOM W/ UTILITY ROOM AND PIPE CHASE

WAITING AREA (RIGHT)

- FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM
- ENTRY FOYER GOING TO THEATER SEATS
- FEMALE REST ROOM W/ UTILITY ROOM AND PIPE CHASE

760 PAX ELEVATED STAIRED SEATING AREA

- HYDRAULIC PASSENGER ELEVATOR W/ MACHINE ROOM
- 2 EXIT FOYERS
- SECURITY ROOM
- 2 STORAGE ROOM
- 2 AHU ROOM
- FIRST AID CLINIC
- 2 GRAND STAIRCASES

THRUST STAGE AREA

BACK STAGE AREA

- PREPARATION AREA
- PRODUCTION CREW OFFICE
- MANAGEMENT OFFICE
- TECHNICAL SUPPORT OFFICE
- TECHNICAL STORAGE ROOM
- 2 PROPS STORAGE ROOM
- 2 GREEN ROOMS WITH T&B
- MALE AND FEMALE DRESSING ROOM
- MALE AND FEMALE RESTROOMS W/ PIPE CHASE & UTILITY ROOM

- PRIVATE ACCESS STAIRCASE
- 2 FIRE EXITS

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER SECOND FLOOR PLAN

DISPLAY AREA

- 2 SETS CONCESSION STANDS
- LED SCREEN MAINTENANCE AREA

MALE AND PWD RESTROOM

ENTRY FOYER GOING TO THEATER SEATS

MALE REST ROOM W/ UTILITY AND PIPE CHASE

FEMALE AND PWD RESTROOM

ENTRY FOYER GOING TO THEATER SEATS

FEMALE REST ROOM W/ UTILITY AND PIPE CHASE

CONTROL ROOM

LIGHT AND SOUNDS ROOM

440 PAX ELEVATED STAIRED SECOND FLOOR SEATING AREA

- BALCONY AREA
- 2 STORAGE ROOMS
- 2 FIRE EXIT STAIRCASES
- HYDRAULIC PASSENGER ELEVATOR

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER ROOF DECK PLAN

ROOF DECK PLAN

- SPACE FOR SOLAR PANELS
- SPACE FOR COOLING TOWERS
- SERVICE MAINTENANCE STAIRCASE

D. KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER GROUND FLOOR PLAN

RECEPTION AREA

2 LOUNGE AREA

2 BLACK BOX THEATER

- TECHNICAL ROOM
- STORAGE ROOM

RESTROOMS

- MALE AND PWD RESTROOM
 - FEMALE REST ROOM W/ UTILITY ROOM AND PIPE CHASE
- PRODUCTION OFFICE

UTILITY CORE

- GENERATOR ROOM
- EM ROOM
- UTILITY ROOM
- WATER PUMP MACHINE ROOM
- FIRE PUMP MACHINE ROOM

E. KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK

INDU: OPEN KITCHEN GROUND FLOOR PLAN

6 SETS KITCHEN STALLS

- KITCHENETTE
- ADMIN'S OFFICE
- COLD STORAGE
- DRY STORAGE
- GAS STORAGE
- PANTRY
- T&B
- DINING AREA

RESTROOMS

- MALE RESTROOM
- FEMALE RESTROOM
- PWD RESTROOM

UTILITY CORE

- 2 PIPE CHASE
- EM ROOM
- 2 UTILITY ROOMS
- GENERATOR ROOM

MAIN UTILITY CORE

- MRF ROOM
- STORAGE ROOM

INDU: COMMECRICAL BUILDING GROUND FLOOR PLAN

LOCAL FOOD VENDOR STALLS PLACE

- WATER AND FIRE PUMP MACHINE ROOM

RESTROOMS

- MALE RESTROOM
- FEMALE RESTROOM
- PWD RESTROOM

UTILITY CORE

- 2 PIPE CHASE
- EM ROOM
- 2 UTILITY ROOMS
- GENERATOR ROOM

5 RENTABLE STALLS

- SALES AREA
- WORK / STORAGE ROOM
- ADMIN OFFICE
- KITCHENETTE W/ T&B

2 STAIRCASES

INDU: COMMECRICAL BUILDING SECOND FLOOR PLAN

10 RENTABLE STALLS

- SALES AREA
- WORK / STORAGE ROOM
- ADMIN OFFICE
- KITCHENETTE W/ T&B

RESTROOMS

- MALE RESTROOM
- FEMALE RESTROOM
- PWD RESTROOM

UTILITY CORE

- 2 PIPE CHASE
- EM ROOM
- 2 UTILITY ROOMS
- GENERATOR ROOM

2 STAIRCASES

F. MAIN UTILITY CORE

MAIN UTILITY CORE

- MRF ROOM
- STORAGE ROOM
- GENERATOR ROOM
- UTILITY ROOM
- E.M. ROOM
- WATER PUMP MACHINE ROOM
- FIRE PUMP MACHINE ROOM

G. SITE DEVELOPMENT PLAN

SITE DEVELOPMENT PLAN

- MUSEUM
- CONVENTION CENTER
- THEATER
- BLACK BOX THEATER
- FOOD PARK (COMMERCIAL BUILDING & OPEN KITCHEN)
- MAIN PLAZA
- PARKING AREA
- BUS & JEEPNEY PARKING AREA

3.2.2 SPACE PROGRAMMING

Architectural Space Programming is a systematic process of gathering and analyzing data in order to determine the proper and efficient spatial requirements needed for a specific project.

Space programming was applied by the designer to determine the minimum total gross floor area for each building of the proposed project. It serves as a guide for the designer to determine the minimum sizes and dimensions of each spaces, therefore ensuring the consideration for proper circulation, efficiency and functionality of the building.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM GROUND FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
MAIN BUILDING										
FRONT PORCH	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50					
PATHWAY	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50					
RECEPTION LOBBY AREA	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
HISTORY EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	50	DISPLAY	5	1	250
					50	BENCH	3	1.2	180	
					50	DISPLAY	3	3	450	
SOUVENIR SHOP	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	50	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	18
					10	COUNTER	2	0.8	16	
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	2	4	USERS	0.65	5.2	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	2	3	USERS	0.65	3.9	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	2	1	USER	1.5	3	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
ELECTRICAL ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
PIPE CHASE	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
ELEVATOR MACHINE ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	1	ELEVATOR MACHINE	1	1	1
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	2	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	40					
MAIN STAIRCASE	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
RIGHT ANCILLARY BUILDING										
MANAGEMENT OFFICE										
MANAGEMENT LOBBY	1	30	EMPLOYEE	1	30	5	SOFA BENCH	1.85	0.85	7.8625
						5	COFFEE TABLE	1	1	5
MANAGEMENT OFFICE	1	20	EMPLOYEE	1	20	20	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	7.2
						20	OFFICE TABLE	2	0.6	24
						3	SOFA BENCH	1.85	0.85	4.7175
RESTORATION ROOM	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	2	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.72
						2	OFFICE TABLE	2	0.6	2.4
						10	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
						1	LONG TABLE	5	2	10
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
CURATOR'S OFFICE	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1	1	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.36
						1	OFFICE TABLE	2	0.6	1.2
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
ADMIN OFFICE	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1	1	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.36
						1	OFFICE TABLE	2	0.6	1.2
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	3	USERS	0.65	1.95	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
ELEVATOR MACHINE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	ELEVATOR MACHINE	1	1	1
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
MAIN STAIRCASE	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50					
LIBRARY										
LIBRARIAN OFFICE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	2	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.72
						2	OFFICE TABLE	2	0.6	2.4
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
CIRCULATION AREA	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	8	BOOK SHELVES	5	1.2	48
STORAGE ROOM	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	10	STORAGE RACK	2	1.2	24
COMPUTER SECTION	1	30	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	30	30	COMPUTER TABLE	1.2	0.6	21.6
						30	COMPUTER CHAIR	0.6	0.6	10.8
						20	BOOK SHELVES	5	1.2	120
LIBRARY AREA	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	100	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	36
						50	TABLE	0.8	0.8	32
PORCH	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
MEETING ROOM	2	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20	2	LONG TABLE	5	1.2	12
						10	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	3	USERS	0.65	1.95	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
LEFT ANCILLARY BUILDING										
STORAGE ROOM FLOOR AREA										
STORAGE ROOM	13	5	EMPLOYEE	1	65	26	STORAGE CABINET	3	1.85	144.3
UTILITIES										
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
ELEVATOR MACHINE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
MAIN STAIRCASE	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50					
HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1					
FREIGHT MACHINE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	FREIGHT MACHINE	1	1	1
				TOTAL AREA (USERS)	1062.2				TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)	1491.71
							TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)			2553.91
							TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)			3575.47
							TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)			4767.30
							TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)			4862.64
							TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)			4863.00

Table 3.2.2. 1 SP GFA Museum

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM SECOND FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
MAIN BUILDING										
TEMPORARY EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	30	DISPLAY	5	1	150
						25	BENCH	3	1.2	90
CULINARY EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	30	DISPLAY	5	1	150
						25	BENCH	3	1.2	90
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	2	4	USERS	0.65	5.2	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	2	3	USERS	0.65	3.9	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	2	1	USER	1.5	3	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
ELECTRICAL ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
PIPE CHASE	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	2	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	40					
MAIN STAIRCASE	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
BALCONY	2	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
FIRE EXIT STAIRCASE	2	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
RIGHT ANCILLARY BUILDING										
ART EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	50	DISPLAY	5	1	250
						30	BENCH	3	1.2	108
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	3	USERS	0.65	1.95	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	2	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	40					
MAIN STAIRCASE	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
BALCONY	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
FIRE EXIT STAIRCASE	2	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
LEFT ANCILLARY BUILDING										
FESTIVAL EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	50	DISPLAY	5	1	250
						30	BENCH	3	1.2	108
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	3	USERS	0.65	1.95	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1					
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
MAIN STAIRCASE	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50					
BALCONY	1	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	10					
FIRE EXIT STAIRCASE	2	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
CONNECTING BRIDGE	3	11	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	33					
TOTAL AREA (USERS)					954.2	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)				1241.27
						TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)				2195.47
						TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)				3073.66
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)				4098.21
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)				4180.17
						TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)				4180.00

Table 3.2.2. 2 SP SFA Museum

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM THIRD FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
MAIN BUILDING										
WORKSHOP EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	50	DISPLAY	5	1	250
						20	BENCH	3	1	60
WORKSHOP EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	50	DISPLAY	5	1	250
						20	BENCH	3	1	60
FULL DOME CINEMA	1	79	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	79	79	CINEMA SEAT	0.8	0.8	50.56
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	2	4	USERS	0.65	5.2	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	2	3	USERS	0.65	3.9	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	2	1	USER	1.5	3	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
ELECTRICAL ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
PIPE CHASE	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	2	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	40					
MAIN STAIRCASE	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
LED DISPLAY MAINTENANCE AREA	1	3	EMPLOYEE	1	3					
FIRE EXIT STAIRCASE	2	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
RIGHT ANCILLARY BUILDING										
LITERARY EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	50	DISPLAY	5	1	250
						20	BENCH	3	1	60
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	3	USERS	0.65	1.95	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	2	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	40					
MAIN STAIRCASE	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
BALCONY	1	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	10					
FIRE EXIT STAIRCASE	2	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
LEFT ANCILLARY BUILDING										
MUSIC/DANCE EXHIBIT	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	50	BENCH	5	1	250
						20	DISPLAY	2.46	1.2	59.04
UTILITIES										
MALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						2	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.48
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	3	USERS	0.65	1.95	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9
HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1					
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
MAIN STAIRCASE	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50					
BALCONY	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
FIRE EXIT STAIRCASE	2	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
CONNECTING BRIDGE	3	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	30					
TOTAL AREA (USERS)					1013.2	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)				1334.87
						TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)				2348.07
						TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)				3287.30
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)				4383.06
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)				4470.73
						TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)				4471.00

Table 3.2.2. 3 SP TFA Museum

FLOOR LEVEL	TOTAL AREA
GROUND FLOOR LEVEL	4863
SECOND FLOOR LEVEL	4180
THIRD FLOOR LEVEL	4471
TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	13514

Table 3.2.2. 4 SP TGFA Museum

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER GROUND FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE						
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE		
PUBLIC AREA											
FRONT PORCH	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50						
ENTRY & EXIT VESTIBULE	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100						
RECEPTION LOBBY AREA	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100						
PRE FUNCTION LOBBY AREA	2	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	200						
MAIN GRAND STAIRCASE	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50						
PRIVATE LOUNGE ROOM WITH RESTROOM	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20	5	SOFA BENCH	2	0.85	8.5	
						5	COFFEE TABLE	0.6	0.6	1.8	
						1	TV CONSOLE	3	0.4	1.2	
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
VIP LOUNGE ROOM WITH RESTROOM	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20	5	SOFA BENCH	2	0.85	8.5	
						5	COFFEE TABLE	0.6	0.6	1.8	
						1	TV CONSOLE	3	0.4	1.2	
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
GRAND HALL	2	300	USERS AT A TIME	1	600	600	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	216	
						120	TABLE	5	1.2	720	
PUBLIC UTILITY											
HYDRAULIC PASSENGER ELEVATOR	2	20	USERS AT A TIME	1	40						
ELEVATOR MACHINE ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	ELEVATOR MACHINE	2	2	8	
ESCALATOR	2	20	USERS AT A TIME	1	40						
UTILITIES LOWER LEFT											
AHU ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	AHU MACHINE	2	2	4	
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
LACTATION ROOM WITH RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1	1	1	SOFA BENCH	1.85	0.85	1.5725	
						1	TABLE	0.8	0.8	0.64	
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	1	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	14						
UTILITIES LOWER RIGHT											
AHU ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	AHU MACHINE	2	2	4	
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
SECURITY ROOM WITH RESTROOM	1	3	EMPLOYEE	1	3	3	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.08	
						3	TABLE	1	0.8	2.4	
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	1	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	14						
UTILITIES UPPER LEFT & RIGHT											
AHU ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	AHU MACHINE	2	2	8	
ELECTRICAL ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8	
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8	
GARBAGE CHUTE						2	GARBAGE CHUTE	1	0.8	1.6	
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	2	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	28						
PUBLIC RESTROOM											
MALE RESTROOM	2	7	USERS	0.65	9.1	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05	
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6	
						4	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.96	
FEMALE RESTROOM	2	11	USERS	0.65	14.3	11	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	14.85	
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
PWD RESTROOM	2	1	USER	1.5	3	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
UTILITY ROOM	2	1	EMPLOYEE	1	2						
PIPE CHASE	2	1	EMPLOYEE	1	2						
EMPLOYEE RESTROOM											
MALE RESTROOM	1	5	USERS	0.65	3.25	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7	
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6	
						3	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.72	
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	4	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	5.4	
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6	
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2						
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2						
KITCHEN											
DUMBWAITER						4	DUMBWAITER	0.9	1	3.6	
PANTRY	4	2	EMPLOYEE	1	8	12	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	10.8	
COLD STORAGE	4	2	EMPLOYEE	1	8	12	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	10.8	
DRY STORAGE	4	2	EMPLOYEE	1	8	12	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	10.8	
GAS STORAGE	4	2	EMPLOYEE	1	8	12	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	10.8	
COOKING AREA	4	10	EMPLOYEE	1	40	12	KITCHEN COUNTER	5	1.2	72	
						12	DISHWASHING COUNTER	5	1.2	72	
BACK OF THE HOUSE											
ADMIN LOUNGE ROOM WITH T&B & KITCHENETTE	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6	
						1	DINING TABLE	3	1	3	
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
						1	SHOWER	1.4	0.9	1.26	
						1	KITCHEN COUNTER	2	0.6	1.2	
ADMIN MANAGEMENT OFFICE	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6	
						10	OFFICE TABLE	1.5	0.6	9	
						1	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	5	
PRIVATE STAIRCASE	1	20	EMPLOYEE AT A TIME	1	20						
HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1						
ELEVATOR MACHINE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	ELEVATOR MACHINE	2	2	4	
STORAGE ROOM	6	2	EMPLOYEE	1	12	6	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	30	
DELIVERY DOCK AREA	1	7	EMPLOYEE	1	7						
TOTAL AREA (USERS)					1482.25	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)					1285.07
						TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)					2767.32
						TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)					3874.25
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)					5165.67
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)					5268.98
						TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)					5269.00

Table 3.2.2. 5 SP GFA Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER SECOND FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE						
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE		
PUBLIC AREA											
LOUNGE AREA	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50						
RENTABLE STALL	4	30	CUSTOMERS AT A TIME	1	120						
MAIN GRAND STAIRCASE	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50						
PRE-FUNCTION LOBBY	2	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	200						
FUNCTION HALL	6	100	USERS AT A TIME	1	600	600	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	216	
						120	TABLE	3	1.2	432	
PUBLIC UTILITY											
HYDRAULIC PASSENGER ELEVATOR	2	20	USERS AT A TIME	1	40						
STORAGE ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8	
ESCALATOR	2	50	USERS AT A TIME	1	100						
UTILITIES LOWER LEFT											
AHU ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	AHU MACHINE	2	2	4	
						1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
LACTATION ROOM WITH RESTROOM	1	3	USER	1	3	2	SOFA BENCH	2	0.85	3.4	
						2	TABLE	0.8	0.8	1.28	
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	1	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	14						
UTILITIES LOWER RIGHT											
AHU ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	AHU MACHINE	2	2	4	
						1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	0.9	
SECURITY ROOM WITH RESTROOM	1	3	EMPLOYEE	1	3	3	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.08	
						3	TABLE	1	0.8	2.4	
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	1	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	14						
UTILITIES UPPER LEFT & RIGHT											
AHU ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	AHU MACHINE	2	2	8	
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8	
ELECTRICAL ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8	
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8	
GARBAGE CHUTE						2	GARBAGE CHUTE	1	0.8	1.6	
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	2	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	28						
PUBLIC RESTROOM											
MALE RESTROOM	2	7	USERS	0.65	9.1	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05	
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6	
						4	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.96	
FEMALE RESTROOM	2	11	USERS	0.65	14.3	11	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	14.85	
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
PWD RESTROOM	2	1	USER	1.5	3	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
UTILITY ROOM	2	1	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1	0.5	0.5	
PIPE CHASE	2	1	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1	0.5	0.5	
EMPLOYEE RESTROOM											
MALE RESTROOM	1	5	USERS	0.65	3.25	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7	
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6	
						3	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.72	
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	4	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	5.4	
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72	
UTILITY ROOM	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1	1	STORAGE CABINET	1	0.5	0.5	
PIPE CHASE	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1	1	STORAGE CABINET	1	0.5	0.5	
KITCHEN											
DUMBWAITER						4	DUMBWAITER	0.9	1	3.6	
PANTRY	4	2	EMPLOYEE	1	8	8	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	7.2	
COLD STORAGE	4	2	EMPLOYEE	1	8	8	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	7.2	
DRY STORAGE	4	2	EMPLOYEE	1	8	8	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	7.2	
GAS STORAGE	4	2	EMPLOYEE	1	8	8	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	7.2	
COOKING AREA	4	8	EMPLOYEE	1	32	12	KITCHEN COUNTER	2	1.2	28.8	
						12	DISHWASHING COUNTER	4	0.6	28.8	
						12	STORAGE RACK	4	0.6	28.8	
BACK OF THE HOUSE											
STAFF LOUNGE ROOM WITH T&B & KITCHENETTE	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6	
						1	DINING TABLE	3	1.2	3.6	
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
						1	SHOWER	1.4	1	1.4	
						1	KITCHEN COUNTER	2	0.6	1.2	
STAFF OFFICE	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6	
						10	OFFICE TABLE	1.5	0.6	9	
						3	STORAGE CABINET	4	0.5	6	
PRIVATE STAIRCASE	1	20	EMPLOYEE AT A TIME	1	20						
HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1						
STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	2	STORAGE CABINET	2	1	4	
STORAGE ROOM	6	3	EMPLOYEE	1	18	18	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	90	
POSTER BALCONY AREA	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10						
TOTAL AREA (USERS)					1423.25	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)					964.00
						TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)					2387.25
						TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)					3342.15
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)					4456.20
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)					4545.32
						TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)					4545.00

Table 3.2.2. 6 SP SFA Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER THIRD FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
PUBLIC AREA										
RENTABLE STALL	6	30	CUSTOMERS AT A TIME	1	180					
MAIN GRAND STAIRCASE	1	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	50					
GALLERY DISPLAY AREA	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
MEETING ROOM	6	20	USERS AT A TIME	1	120	120	CHAIR	0.8	0.8	76.8
						24	TABLE	5	0.6	72
PUBLIC UTILITY										
HYDRAULIC PASSENGER ELEVATOR	2	20	USERS AT A TIME	1	40					
STORAGE ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	4	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	20
ESCALATOR	2	50	USERS AT A TIME	1	100					
UTILITIES LOWER LEFT										
AHU ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	AHU MACHINE	2	2	4
						1	STORAGE CABINET	2	0.6	1.2
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	0.6	3
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	0.6	3
LACTATION ROOM WITH RESTROOM	1	3	USER	1	3	2	SOFA BENCH	2	0.85	3.4
						2	TABLE	0.8	0.8	1.28
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	1	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	14					
LED DISPLAY MAINTENANCE AREA	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5					
UTILITIES LOWER RIGHT										
AHU ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	AHU MACHINE	2	2	4
						1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	1	1.5
ELECTRICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	1	1.5
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	1	1.5
TECHNICAL ROOM	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	5	OFFICE CHAIR	0.8	0.8	3.2
						5	OFFICE TABLE	2	0.6	6
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	1	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	14					
UTILITIES UPPER LEFT & RIGHT										
TECHNICAL ROOM	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	5	OFFICE CHAIR	1.85	0.85	7.8625
						5	OFFICE TABLE	0.8	0.8	3.2
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.6	1.8
AHU ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	AHU MACHINE	2	2	8
						2	STORAGE CABINET	2	0.6	2.4
STORAGE ROOM	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1					
ELECTRICAL ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	10
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	2	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	10
GARBAGE CHUTE	2	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	28	2	GARBAGE CHUTE	1	0.8	1.6
FIRE ESCAPE STAIRCASE	2	20	USERS AT A TIME	0.7	28					
PUBLIC RESTROOM										
MALE RESTROOM	1	7	USERS	0.65	4.55	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						4	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.96
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	11	USERS	0.65	7.15	11	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	14.85
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	5
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	5
EMPLOYEE RESTROOM										
MALE RESTROOM	1	5	USERS	0.65	3.25	2	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	2.7
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						3	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.72
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	4	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	5.4
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	5
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	5
CAFÉ DINING										
DUMBWAITER						1	DUMBWAITER	0.9	1	0.9
PANTRY	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	5	STORAGE RACK	5	1	25
COLD STORAGE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	5	STORAGE RACK	5	1	25
DRY STORAGE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	5	STORAGE RACK	5	1	25
GAS STORAGE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	5	STORAGE RACK	5	1	25
COOKING AREA	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	12	KITCHEN COUNTER	5	1.2	7.2
						12	DISHWASHING COUNTER	5	0.6	3.6
						12	STORAGE RACK	5	1	60
DINING AREA	1	30	CUSTOMERS AT A TIME	1	30	30	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	10.8
						6	TABLE	1.2	0.8	5.76
BACK OF THE HOUSE										
STAFF LOUNGE ROOM WITH T&H & KITCHENETTE	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
						1	DINING TABLE	3	1.2	3.6
						1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	SHOWER	1.4	1	1.4
						1	KITCHEN COUNTER	2	0.6	1.2
STAFF OFFICE	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
						10	OFFICE TABLE	2	0.6	12
						3	STORAGE CABINET	2	0.6	3.6
PRIVATE STAIRCASE	1	20	EMPLOYEE AT A TIME	1	20					
HYDRAULIC FREIGHT ELEVATOR	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1					
STORAGE ROOM	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	5	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	25
AUDITORIUM										
FOYER	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
AUDITORIUM LOBBY AREA	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
TICKET BOOTH	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	1	LONG COUNTER	5	1	5
						5	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.8
CONCESSION STAND	1	6	EMPLOYEE	1	6	3	LONG COUNTER	5	1	15
						6	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	2.16
AUDITORIUM PUBLIC RESTROOM										
MALE RESTROOM	1	8	USERS	0.65	5.2	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						4	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.96
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	11	USERS	0.65	7.15	11	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	14.85
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	1	5
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	1.2	6
STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	5	1.2	6
AUDITORIUM MAIN HOUSE										
ELEVATED SEATING AREA	1	300	USERS	1	300	300	AUDITORIUM CHAIR	0.8	0.8	192
SEATING AREA	1	100	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100	100	AUDITORIUM CHAIR	0.8	0.8	64
STAGE AREA	1	50	USERS AT A TIME	1.5	50					
BACKSTAGE / PREPARATION AREA	1	50	USERS AT A TIME	1.5	75					
FEMALE DRESSING ROOM	1	10	USERS AT A TIME	1.2	12	10	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
						10	TABLE	2	0.6	12
MALE DRESSING ROOM	1	10	USERS AT A TIME	1.2	12	10	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
						10	TABLE	2	0.6	12
STORAGE ROOM	2	5	EMPLOYEE	1	10	6	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	1	45
					TOTAL AREA (USERS)	1603.9				
								TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)		1037.76
								TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)		2641.66
								TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)		3698.33
								TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)		4931.10
								TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)		5029.73
								TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)		5030.00

Table 3.2.2. 7 SP TFA Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER ROOF DECK AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS		AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
						QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
ROOF DECK AREA											
HELIPAD	1	20	EMPLOYEE	1	20	1	HELIPAD	20	20	400	
SERVICE STAIRCASE	1	20	EMPLOYEE	1	20	1	STAIRCASE	6	3	18	
SKYLIGHT WINDOW						1	SKYLIGHT WINDOW PANEL	25	15	375	
COOLING TOWER AREA						10	COOLING TOWER	5	5	250	
					TOTAL AREA (USERS)	40				TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)	1043.00
								TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)		1083.00	
								TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)		1516.20	
								TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)		2021.60	
								TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)		2062.03	
								TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)		2062.00	

Table 3.2.2. 8 SP RFA Convention Center

FLOOR LEVEL	TOTAL AREA
GROUND FLOOR LEVEL	5269
SECOND FLOOR LEVEL	4545
THIRD FLOOR LEVEL	5030
ROOF DECK LEVEL	2062
TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	16906

Table 3.2.2. 9 SP TGFA Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER GROUND FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
FRONT OF THE HOUSE										
PORCH	1	5	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	5					
RECEPTION / LOBBY AREA	1	25	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	25					
WAITING AREA	2	40	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	80	40	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	14.4
						6	CONCESSION STAND	2	0.6	7.2
TICKET BOOTH	1	6	EMPLOYEE	1	6	6	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	2.16
						1	LONG TICKET TABLE	2	0.8	1.6
						3	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	1.8
STAFF OFFICE & LOUNGE ROOM	1	10	EMPLOYEE	1	10	5	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.8
						4	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	2.4
						1	SOFA BENCH	1.5	0.8	1.2
FOYER	2	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	40					
MALE RESTROOMS										
MALE RESTROOM INSIDE FOYER	1	11	USERS	0.65	7.15	5	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	6.75
						1	LAVATORY	3.5	0.6	2.1
						6	URINAL	0.4	0.6	1.44
MALE RESTROOM	1	8	USERS	0.65	5.2	4	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	5.4
						1	LAVATORY	3.5	0.6	2.1
						4	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.96
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2					
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2					
FEMALE RESTROOMS										
FEMALE RESTROOM INSIDE FOYER	1	13	USERS	0.65	8.45	13	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	17.55
						1	LAVATORY	3.6	0.6	2.16
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	4	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	5.4
						1	LAVATORY	3	0.6	1.8
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2					
PIPE CHASE	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2					
MAIN THEATER HOUSE										
ELEVATED SEATING AREA	1	522	VISITORS AT A TIME	0.9	469.8	522	THEATER SEAT	0.8	0.8	334.08
SEATING AREA	1	238	VISITORS AT A TIME	0.9	214.2	238	THEATER SEAT	0.8	0.8	152.32
THRUST STAGE AREA	1	100	PERFORMERS AT A TIME	1.5	150					
AHU ROOM	2	2	EMPLOYEE	1	4	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.5	0.6
						1	AHU MACHINE	2	2	4
FIRST AID CLINIC	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	CLINIC BED	1.8	0.9	1.62
						2	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.72
		2	PATIENT AT A TIME	1	2	1	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	0.6
SECURITY ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	2	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	1.2
						2	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.72
FOYER	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
ELEVATOR MACHINE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	1	ELEVATOR MACHINE	1	1	1
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20					
FIRE EXIT STAIRCASE	1	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	10					
GRAND STAIRCASE	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100					
BACK STAGE AREA / BACK OF THE HOUSE										
BACK STAGE AREA	1	50	PERFORMERS AT A TIME	1	50					
PREPARATION AREA	1	50	PERFORMERS AT A TIME	1	50					
PRODUCTION CREW OFFICE	1	8	EMPLOYEE	1	8	8	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	4.8
						8	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	2.88
MANAGEMENT OFFICE	1	8	EMPLOYEE	1	8	8	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	4.8
						8	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	2.88
TECHNICAL SUPPORT OFFICE	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	5	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	3
						5	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.8
TECHNICAL STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEE	1	2	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.5	1.2
						5	MAKE UP CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.8
MALE DRESSING ROOM	1	10	PERFORMERS AT A TIME	1	10	5	MAKE UP TABLE	1.1	0.6	3.3
						5	WARDROBE CABINET	1	0.6	3
						5	MAKE UP CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.8
FEMALE DRESSING ROOM	1	10	PERFORMERS AT A TIME	1	10	5	MAKE UP TABLE	1.1	0.6	3.3
						5	WARDROBE CABINET	1	0.6	3
						2	TV CONSOLE	2	0.4	1.6
GREEN ROOM	2	10	PERFORMERS AT A TIME	1	20	2	SOFA BENCH	5	0.85	8.5
						2	COFFEE TABLE	2	0.6	2.4
						2	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.48
TOILET & BATH	2	1	USER AT A TIME	1	2	2	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.84
						2	SHOWER	1.5	1	3
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.5	1.2
PROPS STORAGE ROOM	2	3	EMPLOYEE	1	6					
SERVICE STAIRCASE	1	3	EMPLOYEE	1	3					
				TOTAL AREA (USERS)	1450.4	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)				632.70
				TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)					2083.10	
				TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)					2916.34	
				TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)					3888.45	
				TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)					3966.22	
				TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)					3966.00	

Table 3.2.2. 10 SP GFA Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER SECOND FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE						
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE		
FRONT OF THE HOUSE											
DISPLAY AREA	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20						
LED DISPLAY MAINTENANCE AREA	1	3	EMPLOYEE	1	3						
WAITING AREA	2	70	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	140	70	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	17.5	
						6	CONCESSION STAND	1.4	0.6	5.04	
						4	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.44	
LIGHT & SOUNDS ROOM	1	4	EMPLOYEE	1	4	1	STORAGE RACK	1	0.5	0.5	
						4	WORKING TABLE	1	0.55	2.2	
CONTROL ROOM	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	5	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.8	
						5	WORKING TABLE	1	0.55	2.75	
FOYER	2	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	40						
MALE RESTROOMS											
MALE RESTROOM INSIDE FOYER	1	11	USERS	0.65	7.15	5	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	6.75	
						1	LAVATORY	3.5	0.6	2.1	
						6	URINAL	0.4	0.6	1.44	
MALE RESTROOM	1	8	USERS	0.65	5.2	4	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	5.4	
						1	LAVATORY	3.5	0.6	2.1	
						4	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.96	
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
UTILITY ROOM	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1	1	STORAGE CABINET	1	0.5	0.5	
PIPE CHASE	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1	1	STORAGE CABINET	1	0.5	0.5	
FEMALE RESTROOMS											
FEMALE RESTROOM INSIDE FOYER	1	13	USERS	0.65	8.45	13	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	17.55	
						1	LAVATORY	3.6	0.6	2.16	
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	4	USERS	0.65	2.6	4	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	5.4	
						1	LAVATORY	3	0.6	1.8	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42	
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24	
UTILITY ROOM	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1	1	STORAGE CABINET	1	0.5	0.5	
PIPE CHASE	1	1	EMPLOYEE	1	1	1	STORAGE CABINET	1	0.5	0.5	
SECOND FLOOR MAIN THEATER HOUSE											
ELEVATED SEATING AREA	1	440	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	440	440	THEATER SEAT	0.8	0.8	281.6	
FOYER	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100						
FIRE EXIT STAIRCASE	1	10	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	10						
GRAND STAIRCASE	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100						
BALCONY	2	50	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	100						
STORAGE ROOM	2	3	EMPLOYEE	1	6	2	STORAGE RACK	1	0.5	1	
STORAGE ROOM	1	3	EMPLOYEE	1	3	2	STORAGE RACK	1	0.5	1	
HYDRAULIC ELEVATOR	1	20	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	20						
ROOF DECK AREA	1	5	EMPLOYEE	1	5	8	SOLAR PANEL	1	1.6	12.8	
						1	PRIVATE STAIRCASE	3.3	2.25	7.425	
						2	COOLING TOWERS	1	1	2	
TOTAL AREA (USERS)					1026.4	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)					386.76
						TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)					1413.16
						TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)					1978.42
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)					2637.89
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)					2690.65
						TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)					2691.00

Table 3.2.2. 11 SP SFA Theater

FLOOR LEVEL	TOTAL AREA
GROUND FLOOR LEVEL	3966
SECOND FLOOR LEVEL	2691
TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	6657

Table 3.2.2. 12 SP TGFA Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
LOBBY AREA										
GALLERY HALL	1	5	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	5					
LOUNGE AREA	2	5	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	10	3	SOFA BENCH	1.2	0.8	2.88
						2	COFFEE TABLE	0.4	0.4	0.32
						2	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.72
						1	DESK	1	0.6	0.6
BLACK BOX THEATER 1										
SEATING AREA	1	200	VISITORS	0.9	180	200	THEATER SEAT	0.6	0.6	72
STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEES AT A TIME	1	2	1	STORAGE RACK	1.2	0.5	0.6
TECHNICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEES	0.9	1.8	2	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	1.2
						2	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.72
						1	RACK FOR EQUIPMENT	1.2	0.5	0.6
BLACK BOX THEATER 2										
SEATING AREA	1	200	VISITORS	0.9	180	200	THEATER SEAT	0.6	0.6	72
STORAGE ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEES AT A TIME	1	2	1	STORAGE RACK	1.2	0.5	0.6
TECHNICAL ROOM	1	2	EMPLOYEES	0.9	1.8	2	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	1.2
						2	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.72
						1	RACK FOR EQUIPMENT	1.2	0.5	0.6
PRODUCTION OFFICE										
OFFICE	1	2	EMPLOYEES	0.9	1.8	2	WORKING TABLE	1	0.6	1.2
						2	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	0.72
MAIN UTILITY CORE										
WATER PUMP MACHINE ROOM	1	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	1	WATER PUMP MACHINE	1	1	1
E.M. ROOM	1	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.5	0.6
FIRE PUMP MACHINE ROOM	1	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	1	FIRE PUMP MACHINE	1	1	1
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.5	0.6
PIPE CHASE CABINET	1	0	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	0	0					
UTILITY CABINET	1	0	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	0	0					
GENERATOR ROOM	1	3	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	3	2	GENERATOR MACHINE	1	1	2
RESTROOMS										
MALE RESTROOM	1	10	USERS	0.65	6.5	5	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	6.75
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						5	URINAL	0.4	0.6	1.2
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	11	USERS	0.65	7.15	11	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	14.85
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
TOTAL AREA (USERS)					410.55	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)				187.14
						TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)				597.69
						TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)				836.77
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)				1115.69
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)				1138.00
						TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)				1138.00

Table 3.2.2. 13 SP TGFA Black Box Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK: COMMERCIAL BUILDING GROUND

FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
RENTABLE STALL										
ADMIN OFFICE	5	2	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
						10	OFFICE TABLE	1	0.6	6
KITCHENETTE	5	2	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	DINING CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
						5	DINING TABLE	0.8	0.6	2.4
						5	LAVATORY	1	0.6	3
TOILET & BATH	5	1	EMPLOYEE	1	5	5	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	1.2
						5	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	2.1
						5	SHOWER	1.5	1	7.5
WORK / STORAGE ROOM	5	5	EMPLOYEE	1	25	20	STORAGE RACK	1.2	0.6	14.4
						5	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	1.8
SALES AREA	5	30	CUSTOMERS AT A TIME	1	150	5	SALES COUNTER	2	0.6	6
						50	DISPLAY RACK	4	0.8	160
LOCAL FOOD VENDOR STALL SPACE	1	150	CUSTOMERS AT A TIME	1	150	15	STALL	4	4	240
MAIN UTILITY CORE										
STAIRCASE	1	17	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	17					
WATER & FIRE PUMP MACHINE ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	2	WATER PUMP MACHINE	2	2	8
E.M. ROOM	1	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	3	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	2.16
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	4	4	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	2.88
PIPE CHASE	2	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	4	4	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	2.88
GENERATOR ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	3	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	2.16
						3	GENERATOR MACHINE	2	2	12
RESTROOMS										
MALE RESTROOM	1	6	USERS	0.65	3.9	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						3	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.72
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	5	USERS	0.65	3.25	5	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	6.75
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
					TOTAL AREA (USERS)	395.65	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)			495.66
					TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)					891.31
					TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)					1247.83
					TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)					1663.78
					TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)					1697.05
					TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)					1697.00

Table 3.2.2. 14 SP GFA Commercial Building

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
RENTABLE STALL										
ADMIN OFFICE	10	1	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	3.6
						10	OFFICE TABLE	2.1	0.6	12.6
KITCHENETTE	10	2	EMPLOYEE	1	20	20	DINING CHAIR	0.6	0.6	7.2
						10	DINING TABLE	2.1	0.6	12.6
						10	LAVATORY	1.5	0.6	9
TOILET & BATH	10	1	EMPLOYEE	1	10	10	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	2.4
						10	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	4.2
						10	SHOWER	1.5	1	15
WORK / STORAGE ROOM	10	5	EMPLOYEE	1	50	50	STORAGE RACK	2	0.8	80
						20	CHAIR	0.6	0.6	7.2
SALES AREA	10	30	CUSTOMERS AT A TIME	1	300	10	SALES COUNTER	2.3	0.8	18.4
						100	DISPLAY RACK	4	0.8	320
BALCONY	1	100	CUSTOMERS AT A TIME	1	100					
MAIN UTILITY CORE										
STAIRCASE	1	17	VISITORS AT A TIME	1	17					
E.M. ROOM	1	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.8	2.4
UTILITY ROOM	2	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	4	4	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.8	4.8
PIPE CHASE	2	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	4	4	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.8	4.8
STORAGE ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	5	STORAGE CABINET	1.5	0.8	6
RESTROOMS										
MALE RESTROOM	1	6	USERS	0.65	3.9	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						3	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.72
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	5	USERS	0.65	3.25	5	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	6.75
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
					TOTAL AREA (USERS)	530.65	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)			524.18
					TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)					1054.83
					TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)					1476.76
					TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)					1969.02
					TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)					2008.40
					TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)					2008.00

Table 3.2.2. 15 SP SFA Commercial Building

FLOOR LEVEL	TOTAL AREA
GROUND FLOOR LEVEL	1697
SECOND FLOOR LEVEL	2008
TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	3705

Table 3.2.2. 16 SP SFA Commercial Building

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK: OPEN KITCHEN

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
OPEN KITCHEN 1 - 6										
ADMIN OFFICE	6	1	EMPLOYEES	1	6	6	WORKING TABLE	2	0.6	7.2
						6	OFFICE CHAIR	0.6	0.6	2.16
KITCHENETTE	6	2	EMPLOYEES	1	12	6	DINING TABLE	2	0.6	7.2
						12	DINING CHAIR	0.6	0.6	4.32
						6	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	4.32
TOILET & BATH	6	1	EMPLOYEES	1	6	6	SHOWER	1.4	1	8.4
						6	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	1.44
						6	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	2.52
PANTRY	6	2	EMPLOYEES	1	12	18	STORAGE RACK	2	0.5	18
COLD STORAGE	6	2	EMPLOYEES	1	12	12	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	10.8
DRY STORAGE	6	2	EMPLOYEES	1	12	12	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	10.8
GAS STORAGE	6	2	EMPLOYEES	1	12	12	STORAGE RACK	1.5	0.6	10.8
OPEN KITCHEN	6	30	DINERS	0.9	162	6	LONG DINING TABLE	2.5	1.2	18
						24	HIGH DINING TABLE	2.5	0.6	36
						180	DINING CHAIR	0.6	0.6	64.8
						6	KITCHEN COUNTER	4.2	3	75.6
MAIN UTILITY CORE										
E.M. ROOM	1	1	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	1	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44
UTILITY ROOM	2	1	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44
PIPE CHASE	2	1	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44
GENERATOR ROOM	1	3	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	3	3	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.5	1.8
						3	GENERATOR MACHINE	1	2	6
RESTROOMS										
MALE RESTROOM	1	6	USERS	0.65	3.9	3	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	4.05
						1	LAVATORY	1	0.6	0.6
						3	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.72
FEMALE RESTROOM	1	5	USERS	0.65	3.25	5	WATER CLOSET	1.5	0.9	6.75
						1	LAVATORY	1.2	0.6	0.72
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
PWD RESTROOM	1	1	USER	1.5	1.5	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24
						1	LAVATORY	0.7	0.6	0.42
						1	URINAL	0.4	0.6	0.24
TOTAL AREA (USERS)					250.65	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)				308.46
						TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)				559.11
						TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)				782.75
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)				1043.67
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)				1064.55
						TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)				1065.00

Table 3.2.2. 17 SP TGFA Open Kitchen

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
MAIN UTILITY CORE										
MRF ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	5	STORAGE CABINET	5	0.8	20
STORAGE ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	5	STORAGE CABINET	5	0.8	20
TOTAL AREA (USERS)					10	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)				40
						TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)				50
						TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)				70.00
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)				93.33
						TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)				95.20
						TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)				95

Table 3.2.2. 18 SP TGFA Open Kitchen Utility

MAIN UTILITY CORE

NAME OF SPACE / ROOM	NO. OF UNITS	NO. OF USERS	AREA NEEDED PER USER	TOTAL AREA OF USER	FURNITURE, FIXTURE, EQUIPMENT, MACHINE					
					QTY.	NAME OF FURNITURE	LENGTH	WIDTH	TOTAL AREA OF FURNITURE	
MAIN UTILITY CORE										
E.M. ROOM	1	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	0.72
UTILITY ROOM	1	2	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	2	1	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	0.72
STORAGE ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44
						2	STORAGE RACK	1.2	0.6	1.44
FIRE PUMP MACHINE ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	2	FIRE PUMP MACHINE	2	2	8
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44
WATER PUMP MACHINE ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	2	WATER PUMP MACHINE	2	2	8
						2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44
GENERATOR ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	2	STORAGE CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44
						4	GENERATOR MACHINE	2	2	16
MRF ROOM	1	5	MAINTENANCE STAFF AT A TIME	1	5	2	STORAGE RACK	1.2	0.6	1.44
				TOTAL AREA (USERS)	29	TOTAL AREA (FURNITURE)				42.08
				TOTAL FLOOR AREA (TFA)					71.08	
				TFA + CIRCULATION (40%)					99.51	
				TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY (75%)					132.68	
				TFA + CIRCULATION / EFFICIENCY + WALLS (2%)					135.34	
				TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA (SQ. MTS.)					135	

Table 3.2.2. 19 SP TGFA Main Utility Core

TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA COMPUTATION

NAME OF SPACE	SPACE PROGRAMMING TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	UNIT
MUSEUM	13514	SQM
CONVENTION CENTER	16906	SQM
THEATER	6657	SQM
BLACK BOX THEATER	1138	SQM
COMMERCIAL BUILDING	3705	SQM
OPEN KITCHEN	1065	SQM
UTILITY CORE	135	SQM

Table 3.2.2. 20 TGFA Computation

CHAPTER 4: DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

CONTENTS:

4.1 SPACE MANAGEMENT STUDIES AND ANALYSIS

4.2 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN AND DRAWING PRESENTATIONS

4.3 CONCLUSION

4.1 SPACE MANAGEMENT STUDIES AND ANALYSIS

4.1.1 BUBBLE DIAGRAMS

4.1.2 SCHEMATIC DIAGRAMS WITH SCHEDULE OF FLOOR AREAS

4.1.3 MATRIX DIAGRAMS

4.1.4 ACOUSTIC DIAGRAMS AND MOOD BOARDS

4.1.5 MUSEUM TOUR GUIDE DIAGRAM

4.1.1 BUBBLE DIAGRAMS

Bubble diagrams are visual representation of the project's initial concept in the form of a bubble sketch. This type of diagram was utilized to organize and conceptualize the spatial relationship of the spaces within the project.

INDU: SITE DEVELOPMENT PLAN

Figure 4.1.1. 1 BD SDP

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM

Figure 4.1.1. 2 BD GFL Museum

Figure 4.1.1. 3 BD SFL Museum

Figure 4.1.1. 4 BD TFL Museum

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER

Figure 4.1.1. 5 BD GFL Convention Center

Figure 4.1.1. 6 BD SFL Convention Center

Figure 4.1.1. 7 BD TFL Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER

THEATER
GROUND FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGEND	
■	PRIVATE
■	PUBLIC
■	UTILITIES
■	FIRE EXIT
	ACCESS

Figure 4.1.1. 8 BD GFL Theater

THEATER
SECOND FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGEND	
■	PRIVATE
■	PUBLIC
■	UTILITIES
■	FIRE EXIT
	ACCESS

Figure 4.1.1. 9 BD SFL Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER

BLACK BOX THEATER
 GROUND FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

Figure 4.1.1. 10 BD GFL Black Box Theater

MAIN UTILITY CORE

MAIN UTILITY CORE
 GROUND FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

Figure 4.1.1. 11 BD GFL Main Utility Core

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK: COMMERCIAL BUILDING

Figure 4.1.1. 12 BD GFL Commercial Building

Figure 4.1.1. 13 BD SFL Commercial Building

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK: OPEN KITCHEN

Figure 4.1.1. 14 BD GFL Open Kitchen

4.1.2 SCHEMATIC DIAGRAMS WITH SCHEDULE OF FLOOR AREAS

Schematic diagrams are visual representations that shows the project’s initial building form and shape. This type of diagram was utilized to create the project’s main building form, concept, and in creating properly zoned spaces and efficient circulation.

INDU: SITE DEVELOPMENT PLAN

Figure 4.1.2. 1 SD SDP

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM

Figure 4.1.2. 2 SD GFL & SFL Museum

MUSEUM

THIRD FLOOR LAYOUT

NOT TO SCALE

SCHEDULE OF FLOOR AREAS	
PRIVATE	13,333 SQM
PUBLIC	1,042,772 SQM
CIRCULATION	10,718 SQM
CORE	12,145.54 SQM
TOTAL	1,169,070 SQM

LEGEND	
PRIVATE	GREEN
PUBLIC	RED
CIRCULATION	YELLOW
CORE	BLUE

ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	
GROUND FLOOR AREA	4868.2 SQM
SECOND FLOOR AREA	4184.54 SQM
THIRD FLOOR AREA	4476.54 SQM
	13529.28 SQM

Figure 4.1.2. 3 SD TFL Museum

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER

Figure 4.1.2. 4 SD GFL Convention Center

CONVENTION CENTER
SECOND FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGEND

Green	PRIVATE
Cyan	PUBLIC
Yellow	UTILITIES
Red	FIRE EXIT

SCHEDULE OF FLOOR AREAS

PRIVATE	514.51 SQM
PUBLIC	3164.56 SQM
UTILITIES	610 SQM
WALLS	261.80 SQM
ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	4550.87 SQM

Figure 4.1.2. 5 SD SFL Convention Center

CONVENTION CENTER
THIRD FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGEND	
■	PRIVATE
■	PUBLIC
■	UTILITIES
■	FIRE EXIT

SCHEDULE OF FLOOR AREAS	
■ PRIVATE	552.09 SQM
■ PUBLIC	3523.08 SQM
■ UTILITIES	354.85 SQM
■ WALLS	605.00 SQM
ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: 5035.02 SQM	

ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	
GROUND FLOOR AREA	5274.00 SQM
SECOND FLOOR AREA	4550.87 SQM
THIRD FLOOR AREA	5035.02 SQM
ROOF DECK AREA	3012 SQM
	17871.89 SQM

CONVENTION CENTER
ROOF DECK LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGENDS	
■	PRIVATE

SCHEDULE OF FLOOR AREAS	
■ PRIVATE	3012.00 SQM
ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: 3012.00 SQM	

Figure 4.1.2. 6 SD TFL & RDL Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER

THEATER
GROUND FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGEND		SCHEDULE OF FLOOR AREAS	
Green	PRIVATE	Green	PRIVATE 467.00 SQM
Blue	PUBLIC	Blue	PUBLIC 3071.55 SQM
Yellow	UTILITIES	Yellow	UTILITIES 298.75 SQM
Red	FIRE EXIT	Grey	WALLS 136.50 SQM
		ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA 3971.3 SQM	

Figure 4.1.2. 7 SD GFL Theater

THEATER

SECOND FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGEND	
■	PRIVATE
■	PUBLIC
■	UTILITIES
■	FIRE EXIT

SCHEDULE OF FLOOR AREAS		
■	PRIVATE	712.53 SQM
■	PUBLIC	1729.87 SQM
■	UTILITIES	163.80 SQM
■	WALLS	89.93 SQM
ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA		2696.13 SQM

ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	
GROUND FLOOR AREA	3971.3 SQM
SECOND FLOOR AREA	2696.13 SQM
	6667.43 SQM

Figure 4.1.2. 8 SD SFL Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER

BLACK BOX THEATER GROUND FLOOR LAYOUT NOT TO SCALE

Figure 4.1.2. 9 SD GFL Black Box Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK: COMMERCIAL BUILDING

Figure 4.1.2. 10 SD GFL & SFL Commercial Building

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK: OPEN KITCHEN

Figure 4.1.2. 11 SD GFL Open Kitchen

MAIN UTILITY CORE

Figure 4.1.2. 12 SD GFL Main Utility Core

SUMMARY OF ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA

NAME OF SPACE	ACTUAL TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA	UNIT
MUSEUM	13529.28	SQM
CONVENTION CENTER	17871.89	SQM
THEATER	6667.43	SQM
BLACK BOX THEATER	1143	SQM
COMMERCIAL BUILDING	3715.81	SQM
OPEN KICTHEN	1070	SQM
UTILITY CORE	140	SQM

Table 4.1.2. 1 Summary Actual TGFA

4.1.3 MATRIX DIAGRAMS

Matrix Diagram is a visual representation that shows the spatial relationship of spaces and their relevant connections between the building's spaces. This type of diagram was utilized to show the connection and accessibility of individual spaces within the building project.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM

Figure 4.1.3. 1 MD GFL Museum

MUSEUM
SECOND FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGENDS	
	DIRECT ACCESS
	INDIRECT ACCESS

Figure 4.1.3. 2 MD SFL Museum

MUSEUM
THIRD FLOOR LAYOUT
 NOT TO SCALE

LEGENDS	
	DIRECT ACCESS
	INDIRECT ACCESS

Figure 4.1.3. 3 MD TFL Museum

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER

Figure 4.1.3. 4 MD GFL Convention Center

Figure 4.1.3. 5 MD SFL Convention Center

Figure 4.1.3. 6 MD TFL & RDL Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER

Figure 4.1.3. 7 MD GFL Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK: COMMERCIAL BUILDING

Figure 4.1.3. 10 MD GFL Commercial Building

Figure 4.1.3. 11 MD SFL Commercial Building

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK: OPEN KITCHEN

Figure 4.1.3. 12 MD GFL Open Kitchen

MAIN UTILITY CORE

Figure 4.1.3. 13 MD GFL Main Utility Core

SITE DEVELOPMENT PLAN

Figure 4.1.3. 14 MD SDP

4.1.4 ACOUSTIC DIAGRAMS AND MOOD BOARDS

Acoustic Diagrams are visual representations that showcases how sound waves behave and affect a room. This type of diagram was utilized to understand how to create an acoustically sound room.

4.1.4.1 AUDITORIUM ACOUSTIC DIAGRAMS

Figure 4.1.4.1. 1 Auditorium Acoustic Plan Diagram & Reflected Ceiling Plan

Figure 4.1.4.1. 2 Auditorium Acoustic Section Plan & Diagram

Figure 4.1.4.1. 3 Auditorium Mood Board

4.1.4.2 THEATER ACOUSTIC DIAGRAMS

THEATER / CONCERT HALL

AP
CT

ACOUSTIC GROUND FLOOR PLAN DIAGRAM

SCALE: 1:500 MTS.

THEATER / CONCERT HALL

AP
CT

ACOUSTIC SECOND FLOOR PLAN DIAGRAM

SCALE: 1:500 MTS.

Figure 4.1.4.2. 1 Theater Acoustic Plan Diagrams

THEATER / CONCERT HALL

REFLECTED CEILING PLAN

R
CT

SCALE: 1:400 MTS.

LEGEND	
LED CIRCULAR PIN LIGHT	○
LED SQUARE PIN LIGHT	□
LED TRACK LIGHT	—
LED AMBIENT LIGHT	■
SUSPENDED ACOUSTIC CEILING PANEL	▭

THEATER / CONCERT HALL
ACOUSTIC SECTION PLAN

R
CT

SCALE: 1:400 MTS.

THEATER / CONCERT HALL
ACOUSTIC SECTION DIAGRAM

R
CT

SCALE: 1:400 MTS.

Figure 4.1.4.2. 2 Theater Reflected Ceiling Plan & Acoustic Section Plan & Diagram

Figure 4.1.4.2. 3 Theater Mood Board

4.1.5 MUSEUM TOUR GUIDE DIAGRAM

Figure 4.1.5. 1 Kapampangan Cultural Museum Tour Guide Diagram

The diagram above serves as a tour/navigation guide in visiting and exploring the cultural museum. Through this flow the visitors can explore all exhibits in a hierarchal continuous manner, therefore promoting good traffic flow and cultural immersion.

The flow is as follows: Lobby Area – History Exhibit – Temporary Exhibit – Art Exhibit – Literary Exhibit – Music/Dance Exhibit – Festivals Exhibit – Culinary Exhibit – Workshop Exhibit or Souvenir Shop – Lobby Area.

4.2 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN AND DRAWING PRESENTATIONS

4.2.1 SITE DEVELOPMENT PLAN

4.2.2 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM

4.2.3 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER

4.2.4 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER

4.2.5 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER

4.2.6 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL FOOD PARK

4.2.7 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MAIN PLAZA

4.2.8 SPOT PERSPECTIVES

4.2.1 SITE DEVELOPMENT PLAN

Figure 4.2.1. 1 Site Development Plan

Figure 4.2.1. 2 Aerial Perspective

Figure 4.2.1. 3 Site Analysis Diagram

Figure 4.2.1. 4 Road Network Diagram

Figure 4.2.1. 5 Aerial Perspective View 1

Figure 4.2.1. 6 Aerial Perspective View 2

4.2.2 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM

Figure 4.2.2. 1 SDP Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 2 GFP Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 4 TFP Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 5 RPL Museum

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM
1
 FRONT ELEVATION
 CM SCALE: 1:400 MTS.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM
2
 REAR ELEVATION
 CM SCALE: 1:400 MTS.

Figure 4.2.2. 6 Front & Rear Elevation Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 7 Right & Left-Side Elevation Museum

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM
A LONGITUDINAL SECTION A
 CM SCALE: 1:700 MTS.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MUSEUM
B CROSS SECTION B
 CM SCALE: 1:700 MTS.

Figure 4.2.2. 8 Longitudinal & Cross Section Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 9 Exterior Perspective Morning Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 10 Exterior Perspective Night Museu

Figure 4.2.2. 11 Interior Perspective Library Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 12 Interior Perspective Art Exhibit Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 13 Interior Perspective Culinary Exhibit Museum

Figure 4.2.2. 14 Interior Perspective Festivals Exhibit Museum

4.2.3 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER

Figure 4.2.3. 1 SDP Convention Center

KAPANGANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER

GROUND FLOOR PLAN

SCALE: 1:600 MTS.

Figure 4.2.3. 2 GFP Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER

2 SECOND FLOOR PLAN

SCALE: 1:600 MTS.

Figure 4.2.3. 3 SFP Convention Center

Figure 4.2.3. 4 TFP Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER
ROOF PLAN LAYOUT
 SCALE: 1:6000 MTS.

Figure 4.2.3. 5 RPL Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER
FRONT ELEVATION
 SCALE: 1:300 PTS.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER
REAR ELEVATION
 SCALE: 1:300 PTS.

Figure 4.2.3. 6 Front & Rear Elevation Convention Center

Figure 4.2.3. 7 Right & Left-Side Elevation Convention Center

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER
LONGITUDINAL SECTION A
 SCALE: 1:600 MTS.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL CONVENTION CENTER
CROSS SECTION B
 SCALE: 1:600 MTS.

Figure 4.2.3. 8 Longitudinal & Cross Section Convention Center

Figure 4.2.3. 9 Exterior Perspective Morning Convention Center

Figure 4.2.3. 10 Exterior Perspective Night Convention Center

Figure 4.2.3. 11 Interior Perspective Function Hall Convention Center

Figure 4.2.3. 12 Interior Perspective Grand Hall Convention Center

Figure 4.2.3. 13 Interior Perspective Meeting Room Convention Center

Figure 4.2.3. 14 Interior Perspective Auditorium Convention Center

4.2.4 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER

Figure 4.2.4. 1 SDP Theater & Black Box Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER
GROUND FLOOR PLAN
 I
 CT SCALE: 1:500 MTS.

Figure 4.2.4. 2 GFP Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER
SECOND FLOOR PLAN
 2
 CT SCALE: 1:500 MTS.

Figure 4.2.4. 3 SFP Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER
ROOF PLAN LAYOUT
 3
 CT SCALE: 1:500 MTS.

Figure 4.2.4. 4 RPL Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER
1
 CT FRONT ELEVATION
 SCALE: 1:200 MTS.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER
2
 CT REAR ELEVATION
 SCALE: 1:200 MTS.

Figure 4.2.4. 5 Front & Rear Elevation Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER
RIGHT SIDE ELEVATION
 3 CT SCALE: 1:200 MTS.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL THEATER
LEFT SIDE ELEVATION
 4 CT SCALE: 1:200 MTS.

Figure 4.2.4. 6 Right & Left-Side Elevation Theater

Figure 4.2.4. 8 Exterior Perspective Morning Theater

Figure 4.2.4. 9 Exterior Perspective Night Theater

Figure 4.2.4. 10 Interior Perspective Lobby Theater View 1

Figure 4.2.4. 11 Interior Perspective Lobby Theater View 2

Figure 4.2.4. 12 Interior Perspective Main Theater View 1

Figure 4.2.4. 13 Interior Perspective Main Theater View 2

4.2.5 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER

Figure 4.2.5. 1 GFP & RPL Black Box Theater

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER
LONGITUDINAL SECTION A
 SCALE: 1:250 MTS.

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL BLACK BOX THEATER
CROSS SECTION B
 SCALE: 1:250 MTS.

Figure 4.2.5. 3 Longitudinal & Cross Section Black Box Theater

Figure 4.2.5. 4 Exterior Perspective Morning Black Box Theater

Figure 4.2.5. 5 Exterior Perspective Night Black Box Theater

Figure 4.2.5. 6 Interior Perspective Black Box Theater View 1

Figure 4.2.5. 7 Interior Perspective Black Box Theater View 2

4.2.6.1 COMMERCIAL BUILDING

Figure 4.2.6.1. 1 Floor Plans Commercial Building

Figure 4.2.6.1. 2 Front & Rear Elevation Commercial Building

Figure 4.2.6.1. 3 Right & Left-Side Elevation Commercial Building

Figure 4.2.6.1. 4 Longitudinal & Cross Section Commercial Building

Figure 4.2.6.1. 5 Exterior Perspective Morning Commercial Building

Figure 4.2.6.1. 6 Exterior Perspective Night Commercial Building

4.2.6.2 OPEN KITCHEN

Figure 4.2.6.2. 1 Floor Plans Open Kitchen

Figure 4.2.6.2. 2 Front & Rear Elevation Open Kitchen

Figure 4.2.6.2. 3 Right & Left-Side Elevation Open Kitchen

OPEN KITCHEN
A
LONGITUDINAL SECTION A
 SCALE: 1:300 MTS.

OPEN KITCHEN
B
CROSS SECTION B
 SCALE: 1:300 MTS.

Figure 4.2.6.2. 4 Longitudinal & Cross Section Open Kitchen

Figure 4.2.6.2. 5 Exterior Perspective Morning Open Kitchen

Figure 4.2.6.2. 6 Exterior Perspective Night Open Kitchen

Figure 4.2.6.2. 7 Interior Perspective Open Kitchen View 1

Figure 4.2.6.2. 8 Interior Perspective Open Kitchen View 2

Figure 4.2.6.2. 9 Exterior Perspective Morning Food Park

Figure 4.2.6.2. 10 Exterior Perspective Night Food Park

4.2.7 KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MAIN PLAZA

KAPAMPANGAN CULTURAL MAIN PLAZA
FLOOR PLAN LAYOUT
 SCALE: 1:600 MTS.

Figure 4.2.7. 1 FPL Main Plaza

Figure 4.2.7. 3 Right-Side Elevation Main Plaza

Figure 4.2.7. 4 Exterior Perspective Morning Main Plaza

4.2.8 SPOT PERSPECTIVES

Figure 4.2.8. 1 Main Gate Morning

Figure 4.2.8. 2 Main Gate Night

Figure 4.2.8. 3 Entrance Gate

Figure 4.2.8. 4 Exit Gate

Figure 4.2.8. 5 Food Park Arch Right

Figure 4.2.8. 6 Food Park Arch Left

Figure 4.2.8. 7 Parking Area

Figure 4.2.8. 8 Bus Parking Area

Figure 4.2.8. 9 Main Plaza View 1

Figure 4.2.8. 10 Main Plaza View 2

4.3 CONCLUSION

By proposing this project, the Kapampangan people are provided with a **platform** where their rich and unique cultural heritage take center stage. “Indu” may serve as a **cradle** for Pampanga’s social, cultural, and religious celebrations, embodying the Kapampangan cultural identity and serving as Pampanga’s cultural and architectural icon. An icon that will represent Pampanga’s past, present, and future for the new generations to come.

Furthermore, the three core principles of Architecture according to Vitruvius are Firmitas (Durability), Utilitas (Functionality), and Venustas (Beauty), all of which the proposed project embodies. However, there is a fourth principle that “Indu” the proposed project possessed making it unique among all others, and that is **Spirit**. Its emotional and cultural value towards the Kapampangan people.

To summarize, after thorough research, data gathering, and the formulation of architectural design solutions, it has been concluded that the proposed project entitled “Indu: A Kapampangan Culture, Arts, and Tourism Complex” is a **relevant, feasible, and a significant** project may greatly benefit Pampanga’s community, economy and tourism.

Moreover, it is also concluded that the location of the project which is in Dolores, City of San Fernando is a **strategic and suitable location** to host the said project, for its setting is in the capital of Pampanga where the heart of business and commerce is located.

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